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**APPLIED RESEARCH.
GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

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COOPERATION BETWEEN THE GULF STATES AND RUSSIA: SUCCESSSES AND CHALLENGES FOR NETWORKING

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Abstract: *This article examines the prospects for scientific, technological, and, to some extent, economic cooperation between Russia and the Sultanate of Oman, and describes the existing framework for interaction in this area. It highlights the key legal and regulatory acts and state strategies of Oman that govern the activities of economic actors in the country and set the direction for the country's further socioeconomic development. Promising areas for developing scientific and technological cooperation between the two countries are proposed.*

Keywords: *scientific and technological cooperation, Oman, investments, inter-governmental commission.*

Arab countries, especially since Donald Trump's return to power, are increasingly hedging against the risks of instability associated with trade and currency wars, and are therefore actively pursuing cooperation and scientific collaboration with Russia in the fields of high technology and the fuel and energy complex.

For example, one of the leading Gulf countries has repeatedly sent its scientists and top minds in the field of ICT to us, while also having a clear plan for the socio-economic transformation of its country within the framework of Oman Vision 2040. This means that the sultanate is striving to diversify its foreign policy and meet the challenges of the times and the scientific and technological revolution. Despite the intensification of contacts between Moscow and Muscat at various levels, in particular, the sultanate's participation as a guest of honor at the St. Petersburg International Economic Forum (SPIEF) in 2024, there is a lack of domestic and international analysis of the relationship between the two states, which are awaiting a flourishing period in the area of international cooperation.

The legal basis for expanding the economic partnership was the Intergovernmental Agreement on Trade, Economic, and Technical Cooperation between

Russia and Oman, signed in 1994. It outlined key areas of mutual interest: industry, energy, agriculture, trade, transport, and others. The signing of this document was likely purely formal, as no concrete steps were taken to implement it.

However, on April 22 of this year, as part of efforts to expand and strengthen Russian-Omani cooperation in trade, economic, scientific, and technical spheres, the parties signed a Protocol Amending the Agreement between the Government of the Russian Federation and the Government of the Sultanate of Oman on Trade, Economic, and Technical Cooperation of November 24, 1994. These amendments will allow for the creation of a Joint Russian-Omani Commission on Trade, Economic, and Technical Cooperation, signaling both sides' desire to develop and strengthen bilateral economic ties. This protocol was signed during a visit to the Russian Federation by Omani President Sultan Heytham bin Tariq. In 2023, trade turnover between the countries amounted to \$400 million. Moscow clearly has a positive balance in the trade structure between Russia and Oman. For example, according to 2022 data, Russia exported \$246.8 million worth of goods to Oman and imported \$4 million. The fuel and energy sector remains the most active area of interaction in foreign trade with Oman. Supplies of Russian oil and petroleum products, including naphtha, diesel, and fuel oil, remain important. However, despite the steady growth in mutual trade, it should be noted that the volume of trade is extremely small compared to other external players in the region. For example, Oman's trade turnover with the United States in 2023 amounted to over \$3.4 billion, while with China, which is gaining influence in the region, it was over \$2 billion¹.

Oman needs technology to upgrade its technical infrastructure, while Russia has the necessary solutions. Some progress has already been made in this area. For example, Russian petroleum geologists are collaborating with their Omani colleagues to develop the Sultanate's oil industry. A case in point is the construction of a plant for the production of electric submersible pumps, built by the Russian company Borets in Sohar in 2017². Sohar is also the deepest port in the region, at 25 meters, handling up to 6 million containers annually. The port has a liquefied natural gas terminal, and total investment in port infrastructure amounts to \$40 billion, with China being the largest investor (\$1.7 billion). Near the city is the Sohar Free Economic Zone, one of the largest in the country³.

¹ Reshetnyak I. Russian-Omani economic cooperation: a barrel of honey without a fly in the ointment? Electronic resource. // Primakov Foreign Policy Cooperation Center.— URL: <https://elck.ru/3PPjh5> (date of access 09.21.2025).

² Opening of a Russian plant in the city of Sohar Electronic resource. // Embassy of the Russian Federation in Oman.— URL: <https://yagla.tv/cNVqrRI> (date of access 09.21.2025).

³ Between the ocean and the gulf: Oman wants to prove its attractiveness to investors Electronic resource. // Vedomosti.— URL: <https://yagla.tv/cnPF0JI> (date of access

Logistics also deserves mention: the Sultanate of Oman's unique geographical location at the crossroads of trade routes and its extensive coastline make the country an attractive transport and logistics hub with a well-developed port infrastructure. In this regard, Oman is considering joining the North-South International Transport Corridor (INSTC), which is being actively promoted by Russia. Russia views Oman as a promising partner and an opportunity to enter the Gulf market, valued at \$2 trillion. Oman itself is currently assessing the economic viability and potential of the North-South Corridor and is not ruling out joining it in the future.

Particular attention should be given to possible participation in projects to build a railway network in the country and the potential metro project in Muscat. The capital stretches 60 km along the coast, and a well-developed rail connection may become essential in the near future.

There are 12 industrial zones in the country (including those currently under development). They are being developed by the state-owned Madayn (Cities) agency. The total investment volume is \$ 19.4 billion. Many of these are export- or re-export-oriented, as the country's domestic market is small. Duty-free exports and imports are available within these zones.

In addition to the flagship Duqm Special Economic Zone (linked to the port of the same name), the country also includes the aforementioned Sohar Special Economic Zone, the Salalah Special Economic Zone, the Al Mazuna Special Economic Zone, and the Muscat Knowledge Oasis Special Economic Zone. Total investment in these zones amounts to \$52 billion. They house a wide range of industries, from pharmaceuticals and food production in collaboration with India and elsewhere to solar panels and silicon for them in collaboration with China. To attract foreign investment, Oman has a special authority — the Oman Investment Authority¹.

In October 2025, a multi-sector "Made in Russia" business mission was held in Muscat with the support of the Russian Export Center (REC). It brought together 39 Russian companies representing a wide range of products, from agricultural goods to high technology and robotics. Over the course of two days of negotiations, over 300 meetings were held with over 50 Omani companies. The export potential of the negotiations amounted to \$38 million. In parallel, a business mission was organized in October as part of a business visit by the REC, attended by 15 high-tech companies from Moscow. During the business mission, negotiations were held that facilitated the establishment of working contacts with key Omani partners, including the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology and the Oman Investment Authority. Of particular interest were interactions

09.22.2025).

¹ Oman Investment Authority Сайт.. — URL: <https://oia.gov.om/en> (date of access 24.09.2025).

with the state-owned corporation Madayn and the logistics provider Asyad Group, whose structure includes three deep-water ports and one dry port, as well as free economic zones. Technological Interaction

Oman has small proven oil and natural gas reserves. At current production rates, these reserves will last approximately 20–25 years. These natural resources are located in hard-to-reach areas. At the same time, energy production and processing accounts for 60% of Oman's GDP. The Omani energy sector utilizes the latest technologies and seeks experienced foreign companies to provide technological solutions in exploration, energy production, and processing (see Figure 1). Due to the unique characteristics of its oil fields, including the difficulty of oil extraction due to the geological structure of the oil-bearing strata and the challenging terrain, Oman has had to significantly adapt its oil production industry. This adaptation has resulted in the widespread use of advanced oil production technologies such as horizontal and multilateral drilling, seismic technologies, and others. As a result, the Sultanate of Oman has become one of the leading heavy oil producers. Oil production volumes are experiencing steady growth¹. Russia and Oman could benefit from each other's efforts both in technology exchange and in sharing Russian expertise with their Omani counterparts. According to international rankings and Russian-Omani analytical materials², Russia and Oman have comparative competitive advantages, further confirming the relevance of their economic cooperation (see Figure 2).

Metallurgy and pharmaceuticals are also strategic industries for Oman. For example, with population growth (including due to foreign labor), rising incomes, and the spread of diseases, including lifestyle-related ones (diabetes, obesity, etc.), demand for pharmaceuticals has increased. However, over 90% of pharmaceutical products are imported, including medicines, laboratory equipment, and surgical equipment. According to the Vision 2040 strategy, Oman is interested in importing these products and developing its own pharmaceutical production. Therefore, Russia may consider Oman as a market for pharmaceutical products and a market for investment in the pharmaceutical industry³.

The construction sector plays a key role in Oman's plans to diversify its development. It accounts for 8% of GDP. The industry is expected to grow at an

¹ Russia and Oman: Partnership Prospects Electronic resource. // Roscongress.— URL: <https://clck.ru/3PPjg8> (date of access 09.23.2025).

² Materials of the Russian-Omani Business Council Electronic resource. // Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Russian Federation.— URL: <https://org.tpprf.ru/bc/rus-omn/materials/> (date of access 04.12.2025).

³ Russia and Oman: Partnership Prospects Electronic resource. // Roscongress.— URL: <https://clck.ru/3PPjg8> (date of access 09.23.2025).

average annual rate of over 5% in the coming years. In 2023, 42% of government investment will be directed toward infrastructure projects.

Примеры технологических решений, которые уже использует Оман	Примеры направлений, где Оману необходимы технологии
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Технологии EOR (enhanced oil recovery); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Устьевое оборудование скважин, насосы, трубопроводы;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Горизонтальное и многоствольное бурение; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Буровое оборудование, нефтедобывающее оборудование, устройства для удаления песка из сырой нефти, котлы, буровые штанги, сепараторы, горелки в передвижных резервуарах, оборудование подогрева трубопровода для тяжелой нефти, системы очистки воды и контроля качества, системы закачивания пара;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Сейсмические технологии; 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Солнечная энергия для выработки пара в целях увеличения нефтеотдачи пластов (осуществляется путем сжигания природного газа), солнечная фотогальваническая электростанция; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Оборудование для газовых установок, компрессоры;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Технологии гидроразрыва и искусственного газлифта. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Возведение электростанций, оборудование для выработки электроэнергии, а также технологии в области управления процессами на электростанциях.

Figure 1 — Oman’s Technological Solutions Used and Required
 Source: Prospects for Russian-Omani Economic Cooperation
 Electronic resource. // Roscongress.— URL: <https://clck.ru/3PPjbK>
 (accessed September 23, 2025).

Oman’s construction market is fragmented and competitive due to the presence of major international players (Bechtel, Bouygues, CB&I). According to the approved state budget, Oman plans to finance a number of infrastructure projects in 2023. These include the construction of:

- highways with a total length of over 1,300 km;
- rail links between Sohar and the UAE;
- rail links between Oman and Saudi Arabia;
- Muscat Metro;
- land ports in Buraimi Governorate;
- a smart city in Al Amerat;

Россия	Оман
Наличие широкого рынка сбыта;	Привлекательный инвестиционный климат (69 из 180 по рейтингу ПИИ в 2023 г.);
Богатство природных и энергетических ресурсов;	Стратегическое географическое расположение (точка входа на рынки стран Персидского залива);
Развитость отдельных отраслей с высокой добавленной стоимостью, которые не развиты у Омана (например, фармацевтическая отрасль).	Наличие и использование усовершенствованных технологий по добычи энергетических ресурсов (в связи с их труднодоступностью).

Figure 2 — Key Comparative Competitive Advantages of Russia and Oman

Source: Prospects for Russian-Omani Economic Cooperation

Electronic resource. // Roscongress. — URL: <https://clck.ru/3PPjbK> (accessed September 23, 2025).

If these projects are implemented, there are prospects for increasing Russian exports in a number of areas: cable products, plywood made from common wood species, hot-rolled steel, diesel trucks weighing up to 5 tons, and others. Direct participation in their implementation appears to be the most beneficial for Russia.

Steel production in Oman increased from 300,000 tons in 2012 to 2,900,000 tons in 2023, with an average annual growth rate of 37.84%. Over the past few years, the Omani government has pursued a policy aimed at improving the country's business environment in an effort to attract foreign capital. As a result, a number of large international companies have located their production facilities in the country, including the Indian steelmaker Jindal Shadeed and Brazil's largest mining company, Vale. Oman currently has underdeveloped domestic production of raw materials for metallurgy, so companies rely on imported iron ore and metallized pellets. Several major projects for the construction of new metallurgical facilities have been announced in the country. Among them are:

- Sohar Steel — construction of a steel plant in the Sohar Free Economic Zone. Sohar Steel currently comprises two plants: the Sohar plant, located in the free zone, with a capacity of 600,000 tons of steel and 500,000 tons of rebar per year, and the Sharq Sohar rolling mill with a capacity of 300,000 tons of rebar per year.

• Jindal Shadeed — construction of a steel plant with a capacity of 5 million tons per year in the Duqm Free Economic Zone for the production of automobiles, wind turbines, and consumer goods.

Such projects are particularly relevant given that metal demand in the Persian Gulf is expected to reach 11 million tons per year by 2030¹.

Furthermore, the future growth of Middle Eastern infrastructure will increasingly shift toward innovation and green energy. This creates a paradox: major oil-producing countries will be required to spend their fuel and energy revenues on achieving carbon neutrality and striving for zero carbon in the coming decades. This places the development strategies of these countries in increasing conflict with the raw materials and innovation paradigms, as hydrocarbon exports cannot be fully diversified without compensating participation in growing international scientific and technological cooperation. In such global network and cooperation projects, the leaders of such transformations remain the United States and China, the EU and South Korea, Israel and Canada, Japan and Brazil. This means that at some point, we will have to choose our place either within the ecosystems of these “high-tech” countries or understand that the continued exploitation of resources and the gradual decline of the initially successful and universally sought-after raw materials-based socioeconomic model is becoming a burden to the increasingly high-quality achievement of the UN SDGs and the “green agenda,” renewable energy sources, and “smart” and “energy-saving” development systems.

“Russia is concentrating,” as A. M. Gorchakov wrote. “Old friends” and new partners are increasingly recognizing and understanding the dividends they can derive from mutual projects and from growing network cooperation across the entire spectrum of “high-tech” and creative industries, where our Soviet legacy has allowed us to create scientific schools for many decades and assist the “global South” in matters of sustainable and effective development.

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¹ Foreign Trade Digest: Industry. Sultanate of Oman Electronic resource. // Foreign Trade Center of the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Russian Federation.— URL: <https://yagla.tv/cagXV1d> (date of access 04.12.2025).

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**ON THE EVOLUTION OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING
THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF
FEDERAL MINISTRIES AND DEPARTMENTS OF THE RUSSIAN
FEDERATION**

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Abstract. *The article discusses modern approaches to assessing the effectiveness of digital transformation of federal executive authorities of the Russian Federation. New indicators and criteria used to measure digital maturity and the effectiveness of digital transformation in ministries and departments are revealed. Special attention is paid to metrics focused on practical effects for citizens and the state. The evaluation system has evolved from operational and technical indicators of previous years to comprehensive indicators reflecting the real impact of digital initiatives. Conclusions are drawn about the importance of these approaches for improving the effectiveness of public administration and achieving national digital development goals.*

Keywords: *digital transformation, efficiency, digital maturity, public administration, assessment indicators, federal executive authorities.*

The digital transformation of public administration requires not only the introduction of modern technologies, but also a system for monitoring the effectiveness of these transformations. In Russia, priority attention is being given to this issue: methodologies for assessing the “digital maturity” of government authorities are being introduced and performance indicators for digital projects are being developed. In the scientific literature, the digitalization of public administration is analyzed through the prism of the concept of “digital maturity”, which integrally characterizes the level of implementation of digital technologies in government activities. The national development Goals provide for achieving full digital maturity of public

administration by 2030—100% of the implementation of digitalization targets in each region of the country. Accordingly, there is a need at the federal level for a unified assessment system to measure how effectively ministries and departments are implementing digital transformation programs.

Assessment approaches have evolved in recent years. Previously, the focus was on operational indicators (technological and process maturity of IT systems, development of the public services portal, compliance with deadlines and budget discipline, etc.), but now the focus is shifting to the final effects for the state and society. The main criterion is the result that digitalization gives citizens — reducing the cost of time and money in obtaining services, improving their quality.

In 2025, the Government’s Subcommittee on Key Digital Transformation Projects approved an updated set of indicators to assess the effectiveness of digital transformation of federal ministries and departments. These metrics cover five key areas 1–4..

1. Development of electronic services and services “for life situations” — the provision of mass socially significant public services in an electronic, proactive format is evaluated. The indicators of this block reflect the transfer of priority services to online mode, the introduction of proactive provision of services without an application, as well as the improvement of the quality of services on the portal of public services (PPS).

2. Import substitution and the use of domestic solutions — the degree of technological independence of departments from foreign software and equipment is measured. This area takes into account the transition to domestic application software in government activities, the replacement of foreign software in government information systems, as well as the introduction of modern Russian information security tools.

3. Ensuring information security — measures are being evaluated to protect the department’s information systems and citizens’ data. The indicators include the level of security of departmental information resources, connection to the unified state system for countering cyber threats (GOSOPKA), conducting independent security audits (for example, bug bounties, pen tests) and advanced training of cybersecurity specialists.

4. Digitalization of internal processes (digital maturity of provision) — the degree of automation and optimization of internal work processes of ministries is analyzed. We are talking about the introduction of electronic document management, corporate communication services (secure messengers, video conferencing, etc.), the transition to centralized cloud infrastructures (Gosoblako), the provision of workplaces with modern equipment and high-speed access to communication networks. This block reflects the agency’s willingness to work effectively in a digital environment.

5. Implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) — based services — the use of AI technologies to improve the effectiveness of government functions is evaluated.

The indicator includes projects on the use of artificial intelligence in the provision of public services and the implementation of control and supervisory measures, as well as in the management of internal processes. The dissemination of AI solutions is considered as an indicator of the innovative development of the department.

The new criteria largely continued the logic of the previously applied ones, but supplemented it with relevant aspects. As D. Grigorenko noted, the previous system was technocratic in nature and consisted of 22 indicators in four groups (technological maturity, PPS development, maturity of information systems, budget discipline). The modern approach takes into account “traditionally significant” parameters — the share of electronic services, the level of information security, import substitution — and complements them with metrics for the introduction of breakthrough technologies (AI, data analysis, etc.). Thus, the focus has shifted from the process to the result and specific benefits: how digitalization of a particular agency reduces costs, speeds up processes and improves interaction with citizens.

It is important that the assessment of the effectiveness of digital transformation is now linked to national development goals. All digital projects of the ministries correspond to the achievement of the targets set by the state. The formation of clear, measurable “result images” for each project allows monitoring the implementation of digital transformation programs in close to real time (several times a year). This creates transparency and encourages authorities to focus on the end effect.

The practical implementation of the assessment system is reflected in the regular monitoring and ratings of the digital maturity of departments. On a monthly basis, the Ministry of Digital Development calculated an operational rating of the achievement of indicators of digital transformation of federal authorities. For example, the Ministry of Industry and Trade assessed 17 indicators, and based on the results of monthly monitoring, management was given recommendations for improving work. The results of such ratings serve as a tool for management decisions — they allow identifying lagging areas and timely adjusting departmental programs. In addition, a number of indicators are linked to citizens’ assessments: through the Feedback Platform, the opinion of the population on the quality of electronic services is collected, on the basis of which the indicators and the public services themselves are improved. This feedback ensures that the digital transformation is focused on end-user satisfaction 5..

Since 2021, the rating of digital transformation of federal ministries has been formed in Russia, which annually determines the leaders and outsiders of digitalization. The first iterations of the rating included indicators of the level of digital interaction with citizens, the degree of implementation of AI and advanced electronic document management systems, etc. In 2022, the state methodology for evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of heads of digital transformation (DTS) departments was developed. This methodology (developed by the RANEPА in collaboration with the Ministry of Finance) took into account three components: meeting the

digital transformation targets, financial discipline of project implementation, and an internal operational performance rating of the RCT. In 2023, the list of criteria for evaluating managers was expanded to 12 points, which included indicators of “digital maturity” in five key sectors (education, healthcare, transport, urban economy, public administration itself), the level of operation of interdepartmental electronic interaction systems, the introduction of feedback platforms, and others. By the end of 2023, federal agencies that scored more than 70% of the maximum score belonged to the high efficiency group, and among the leaders of the rating were such agencies as Rosgvardiya, Roskomnadzor, Rosimushchestvo and the Ministry of Emergency Situations 6..

Thus, a multi-level system has been built that evaluates the digital maturity of public administration: from integral indices for the implementation of national goals to targeted ratings of ministries and assessments of the work of specific responsible managers (digital transformation managers). Comprehensive monitoring makes it possible to monitor the progress of digitalization at all levels and stimulate the exchange of best practices between departments. Experts note that so far the public sector is lagging slightly behind the advanced industries (financial, trade, education) in terms of the effects of digitalization, which was confirmed by pilot measurements of socio-economic results. This means that in the coming years it is necessary to increase the pace of digital transformation and maximize the use of new assessment criteria as a lever to accelerate change 7..

Thus, evaluating the effectiveness of digital transformation of federal ministries and departments is an integral part of the digital state development strategy. The transition from narrowly technical indicators to complex metrics focused on the end result and benefits for society indicates the maturity of the approach to digitalization of public administration. New indicators, such as the coverage of life situations by electronic services, the share of domestic software, the level of information security, the digital maturity of processes and the introduction of AI— provide a holistic picture of the progress of each department. Their use in the rating and monitoring system has already made it possible to identify the best practitioners and problem areas, which creates the basis for the exchange of experience and targeted support for laggards.

The implementation of these approaches increases the transparency and accountability of digital projects: managers are responsible not only for the implementation of activities, but also for achieving measurable results. Regular assessment according to uniform criteria stimulates healthy competition between authorities in the field of innovation and orients everyone towards a single guideline — improving the quality of public administration. Ultimately, the effectiveness of digital transformation is reflected in the satisfaction of citizens with the services provided and in the productivity growth of the state apparatus itself. Further improvement of assessment methods (taking into account the specifics of various bodies, the opinions

of independent experts and feedback from society) will contribute to achieving the goals of Russia's digital development by 2030.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A STANDARD ALGORITHM FOR ENSURING OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN ORGANIZATIONS IN THE AIRCRAFT MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY

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***Annotation.** In today's digitalized production environment, occupational safety issues are becoming increasingly important. The aircraft manufacturing industry, one of the most technologically complex, faces new challenges related to the need to integrate digital technologies into risk management and monitoring of working conditions. The introduction of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and big data offers new opportunities for improving workplace safety, but requires the development of tailored and effective approaches. Automation and robotization of production processes, which are an integral part of modern aircraft manufacturing, introduce their own specific features into occupational safety.*

***Key words:** high-tech enterprises, labor protection, labor economics, aircraft manufacturing industry, human resources.*

A 2020 study in the Russian aircraft manufacturing industry showed that the use of digital platforms for monitoring equipment conditions and working conditions reduced the number of accidents by 15%. This demonstrates the importance of implementing digital solutions to optimize occupational safety management processes, especially in high-tech and critical industries such as aircraft manufacturing. The development of a methodology for assessing the level of digitalization of economic entities involves analyzing various factors affecting the effectiveness of digital transformation. Therefore, a comprehensive approach to digitalization can significantly improve both safety and efficiency in this sector.

According to a 2020 report by the Association of Aircraft Manufacturers, the increasing use of robotics in enterprises is leading to new types of occupational injuries related to human-machine interactions. This requires the development of new approaches to personnel training and the organization of safe interactions with automated systems. The digitalization of enterprises allows them to integrate into

the rapidly developing digital economy, leading to the digital transformation of their operations. Adaptation to new technologies not only changes production processes but also requires a rethinking of occupational safety approaches, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach to this issue.

Traditional occupational health and safety risk management methods in the aircraft manufacturing industry are based on international standards and best practices. One key standard is ISO 45001, which defines requirements for occupational health and safety management systems. This standard aims to systematically identify, assess, and manage risks, thereby reducing the likelihood of accidents and improving employee safety. Implementing ISO 45001 allows organizations to structure their processes, ensuring regulatory compliance and improving their overall safety culture. According to research conducted in 2018, 70% of aircraft manufacturing companies in Russia used risk analysis methods based on accident statistics. These methods include collecting and analyzing incident information, determining their causes, and developing corrective measures. This approach allows companies to identify the most vulnerable areas and develop risk mitigation strategies. Statistical analysis provides objective data that serves as the basis for decision-making aimed at ensuring occupational safety. Historically, risk management methods in the aircraft manufacturing industry developed based on approaches developed in the mid-20th century. One such method is FMEA (failure modes and effects analysis), which is used to identify potential system failures and their consequences. This method allows for the identification of weaknesses in processes and equipment, facilitating the development of preventive measures. Using FMEA in aircraft manufacturing helps minimize the likelihood of errors and improve system reliability, which is especially important in an environment with increased safety requirements.

The aircraft manufacturing industry is characterized by highly complex production processes and stringent occupational safety requirements. However, existing approaches to occupational safety management face a number of limitations. A key factor affecting the effectiveness of these approaches is their reliance on outdated methodologies that fail to address the challenges of modern digitalization. “Modern enterprises are faced with the inevitable need to improve their production efficiency to meet growing market demands and ensure business sustainability.” Therefore, it is important to adapt occupational safety management methods to the new conditions, which will improve their effectiveness and align them with modern requirements.

The concept of the proposed algorithm is based on the use of modern digital technologies to ensure occupational safety in organizations in the aviation industry. The main goal of the algorithm is to create an integrated system that combines data from various sources, such as IoT sensors, monitoring systems, and analytical platforms, for effective risk monitoring and management. For example, Boeing’s implementation of an IoT-based occupational safety monitoring system in 2020

reduced the number of industrial injuries by 15%. This example demonstrates the potential of digital technologies to improve working conditions and minimize risks. The algorithm also utilizes artificial intelligence to analyze data and predict potential incidents, thereby enhancing safety.

The structure of the proposed algorithm includes several key elements that ensure its functionality and effectiveness. First, a data collection system that uses IoT sensors to monitor environmental parameters and equipment conditions. Second, an analytical module based on artificial intelligence technologies processes the collected data and identifies potential threats. Third, a user interface that provides operational information and recommendations for incident prevention. According to research by Accenture, 72% of companies that implemented digital technologies in occupational safety processes reported improved risk management. This confirms the importance of integrating digital solutions into the algorithmic structure. Thus, the algorithmic structure ensures a comprehensive approach to occupational safety management.

Modern digital technologies play a key role in ensuring occupational safety in enterprises, providing tools for monitoring, analyzing, and preventing potential risks. One such technology is the Internet of Things (IoT), which collects data from various sensors installed on equipment and in work areas. This data is used to analyze the condition of the equipment and the surrounding environment, helping to promptly identify potential hazards. According to a McKinsey report, the implementation of IoT in industry helps reduce the rate of occupational injuries by 10–25%. An example of the successful application of digital technologies is Honeywell's Safety Suite system, which includes wearable devices and software for monitoring workers' condition, alerting them to potential hazards. These examples demonstrate how modern technologies can significantly improve occupational safety.

In the aircraft manufacturing industry, digital technologies are widely used to improve occupational safety. For example, Boeing successfully uses augmented reality (AR) systems to train employees and test their actions during aircraft assembly. This reduces errors by 30%, positively impacting the safety of production processes. Furthermore, using drones to inspect hard-to-reach areas at aircraft manufacturing facilities reduces the risk of worker injury and increases the effectiveness of inspections. These technologies are integrated into occupational safety algorithms, providing tools for data analysis and real-time decision-making. Thus, digitalization is becoming an important element of the safety strategy in the aircraft manufacturing industry.

Accuracy in identifying hazardous situations plays a key role in evaluating the effectiveness of algorithms. A 2021 study by the Institute of Occupational Safety found that integrating IoT technologies for monitoring working conditions increased hazard detection accuracy by 25%. Thus, the use of the Internet of Things significantly improves risk monitoring and control. Furthermore, the development

of AI-based monitoring and forecasting systems helps reduce the risk of accidents and improve equipment reliability. As Panteleev notes, “improving equipment safety and reliability” is an important aspect in this area. These findings highlight the importance of a comprehensive approach to safety, where modern technologies play a crucial role in preventing accidents and ensuring system reliability.

The next step is to develop an algorithm integration plan tailored to the specifics of the enterprise. It is important to consider the specifics of production processes, infrastructure, and personnel. “Defining the set of system states characterizing the level of digitalization of an i-group of factors involves compiling a matrix of transition probabilities of system states and analyzing the resulting models” (Kalitovskaya, 2024, p. 5). An example of the successful application of this approach is Airbus, which implemented an IoT-based working conditions monitoring system, reducing the risk of occupational diseases among employees by 15%.

The study resulted in the development of a standard occupational safety algorithm that integrates modern digital technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, and analytical platforms. This algorithm aims to improve the effectiveness of risk management and adapt to modern technological changes in the context of digitalization. An analysis of current approaches to occupational safety in the aircraft manufacturing industry revealed shortcomings, such as limited adaptability to new challenges and low efficiency in the face of increasing digital data volumes. The developed algorithm takes these aspects into account, offering innovative solutions for monitoring and analyzing working conditions. To successfully implement the algorithm in company practice, it is necessary to consider the individual characteristics of enterprises, including their technological infrastructure and personnel training. It is also important to develop strategies to minimize risks associated with the use of digital technologies, such as cyber threats and human error. The results of the study highlight the importance of integrating digital technologies into occupational safety processes. This will not only reduce the incidence of industrial injuries but also improve the overall effectiveness of occupational safety management, which is especially relevant in the context of global digitalization. Thus, the implementation of the proposed algorithm is an important step towards creating safe and comfortable working conditions at enterprises in the aircraft manufacturing industry, ensuring their compliance with modern requirements and standards.

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INNOVATIVE APPLICATIONS OF PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS IN SALES MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: *This article examines the role of predictive analytics as a key tool for transforming sales management in the digital economy. The authors systematize the limitations of traditional accounting and analytical systems and justify the need to implement predictive methods. Based on global research, the key advantages of using predictive analytics in sales are highlighted. Innovative modeling methods, such as churn forecasting and ARIMA, are described.*

Keywords: *predictive analytics, sales management, forecasting, machine learning, Big Data, business analytics, customer focus.*

In today's world, digital technologies not only significantly improve enterprise efficiency but also completely transform it: from structure and business processes to management principles and methods.

In the digital economy, the competitive advantage of large companies directly depends on the quality and speed of information and analytical support for corporate management. For this purpose, modern corporations use accounting and analytical systems based on big data processing technologies, such as Online Transaction Processing and Online Analytical Processing. The most common of these are modern ERP systems, Business Intelligence systems, and Corporate Performance Management systems. However, in the new economic realities, the traditional functionality of these systems is no longer sufficient to address new digital challenges. ERP systems focus on analyzing past events, the so-called “Plan-Fact” model, while BI applications focus on analyzing the past and present. CPM systems lack built-in forecasting tools 3..

This study examines the use of predictive analytics — a powerful forecasting tool that, based on data mining methods, statistics, modeling, and machine learning, enables forecasting future events based on the analysis of current information and effectively using large volumes of data to achieve an enterprise’s business goals. The relevance of this research topic is due to the fact that predictive analytics is increasingly being used in sales as an effective tool for improving business performance, which has become possible due to the increased availability of data, the development of artificial intelligence technologies, and, as a result, the increased need to optimize business processes.

This trend is confirmed by research from major global consulting and analytics companies. For example, according to MarketsandMarkets, an expert in B2B market research, the global predictive analytics market was valued at \$ 10.5 billion in 2022 and is expected to reach \$28.1 billion by 2027, with an annual growth rate of 21.9% 8.. According to a report by the American company Salesforce, developer of the CRM system of the same name, 79% of companies use or plan to use predictive analytics to improve their sales 11.. Aberdeen Group, an international marketing analytics company, concluded that businesses using predictive analytics increase their sales faster than those that do not use such technologies. According to a report by Deloitte, 75% of managers at surveyed companies have increased their investments in predictive analytics over the past three years 12.. Predictive analytics is generally recognized as a set of analytical and statistical methods aimed at forecasting future actions or behavior, using data and technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning to predict future outcomes. In a business context, predictive analytics serves as the basis for decision-making and strategy optimization, enabling the assessment of risks and opportunities 1., 6..

The use of predictive analytics in sales management offers numerous benefits that help companies optimize processes, improve efficiency, and increase profits 5..

By investing in predictive analytics, a company can 4.:

1. Improve the accuracy of marketing segmentation. Business-to-business (B2B) firms apply big data analytics early in the sales funnel, particularly in market

segmentation, allowing sales teams to more accurately segment the market. To create an ideal customer profile and more accurately and precisely target marketing efforts, specialists collect sales data and analyze it to distribute existing customers into target segments.

2. Improve conversion. Data analytics helps B2B companies use past sales data to identify promising leads. Managers develop lead scoring algorithms, combining them with external information to predict who is most likely to make a purchase. It is estimated that this approach can increase the conversion rate in B2B by 30% across various industries.

3. Improve sales forecasting. Accurate forecasts enable businesses to plan and ensure stable profitability. This is achieved by using CRM data (reviews, customer behavior, purchase history) and statistical methods such as ARIMA (autoregressive integrated moving average algorithm), which helps identify hidden opportunities to increase sales 9, 10.. Using customer data and advanced algorithms can significantly improve the accuracy of sales forecasts, allowing companies to better plan their resources and maximize profits.

4. Improve the accuracy of recommendations. Using DataAnalytics algorithms, sales managers can segment customers based on their needs, enabling more personalized and effective offers. Furthermore, this data-driven approach can reveal hidden cross-selling opportunities, thereby increasing revenue.

5. Increase transparency of customer lifetime value. In the B2B sector, it is crucial to accurately understand how much profit a customer will generate over the entire relationship. Data Analytics, particularly predictive analytics methods and techniques, can be used to more accurately predict CLV. This allows for long-term customer engagement and effective customer engagement.

Understanding and predicting customer behavior is crucial for modern businesses, especially in the retail sector. Advanced modeling techniques based on machine learning provide invaluable insights into various phenomena, such as customer churn, sales forecasting, and personalized offers. These modeling techniques include churn prediction, SKU-based sales forecasting, and personalized offer modeling.

Churn modeling begins with creating a training set, including data on customers who have discontinued their relationship with the business. Depending on the industry, the period after which a customer is considered “lost” is determined. For high-frequency customer sectors, such as grocery stores or gas stations, a period of the past three months is considered, while for low-frequency

customer sectors, such as non-food retail, this period is extended to one to two years. Next, cluster analysis is used to identify common characteristics of churners. Based on these identified patterns, a model is built that can detect behavioral changes that predict churn. Simultaneously, the factors influencing churn are analyzed to identify the most significant ones.

To accurately forecast each specific product (SKU), it is necessary to first classify the products to select the optimal forecasting method. It is important to consider inventory management issues such as stockouts, returns, and the impact of promotional campaigns. Predictive analytics allows for a high probability (up to 95 %) prediction of a customer's purchase. However, to improve accuracy, factors such as seasonality, holidays, and weather conditions, which can significantly impact demand, should be taken into account. Once these factors are identified and accounted for, predictive models are thoroughly tested on historical data and, if successful, are used to forecast sales in real time.

Creating a personalized offer requires a data set spanning at least a year to capture the full spectrum of customer purchasing behavior. First, a customer segmentation method is selected, then changes in purchasing habits that indicate potential shifts to competitors are identified.

One approach can be look-a-like modeling (a method used in marketing, advertising, and data analysis to find audiences similar to an existing target group). Based on the purchase patterns of loyal customers, a list of frequently purchased products is created. The system generates alerts if: a) a loyal customer stops purchasing these products, or b) customers from other segments do not purchase these identified products. The model is validated on historical data and monitored in real time before final deployment.

In conclusion, it should be noted that despite significant potential, the implementation and use of predictive analytics is associated with a number of challenges and limitations, the main ones related to data quality, model complexity, competency gaps, and the influence of external factors 2., 5.. The accuracy of forecasts directly depends, among other things, on the quality of the data used, meaning it's critical to ensure reliable processes for collecting, cleaning, integrating, and updating information from various sources. The development, validation, and maintenance of effective predictive models require an appropriate level of expertise in statistics, data analysis, and subject matter. The shortage of qualified analysts capable of accurately interpreting results and managing the model lifecycle remains a pressing issue. Unforeseen changes in the external environment, such as market shocks, geopolitical events, regulatory changes, and technological breakthroughs, can render past patterns irrelevant, requiring constant refinement and adaptation of models to new conditions.

However, despite these challenges, predictive analytics is emerging as a powerful sales management tool, enabling companies not only to respond to current changes but also to project future trends and make strategic decisions. The integration of big data analytics and advanced statistical modeling into sales processes leads to significant increases in efficiency, increased profitability, and a stronger competitive position in the digital environment.

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**IDENTIFYING POTENTIAL INVESTMENT GROWTH POINTS
IN BRICS COUNTRIES AND COMPETING WITH THE ANGLO-
SAXON 5C+1 STRATEGY: THE BATTLE FOR EURASIA IN THE
21ST CENTURY**

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Abstract: *Using the example of the RIC (Russia, India, and China) and Central Asia, the authors examine the ongoing competing development concepts in the post-Soviet space from the perspective of national-sovereign development institutions and Anglo-Saxon governance structures in the context of the Indo-Pacific expansion of the Heartland within the “5C + 1” concept, as a zone of turbulent confrontation and intensifying competition for the most promising territories of the 21st century.*

Keywords: *Heartland, Russia, Anglo-Saxons, Eurasianism, RIC, BRICS, SCO, EAEU, 5C + 1, national security, integration, USA, AUKUS.*

Following Alaska and in the lead-up to the Berlin summit between the Americans and Europeans and the leaders of the Ukrainian fascist junta, each country is attempting to find its optimal vector for developing the geoeconomic regionalization of Central Asia and offer the Eurasian continent its signature turnkey project. This includes belief in the post-Soviet unity of the former fraternal socialist republics, Shiite and Sunni projects (“Greater Persia,” “New Turan,” a Shiite belt of states, Chinese assimilation according to the rules of implementing investments, materials, and technologies under the auspices of the “Belt and Road” initiative), as well as an attempt to moderate the appetites of global elites who are unwilling to develop this region beyond that of a vassal state, a raw materials appendage of the “collective West,” from the perspective of neocolonialist inclusion in primitive resource chains without the right to innovative redistribution.

Meanwhile, BRICS and SCO countries have been announcing for the past 10–15 years that they are taking measures to develop existing and create new transport routes that could contribute to strengthening ties and expanding international co-operation and trade partnerships between Russia, India, and China.

When analyzing these international routes, it is necessary to consider both their obvious advantages and the hidden disadvantages of growing geopolitical volatility. Some of the advantages include faster cargo delivery, reduced transit times, and expanded markets for RIC countries. However, there are also some disadvantages, such as high transportation costs, capacity limitations, and potential security issues, which may hinder the stable and rapidly growing flow of expected shipments. To optimize and develop international routes, it is necessary to consider measures such as improving infrastructure, reducing transportation costs, streamlining logistics processes, and simplifying customs procedures.

Table 1. Analysis of international routes linking RIC countries

Advantages:	Flaws:	Measures for optimization and development:
Trans-Siberian Railway		
- Geographic location: connects Europe and Asia, providing the shortest route for transporting cargo between Russia, India, and China. — High throughput: allows for the transportation of large volumes of cargo.	- Limited infrastructure: modernization and development of rail infrastructure is required, including expansion of container terminals and track upgrades. — Dependence on weather conditions: Delays may occur in winter due to snowfall and frost.	- Investments in infrastructure modernization: expansion and modernization of container terminals, upgrade of routes and transport facilities. — Improvement of operating conditions: ensuring the reliability and safety of transportation, including weather control. — Development of logistics centers and terminals: creating efficient logistics chains for faster and more efficient cargo delivery.
Sea route through the Indian Ocean		
- Access to global markets: The sea route provides access to various countries and regions, expanding trade opportunities. — Large cargo capacity: Sea vessels are capable of transporting large volumes of cargo,	- Weather vulnerability: Maritime shipping is susceptible to weather factors such as storms and tides, which can cause delays and instability. — Capacity issues: Some ports may face congestion issues and in-	- Investments in port infrastructure: expansion and modernization of ports, increasing throughput capacity and ensuring efficient cargo handling. — Improved navigational safety: application of modern technologies and navigation systems to reduce risks and ensure safe navigation. — Development of supply chains:

Advantages:	Flaws:	Measures for optimization and development:
enabling increased trade volumes.	sufficient infrastructure.	improving connections between ports and inland transport networks to ensure faster and more efficient cargo delivery.
China-Russia Highway		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility and speed: Road transport provides fast cargo delivery and flexibility in route selection. — Accessibility to remote regions: Road routes can be used to deliver cargo to remote and hard-to-reach areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capacity issues: Road networks may face congestion and limited capacity. — High fuel and maintenance costs: Road transport can be expensive compared to other modes of transport. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investments in road infrastructure: expansion and modernization of roads and highways, creation of bypass routes and service points. — Development of logistics centers: creation of efficient logistics chains and warehouse complexes to optimize road transport. — Promotion of the use of electric and gas-powered vehicles: reduction of environmental impact and fuel costs.
Air cargo routes		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fast delivery: Air freight provides the fastest way to deliver cargo over long distances. — Intercontinental connectivity: Air routes connect different continents and ensure global accessibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High costs: Air freight is more expensive than other modes of transport. — Limited cargo capacity: Aircraft have limited cargo capacity, which may be insufficient for transporting large and heavy cargo. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving airport logistics infrastructure: expanding cargo terminals, increasing throughput, and reducing cargo handling times. — Improving customs procedures: simplifying and accelerating customs clearance to reduce cargo dwell time at airports. — Developing cargo hubs: creating efficient cargo hubs to ensure more efficient cargo handling and logistics integration.

It is important to note that all proposed measures to optimize and develop international routes must be based on national interests and trade priorities to build a more economically significant model of mutual cooperation and to correctly focus dialogue between Russia, India, and China. These measures also require financial and organizational resources for their successful implementation.

Following this analysis, it becomes clear that the main international routes between Russia, India, and China play a vital role in the development of international trade and economic cooperation, challenging Anglo-Saxon dominance in the Heartland region and preventing Western hegemony in the “Global South.” The Trans-Siberian Railway, sea routes, and air travel are the primary means of

communication between these countries. Optimizing and developing these routes, as well as creating new transport corridors, can contribute to strengthening ties and expanding cooperation in the region, leading to synergistic development effects across the territories and increased efficiency in all forms of business, due to the resulting multiplier effects and a more streamlined delivery system for the redistribution of goods between consumers.

Meanwhile, our opponents held a Central Asian summit in Washington on November 6, 2025, to commemorate the 10th anniversary of the 5C+1 platform. At the conclusion of his working visit to Washington, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev met with representatives of leading American companies, investment funds, and financial institutions. The event was attended by US Secretary of Commerce Howard Lutnick, Special Assistant to the President Ricky Gil, Special Presidential Envoy Paolo Zampolli, Deputy Secretary of Agriculture Steven Vaden, as well as leaders of the American-Uzbekistan Chamber of Commerce and top managers of major corporations including Traxys, FLSmidth, BCG, Meta, Google, Amazon, Boeing, Air Products, Axiom Space, Cove Capital, Freeport-McMoRan, Orion CMC, Cargill Cotton, John Deere, Honeywell, Valmont Industries, Flowserve Corporation, and many others. Opening the meeting, Uzbek President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who has long been protected by British private military companies, noted that trade between Uzbekistan and the United States has quadrupled over the past eight years, and that more than 300 American companies are successfully operating in the country. The head of state emphasized that the current level of cooperation is only the beginning of a new stage, opening up broad opportunities for joint projects. He announced that specific areas of economic cooperation and new initiatives are planned to be discussed during his upcoming meeting with US President Donald Trump. The President outlined key areas of strategic partnership between the two countries. According to him, by 2030, Uzbekistan will have a new-generation energy system with an installed capacity of 18–20 gigawatts of renewable energy, with more than half of all electricity generated by solar and wind. In this context, the parties intend to develop the mining and advanced processing of uranium, copper, tungsten, molybdenum, and graphite, establish sustainable supply chains, and implement advanced American processing technologies. Particular attention is being paid to the modernization of roads, railways, terminals, and airports. Over \$12 billion is planned for the development of transport infrastructure by 2030. Digital partnerships with Google, Meta, and NVIDIA are actively developing: the country is implementing the Apple Pay and Google Pay payment systems, and a Digital Academy and a network of startup hubs are being created. Resources from the Development Finance Corporation (DFC) and the US Eximbank will be used to finance these projects. At the end of the meeting, Shavkat Mirziyoyev confirmed his readiness

to personally support the investment initiatives of American companies and emphasized that Uzbekistan remains a reliable partner and guarantor of success for foreign investors.

Other presidents, both members of the CSTO and the EAEU, have also demonstrated similar activity, which does not prevent them from maintaining their own multipolar framework for the development of their countries. For example, speaking about Kyrgyz-American relations, Kyrgyz President Sadyr Japarov outlined priority areas of cooperation, highlighting the economy, investment and tourism, hydropower, the digital economy, artificial intelligence and the IT sector, security, and sustainable development. In his speech, the Kyrgyz leader placed particular emphasis on bilateral cooperation in the field of digitalization. He noted that although Kyrgyzstan has historically never exported products to the United States, “over the past five years, IT services exports to the United States have increased 45-fold.” Based on this, Sadyr Japarov proposed that the United States continue to develop partnership in the field of digital regulation. Specifically, he suggested that they consider the possibility of establishing a regional RegTech Trust Hub in Kyrgyzstan. During the summit, the US President announced the conclusion of an “incredible trade and economic agreement” with Uzbekistan worth over \$ 100 billion. The deal envisages Uzbek investment of approximately \$ 35 billion in American industries over the next three years, ranging from mineral extraction and auto component manufacturing to aviation, IT, and energy. Over the next decade, the volume of investment is expected to exceed \$ 100 billion. This includes investments in mineral extraction, aviation, energy, and other sectors.

At the same time, Uzbek President Shavkat Mirziyoyev announced a new set of initiatives to strengthen regional cooperation. Specifically, he proposed the creation of a permanent C5+1 Secretariat (to be located on a rotating basis in participating countries), an Investment and Trade Coordination Council, and a Central Asian Investment Partnership Fund. The head of Uzbekistan proposed initiatives for the joint development and processing of critical minerals (he proposed creating a special committee), modernizing agriculture using American technologies, and holding an exhibition of the cultural heritage of Central Asian countries in leading US museums. The leader of Uzbekistan also expressed his readiness to actively work with the United States on major transportation, communications, and energy projects linking Central Asia with the South Caucasus and Europe.

Speaking at the summit’s working dinner, Tajikistan’s President Emomali Rahmon also noted his country’s desire to develop cooperation in green energy, given Tajikistan’s extensive water resources and strategic location. He also emphasized the country’s readiness to implement joint projects in the extraction and processing of minerals. In this regard, the United States and Tajikistan signed agreements on critical minerals. Dushanbe signed a \$32.5 million agreement with the American

organization Transparent Earth. The agreement provides for technical assistance and the use of remote sensing technologies to improve efficiency in Tajikistan's mining and agricultural sectors. The topic of critical minerals was a key item on the agenda of Trump's meeting with Central Asian leaders, further underscoring Washington's true interests in the region. Trump stated his intention to reduce dependence on critical minerals from China and Russia, noting the American side's willingness to invest billions of dollars in their extraction and processing in Central Asian countries. The US leader also emphasized the importance of new transport corridors across the Caspian Sea.

Speaking at the C5+1 summit, US Secretary of State Marco Rubio announced plans to visit all five Central Asian countries in 2026, noting the importance of joint "responsible resource development." Donald Trump also called Central Asia an "extremely rich region" and a "bridge" between East and West. For Washington, Central Asia is also a battleground for confrontation with China and Russia. Meanwhile, for countries in the region that have demonstrated an interest in developing relations with the US, this is one of their goals to diversify their external ties and reduce dependence on traditional partners like Beijing and Moscow. Furthermore, it provides an additional source of investment and technology. Therefore, even if such interactions are skewed in Washington's favor, this will not diminish the interest of regional players in cooperating with the United States. Organizing the event in the US capital also further underscores the Trump administration's growing interest in the region.

On November 6, Kazakh President Kassym-Jomart Tokayev arrived in Washington on an official visit. His agenda, like that of all Central Asian leaders, included not only participation in the summit but also a bilateral meeting with US President Donald Trump. Tokayev also held talks with Secretary of State Marco Rubio, Secretary of Commerce Howard Lutnick, US Special Presidential Envoy for South and Central Asia Sergio Gore, as well as several representatives of American business and Congress. The central topics of the talks were energy, critical minerals, digitalization, artificial intelligence, and the development of transport corridors. A key outcome of the visit was the signing of a memorandum of understanding between Kazakhstan and the US on cooperation in critical minerals. The document, signed by Kazakh Industry Minister Yersaiyn Nagaspayev and US Commerce Secretary Howard Lutnick, provides for the participation of American companies in the mining and processing of rare earth metals in Kazakhstan. Furthermore, the National Bank of Kazakhstan and Visa Corporation signed a memorandum on the creation of a competence center for digital payment technologies. The total value of agreements signed during the visit exceeded \$17 billion, including contracts with Nvidia, Boeing, OpenAI, John Deere, and other tech and industrial giants. At the White House, Tokayev expressed his sincere appreciation

for President Donald Trump's policy in Central Asia, thanking him for the invitation and acknowledging his contribution to strengthening international stability and US economic leadership. Kazakhstan supported the US-led "Trump Route for International Peace and Prosperity" (TRIPP) initiative, aimed at developing the Middle East Transport Corridor (MITR) in the Caucasus. The US side emphasized its readiness to strengthen the strategic partnership, expand investment, and foster technological collaboration. Participants estimated the potential for economic cooperation between the two countries at over \$500 billion, including in energy, transportation, finance, industry, and education. A business conference was held as part of the summit, discussing, among other things, the possibility of expanding the presence of American capital in Kazakhstan. In particular, IThirty Holding presented a project to build a chemical complex worth approximately \$130 million. Separately, it is worth noting the agreement reached on Kazakhstan's accession to the Abraham Accords, which normalize relations between Israel and Arab countries. According to an official statement from the presidential press service, by joining the Accords, the Republic seeks to contribute to overcoming the confrontation in the Middle East, promoting dialogue, and upholding international law based on the UN Charter. This step is also symbolic, highlighting Astana's growing political and economic rapprochement with Washington.

On November 6, Kyrgyz President Sadyr Japarov met with James Risch, Chairman of the US Senate Committee on Foreign Relations, and US Senators in Washington. During the talks, the parties discussed political and interparliamentary cooperation, as well as interaction in trade, economic, and investment spheres. That same day, Sadyr Japarov held a bilateral meeting with Donald Trump, where they discussed current issues of bilateral cooperation and ways to strengthen partnership, including in the political sphere, as well as in financial technology and artificial intelligence. The Kyrgyz President emphasized that although Kyrgyzstan does not possess oil or gas reserves, the country's greatest asset is its educated youth, some of whom are actively pursuing IT careers.

Before the summit, Sadyr Japarov made a press statement expressing confidence that joint efforts will yield concrete results and contribute to the mutual benefit of both countries. In his speech at the summit, the Head of the Kyrgyz Republic expressed confidence that this event would provide a unique opportunity to expand cooperation in areas such as agriculture, e-commerce, information technology, transport and logistics, tourism, and banking and finance.

Tajik President Emomali Rahmon, who is participating in the summit, initiated separate bilateral talks with US President Donald Trump. The two leaders discussed the current state and prospects of cooperation. Particular attention was paid to strengthening trade, economic, and investment ties. Industry, mineral extraction and processing, energy, agriculture, transport, science, as well as artificial

intelligence and technology, were mentioned as areas for further cooperation. The fight against terrorism, extremism, and drug trafficking were also discussed. During the meeting, it was also noted that more than 70 companies with American capital currently operate in Tajikistan. On the sidelines of the summit in Washington, representatives of the Tajik government and business also met with their American counterparts. On November 5, talks were held in Washington between Khabibullo Nazarzoda, Director of the Civil Aviation Agency under the Government of the Republic of Tajikistan, and Kristen Gatlin, Deputy Administrator of the US Federal Aviation Administration. Strengthening bilateral cooperation in civil aviation was discussed, including the preparation of an agreement between the two governments “On Air Communications” and the possible establishment of direct flights between Tajikistan and the United States. Continuing with the topic of aviation, one of the bilateral meetings resulted in the announcement of the purchase of 14 Boeing aircraft for the national airline of Tajikistan, Somon Air. This is the largest order in the history of the Tajik carrier. These aircraft are 787 Dreamliners and 737 MAXs from the American company. In the area of digital modernization, partnership and licensing agreements signed by Tajikistan with Starlink represent a significant step. They provide for cooperation on expanding the country’s digital infrastructure and ensuring reliable communications, even in hard-to-reach areas. Also noteworthy are the agreements reached by SuperMicro, Cerebris, and zypl.ai, which will develop infrastructure for AI-powered data centers in Tajikistan. Tajikistan has committed to building 1 GW of hydroelectric power, which will lay the foundation for the country’s potential transformation into a regional hub for high-tech solutions. Furthermore, as part of the Central Asia-USA Summit, a business conference was held with representatives of regional governments and entrepreneurs, at which Tajikistan presented its key investment projects in such sectors as mechanical engineering, metallurgy, light industry, food processing, chemical and pharmaceutical industries, construction materials production, and tourism..

Turkmen President Serdar Berdimuhamedov also attended the Central Asia-US Summit and held a series of meetings with US officials and business representatives. At the bilateral meeting between the presidents of Turkmenistan and the United States, Berdimuhamedov noted the importance of the summit, noting that this format opens up new opportunities for strengthening cooperation across a wide range of areas. He expressed confidence that the event would be “an important step in the development of traditionally friendly relations” between Turkmenistan and the United States. The parties reaffirmed their commitment to further expanding and deepening interstate cooperation in key areas. Berdimuhamedov also met with Bill Huizenga, Chairman of the Subcommittee on South and Central Asia of the US House of Representatives Committee on Foreign Affairs, and Sidney Kai Kamlager-Dove, his deputy. During the talks, the Turkmen leader

emphasized the importance of developing cooperation with the United States in the political, economic, and humanitarian spheres. He expressed Ashgabat's commitment to strengthening cooperation with the US Congress, particularly in areas such as exchanging legislative experience and discussing regional and international issues. As part of the Turkmen President's working visit to the US, a business forum, "Turkmen-American Business Cooperation: New Opportunities and Prospects for Partnership Development," was successfully held. The forum was attended by government officials and business representatives from both countries, including renowned companies such as John Deere, General Electric (GE), SpaceX, and Oppenheimer Holdings Inc., as well as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund. On the sidelines of the event, representatives of relevant US organizations noted the growing interest of American businesspeople in the Turkmen market, confirming their willingness to participate in implementing Turkmenistan's socioeconomic development programs and to provide technology, innovation, and expertise. Discussing cooperation in the fuel and energy sector, the parties touched on issues related to the modernization of relevant infrastructure, the implementation of technologies, and the intensification of partnerships in the renewable energy sector. One of the main topics of discussion was cooperation in the processing industry. In particular, a desire to collaborate in areas such as food and textile production, increasing their export potential and expanding sales markets, and enhancing employee professionalism was expressed.

The forum included bilateral meetings at which prospects for expanding cooperation were discussed. The discussion between the President of Turkmenistan and John Reese, CEO of Nicklaus Companies, held the day before the business forum deserves special attention. Serdar Berdimuhamedov emphasized that the Turkmen-American business forum provides an excellent opportunity for business representatives from both countries to exchange views on promising projects and investment cooperation. Nicklaus Companies specializes in the design and development of golf infrastructure, and the head of state emphasized the excellent opportunities for bilateral partnership in this area. He noted that Turkmenistan views the development of sports and tourism as important areas of sustainable development.

Conclusion

The C5+1 format, created in 2015, is gradually transforming from a diplomatic platform into an instrument of US economic and resource influence, strengthening the Anglo-Saxon position in Central Asia and providing AUKUS with raw materials based on supplies from all countries in the region. The White House is developing a systemic strategy: to strengthen partnerships, secure access to raw materials, and expand logistics routes, including bypassing Russia and preventing

it from participating in projects with China and India in the Harteland region. The summit goes beyond protocol meetings. The US is consistently strengthening its influence in the region, while Central Asian countries are seeking to balance interests between global power centers. The region is increasingly becoming an arena for major power rivalry. The expansion of strategic partnerships between Central Asian states (especially Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan) with the US and other Western institutions could, among other things, undermine the positions of Russia and China in the region, particularly on the economic front. Moscow and Beijing continue to rely on long-established ties and agreements with Central Asian countries, including geographic proximity. However, these circumstances are not always decisive, as global political history demonstrates. The meeting in the US capital clearly demonstrated that even with a change in the US president, the US course in Central Asia remains unchanged. Washington continues to methodically strengthen its position in the region, using a combination of diplomacy, investment, and resource initiatives. The countries of the former Central Asia, based on their pragmatic interests, hope to reap certain benefits from a partnership with the US, primarily in economic diversification and investment, industrial cooperation, technological partnerships, security (especially in the areas of cybersecurity, counterterrorism, and transnational crime), and the development of transport and logistics projects and corridors. The very presence of the US as a third power in the region (alongside Russia and China) provides the Central Asian countries with greater room for foreign policy maneuvering. This is a bargaining tool that allows for more favorable terms within platforms such as the Eurasian Economic Union, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, or the Belt and Road Initiative. The viability of such a course will directly depend on the ability of Central Asian governments to pursue pragmatic and balanced policies.

Potential investment convergence points for successful development on the Eurasian continent require their own “roadmaps” between Vladimir Putin and Donald Trump. Otherwise, instead of investment, they will be reduced to a series of local conflicts and a bitter confrontation between some systemic players and others. This will implode the region from within and throw it back to feudal times, with Basmachi and banditry.

Therefore, the Alaska Agreements and the consolidated victory of Russia and the “Global South” in Ukraine in the North-East Asia should put an end to the Berlin “internecine squabbles” and launch the RIC into a decisive offensive for the priority, high-quality development of the Eurasian space. Otherwise, the “5C + 1” will make these territories corporate-controlled and deprive Russia of the last remnants of Soviet good-neighborly relations with the RIC countries from the EAEU to the CSTO, SCO and BRICS, which is unacceptable and will lead to a global war between all participants.

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PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN TRADE OF THE EAEU COUNTRIES IN THE PROCESS OF CREATING GLOBAL MACROREGIONS (ICT TRENDS)

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Abstract: *This article examines the development of foreign trade among the EAEU countries as they transition to a single Eurasian macroregion. It also discusses Donald Trump's idea of a G5 to replace the G7, as an alternative to the G7, and the creation of unified global trade standards in the context of the deterioration of WTO institutions and ongoing tariff and currency wars between East and West.*

Keywords: *information and communications technology (ICT), Russia, EAEU, artificial intelligence (AI), sanctions, Covid-19, Big Data, Central Asia.*

The 11 years of successful development of the EAEU prompt reflection not only on the transformation of investment and innovation processes but also on foreign trade trends among the five countries themselves, which are successfully exploring the Eurasian space and deepening cooperation and networking. Prior to the well-known events in Ukraine at the end of February 2022, the situation was recorded and analytically assessed in terms of expected growth in the global IT services market, which could grow by approximately 8% per year over the next 3–5 years. The Russian market for these services grew by 5% in dollar terms or 14% in ruble terms in 2020 1.. Over the next five years, its dollar value will grow by 7% per year, unless speculative expectations for a currency corridor disappoint investors and financial resources are redirected toward currency speculation and the inflating of overheated market bubbles in global energy commodity markets, which are currently breaking all previously achieved pricing records.

The growing labor shortage and the loss of a significant portion of the ICT industry's workforce, even after the protectionist measures outlined by the Russian government, will lead to an exponential increase in demand for IT services and the closure/freezing of insourcing companies, their partial nationalization, and their incorporation, either fully or in a transformed form, into leading Russian telecommunications holdings. The law on fake news on social media and the increasing lobbying for exclusively pro-Western viewpoints that denigrate the current Russian policy have already led to the departure of a number of internet providers from the Russian market. However, international petitions signed by various European organizations and guilds to uphold freedom of speech and the need for unimpeded access to open information in Russia will convince some foreign companies to continue their activities in Russian cyberspace.

At the same time, the dualistic approach will likely be maintained: market access in exchange for loyalty to the authorities will be offset by the "soft power" of potentially destabilizing the domestic situation through Russian internet users, particularly among the passionate demographic under 30. ICT market customers will increasingly seek to utilize diversified digital tools, previously abundantly available to all, but now, following the departure of leading players, becoming more national and Asian-focused. The real market potential before the Ukrainian crisis previously allowed for price reductions for relevant IT service pools, such as low-cost services, platform services, and automated monitoring and incident response systems, which, due to intense competition among operators and vendors, began to operate at minimal profitability levels. The changing ICT infrastructure will now become not only flexible but also quite unbalanced. Leading global companies such as Oracle, Microsoft, Apple, IBM, and others, which have withdrawn due to sanctions, will prevent the current 7–10-year lag in ICT and digital services, payment systems, and marketplaces from being overcome in the near future. They will accelerate the creation of financial digital ecosystems and metaverses dependent on both the hardware and software of existing technical protocols and existing generally accepted computer languages and programs.

According to an IDC report (October 2024), the global IT services market (systems integration, consulting and custom software development, hardware and software installation and support, IT training, and professional coaching) will reach \$ 1.1 trillion in 2024, up 3.4% from the previous year. In 2025–2026, it will grow annually by 3.8–4%, and in the medium term by 4.3%, mainly due to government digitalization programs, infrastructure and national projects.

Considering the practice of Chinese internet giants and ICT unicorns in their innovative market, who are willing to support Russian manufacturers and help restore the lost achievements of domestic programmers from the Soviet era, together with Indian and Malaysian software developers, it is safe to assume that the pace

of development of ICT technologies, and indeed the IT services market itself, will accelerate and drive the new model of the IT industry in modern Russia.

The primary and key driver of global market growth could be high demand for ICT startups and business services in areas where major government programs and projects for the digitalization of logistics and the financial sector are being implemented, as is currently the case in Europe and the Asia-Pacific region. At the same time, a potential growth driver is emerging from the resource potential of African and Eurasian Economic Union countries.

IT and business services market by region, \$ billion (forecast): IDC, 2021

The trend under study can be analyzed and highlighted by trends in the active transformation and growth of the IT services market, as well as challenges in identifying potential opportunities for the coming convergence of science, business, and consumers. Here, deep specialization in a narrow range of services is valued, leveraging expert capabilities and tailoring the needs of a specific client to personalized, specialized, comfortable, and creative capabilities and inherent competencies.

According to Statista 2., revenue in the IT services market (consulting, software development, systems integration, equipment installation and technical support, training, hosting, and outsourcing) will reach \$1.03 trillion in 2024. A significant portion of this revenue is expected to originate in the United States (\$380.4 billion). The most significant and largest market segment will be IT outsourcing, reaching \$359.8 billion, which will sustain and support the expected growth of this segment. In the coming years, the global IT services market is expected to grow by 7.89% annually, reaching \$1.51 trillion within five years. Based on forecasts from current analysts in the global ICT industry, average spending per employee in the IT services market will reach \$300.66 in 2024 and will increase by 5–8% annually 3..

At the end of 2024, Gartner analysts 4. noted that the IT services segment is one of the three fastest-growing trends in the global economic infrastructure in 2024, driven by increased IaaS spending. The total market size will reach \$ 1.176 trillion in 2024, up 9.8% from \$ 1.071 trillion in 2023. In 2026, the IT services market could grow by 8.5% to \$ 1.277 trillion, and with the reformatting of a number of scientific, technological, and industrial schools due to sanctions against Russia and Belarus, this could add another 0.3–0.5%. The pre-sanctions Russian IT services market (systems integration, consulting and custom software development, hardware and software installation and support, IT education and training) grew by 14.2% in rubles in 2020 to ₺411.61 billion, and by 4.9% in dollars to \$ 6.75 billion, according to IDC 4..

According to IDC analysts, in 2024–2025, the drivers of growing IT spending in the financial sector were driven by digitalization services offered by the global banking community. At the same time, acquiring services grew, personal and corporate financial security systems for clients were developed in the digital environment, and there was an active evolutionary process of mergers and acquisitions in the field of software products and services for online banking, the development of digital mobile applications, payment systems, and data transfer in e-commerce.

Largest IT Service Providers 2024

№ 2020	Name	Revenue in 2024, ₺ thousand, with VAT	Revenue in 2023, ₺ thousand, with VAT	Рост 2020/2019, %
1	Lanit	92271 563	80922 868	14,0%
2	Krok	21079 193	19971 155	5,5%
3	T1 Group (formerly Technoserv)	18131 113	18032 374	0,5%
4	Jet Infosystems	17439 001	16179 546	7,8%
5	Digital Economy League	16772 000	12195 000	37,5%

Source: CNews Analytics, 2024

The ongoing “greening” of the global economy and the global energy transition to ESG standards are forcing industrial manufacturers and innovation-oriented companies responsible for energy generation, distribution, and ICT architecture to further digitalize every aspect of their business processes and apply robotics and automation to existing systems using inclusive BIG DATA technologies and artificial intelligence (AI). This has led to an explosive growth of ideas and business models among e-commerce startups, from online platforms, marketplaces, and operational systems for product distribution zones, improving the post-COVID

trend of self-service in virtual networks, facilitating targeted services in delivery, storage, warehousing, and forecasting of material and information flows. However, recessionary trends in the global economic recovery have determined a selective approach to budgeting and financing various import substitution options worldwide, leading to a reduction in operations and redistribution of transnational supply chains, and have also impacted IT costs related to migration to hybrid clouds, with a phased and controlled transition to microservices architecture and container virtualization. Office-based work has led to the dominance of offline ICT structures in business, the securitization of various risks in the storage and transmission of personal data, the provision of local and corporate information security for servers and networks, and the targeted and consistent replacement of elements in the modernized IT architecture, including the implementation of software-defined infrastructure and hyperconverged solutions. These streams of future evolution within the digital transformation have begun to grow, both in informational and financial terms, as both the growing ecosystems and the expanding IT services segment have begun to be conceived and implemented through the development of proprietary virtual spaces for interaction, both within the network (for employees and managers) and in working with a client base that has grown significantly during lockdowns and some employees working from home or in coworking spaces.

According to Statista, revenue in the Russian IT services market (consulting, software development, systems integration, equipment installation and technical support, training, hosting, and outsourcing) could grow to \$6.49 billion in 2024. IT outsourcing will continue to be the main segment of the IT services market in Russia. The sector's growth forecast for 2024 could reach \$2.26 billion. By 2026, if sanctions are successfully overcome, the IT services market will grow by 6.98% annually, reaching \$9.096 billion. Average spending per employee in the IT services market could approach \$745.38 5..

IDC analysts 6. also expect the IT services market to grow in 2022, driven by demand for relevant replacements for global ICT giants that have left the Russian market, and by the observed increased demand for economic sovereignty. Cloud technologies and related services, infrastructure hosting, application management, software maintenance, upgrades, and administration will be in high demand. Accordingly, one of the main factors slowing this growth will be a shortage of qualified ICT specialists and experts, their migration, and the withdrawal of teams with anti-Russian sentiments from global IT projects involving international cooperation. A natural loss of financial resources from the IT services sector is also expected, either from companies that have collapsed completely or from the partial freezing of assets in the sector's development due to the post-COVID shocks of recent years. Moreover, growth trends in the ICT sector itself after the pandemic

are evolving in different directions and guarantee more accurate forecasts for trading and stock exchange operations, deeper and more comprehensive analysis of the development of new goods and services in behavioral economics, and also affect the speed of companies' recovery from the "black swan" effects of COVID and the escalating US and European sanctions. At the same time, the consequences of the coronavirus crisis are hardly clear-cut: some organizations are forced to increase investments in IT services. Thus, despite the mounting shocks and planned diversification and hedging of risks from global sanctions for the ongoing operation in Ukraine, Russia will be given a unique opportunity to individually develop "roadmaps" for emerging from autarky in Industry 4.0 in the field of ICT technologies and maintaining its participation in future global projects. Therefore, the very task of import substitution and the revival of scientific schools focused on best global practices and startups will have to become the norm and lay the foundations for imperial plans for a polycentric and multipolar world. Previously considered a fetish and a mirage, it is now becoming a matter of survival and sovereign self-sufficiency, based on threats to national security and overcoming technological dependence and backwardness relative to Western countries.

Existing labor resources and a coherent ideology within the state and abroad, based on patriotism and systematic action, will ensure the concentration of resources and create the conditions for the necessary technological and scientific breakthrough. This means there is a real opportunity to catch up with competitors in alternative knowledge and unique Russian competencies and maintain some of our influence in a world dominated by transnational capital and a reformed post-COVID corporatocracy.

When forming macroregions based on Eurasianism and the EAEU's institutions and EEC regulations, it is important to remember that trade, in addition to the ICT sphere discussed above, will also include work in the "Great Three," the RIC (Russia-India-China), and in the following areas:

- Energy and raw materials;
- Transport and logistics;
- Economic cooperation agreements/potential free trade zone;
- Pharmaceuticals/medicine;
- Defense-technical cooperation and high technologies for the military-industrial complex and space;
- Agriculture and fertilizers.

For example, when forming a macro-region with India, we can talk about:

- International North-South Transport Corridor (INSTC/NSITC) — active work on developing land-sea routes between India and Russia/EAEU countries.
 - Energy supplies (long-term oil/LNG contracts) between Russian suppliers and Indian buyers — a significant contribution to trade turnover.
-

- Pharmaceutical partnership — export of finished vaccines and drugs, negotiations on technology transfer/production partnerships.

- Discussions about establishing a free trade area between the EAEU and India are planned to resume in 2025.

- In 2024, trade between the EAEU and India amounted to \$69 billion.

And with Brazil, the EAEU is building supply chains in the following areas:

- Agribusiness and agricultural technology;

- Mining and metallurgy;

- Science and education;

- Trade and economic dialogues between the EAEU and Mercosur/Brazil;

- Trade turnover between the EAEU and Brazil in the first eight months of 2024 increased by 15.9% compared to the same period in 2023. EAEU exports to Brazil increased by 32.1%.

However, despite successes in foreign trade, a macro-regional partnership is unlikely to materialize here, given Trump's return to the "Monroe Doctrine," which, as exemplified by the expected invasion of Mexico, has become the "Dolro Doctrine" of Trump the Conqueror himself.

Macro-regional cooperation between the EAEU and South Africa may be simpler. Specifically, in 2024, a dialogue was held with business representatives in South Africa to address the issue of escaping Anglo-Saxon colonial pressure.

- Discussion of prospects for mutually beneficial cooperation in agriculture between the EAEU member states and South Africa, and issues of expanding access for agricultural products and food produced in the EAEU to third-country markets.

- Issues of developing crop production and seed production, including the use of innovative technologies to improve agricultural efficiency and the competitiveness of crop products in the EAEU domestic market and third-country markets. Therefore, all existing foreign trade options within the EAEU must now take control of both resources and GVCs (global value chains) in order to understand the unity of goals and the perfection of mechanisms for future interaction and diversification of growing currency and country risks.

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THE ROLE OF MARXIST-LENINIST IDEOLOGY IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF A UNIFIED ERITREAN NATIONAL IDENTITY: 1961–PRESENT

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Abstract. *This study analyses the role of Marxist-Leninist ideology in the formation and consolidation of Eritrean national identity during the struggle for national independence (1961–1991) and in the post-independence period. Through a systematic meta-synthesis of twenty-one scholarly works published between 1983 and 2024, three principal interpretive positions are identified and examined: Marxist-Leninist ideology as the primary mechanism for transcending ethno-linguistic fragmentation, as an instrumental rhetoric concealing an underlying ethno-nationalist project, and as a source of hybrid revolutionary nationalism with an unconstitutional consequence. The analysis demonstrates that while the ideology facilitated unprecedented organizational cohesion during the armed struggle, its vanguardist institutional legacy has significantly shaped the centralized and non-pluralist character of the post-1993 Eritrean state.*

Keywords: *Eritrean nationalism, Marxist-Leninist ideology, Eritrean People's Liberation Front (EPLF), national identity formation*

Introduction

The Eritrean struggle for independence constitutes one of the longest armed liberation movements in twentieth-century Africa. Between 1961 and 1991, the Eritrean People's Liberation Front (EPLF) succeeded in mobilizing a multi-ethnic population divided across nine ethno-linguistic communities and two major religions against successive Ethiopian regimes. From the mid-1970s the Front formally adopted Marxist-Leninist ideology, established a clandestine Marxist-Leninist party (the Eritrean People's Revolutionary Party, 1971–1989), and implemented comprehensive political education programs throughout the liberated and semi-liberated areas (Pool, 2001; Iyob, 1995: pp. 114–127).

Following Eritrea's independence in 1993, the leadership gradually moved away from socialist economic policies, deferred the implementation of the 1997 constitution, and established a centralized governance system (Alidu et al., 2023). Such political trajectory raises a core research problem: to what extent did Marxist-Leninist ideology serve as a genuine instrument of supra-ethnic national integration, and to what extent was it a conditional framework later discarded when no longer strategically useful?

Research objectives

To evaluate the most common interpretative frameworks through a structured critical debate rather than descriptive review.

To assess the framework that most adequately explains both the cohesion achieved during the armed struggle and the political trajectory of independent Eritrea

Methods and Materials

The study employs qualitative meta-synthesis of twenty peer-reviewed journal articles, book chapters, and monographs published in English, French, and Italian between 1983 and 2024. Sources were retrieved through systematic searches in JSTOR, Project MUSE, Scopus, AfricaBib, and Google Scholar using Boolean combinations of the terms "Eritrea," "EPLF," "Marxist-Leninist," "ideology," "nationalism," and "identity." Only works containing substantive analytical sections (minimum 15 pages or equivalent) on the ideological dimension of Eritrean nationalism were included. Citation and reference chaining supplemented the database searches.

Results

As a starting point, a significant body of scholarship maintains that Marxist-Leninist ideology provided the essential universalist language and organizational technology required to overcome ethno-linguistic and religious fragmentation (Pool 1983; Pateman 1990; Iyob 1995; Connell 1997; Pool 2001; Hepner 2009; O'Kane & Hepner 2011; Bereketeab 2016). The EPLF's 1977 and 1987 National Democratic Programs explicitly committed the movement to scientific socialism and the creation of a new democratic society. Political education departments operated in every military unit and liberated village, while regular criticism and self-criticism sessions (*gimgema*) were institutionalised as mechanisms of ideological conformity and collective identity formation. Iyob (1995) describes this process as the substitution of a secular salvation narrative for particularistic loyalties, whereas Pool (2001) emphasizes the adaptation of Maoist mass-line techniques to local conditions, producing a distinctively Eritrean form of revolutionary practice.

A second group of scholars contend that Marxist-Leninist discourse was adopted primarily for pragmatic reasons in the 1970s, mainly to secure material and

diplomatic support from the Soviet bloc and South Yemen after the Arab-oriented Eritrean Liberation Front (ELF) fragmented (Cliffe 1989; Markakis 1995; Tronvoll 1998; Reid 2003; Woldemikael 2009; Hirt & Mohammad 2018; Riggan 2021). These authors point to the rapid abandonment of socialist terminology after 1991, the sidelining of Muslim and lowland communities in senior state and party positions, and the continued dominance of Tigrinya and Arabic as the working language of government as evidence that the ideology lacked deep roots. Tronvoll (1998) characterizes the EPLF's Marxism-Leninism as a "flag of convenience," while Hirt and Mohammad (2018) argue that the post-liberation order represents revolutionary nationalism stripped of its revolutionary content.

A third interpretive current seeks synthesis, arguing that Marxist-Leninist ideology was simultaneously instrumental and internalized, producing a distinctive Eritrean revolutionary nationalism rather than either pure socialism or pure ethno-nationalism (Young 1996; Bundegaard 2004; Müller 2012; Plaut 2016; Killion 2017; Bereketeab 2020; Riggan & Pool 2022). The organizational practices developed during the struggle — centralized democratic centralism, perpetual mobilization, the sacralization of martyrdom, and the subordination of individual rights to collective goals — were retained after independence. Müller (2012) contends that the EPLF did not betray Marxist-Leninist principles but rather realized their controlling potential in a new national context. Similarly, Bereketeab (2020) describes the post-1993 political system as exhibiting "vanguardist continuity" rooted in the liberation-era ideological apparatus.

Discussion

The first interpretive current most convincingly accounts for the remarkable internal cohesion and low desertion rates observed during the armed struggle, phenomena difficult to explain through ethno-nationalist mobilization alone. The second interpretive current, mainly explains the speed and thoroughness with which socialist policies and rhetoric were discarded after 1991, as well as persistent grievances among lowland communities articulate regarding cultural and political marginalization. The third provides the strongest explanation for long-term institutional continuity: the same vanguardist mechanisms that enabled a small movement to defeat a much larger Ethiopian army have been redeployed to justify indefinite national service, the absence of political pluralism, and the postponement of constitutional practices. The 1998–2000 border war with Ethiopia and the subsequent "no war, no peace" stalemate further entrenched the liberation-era mindset that only the vanguard can define and defend the nation.

Conclusion

Marxist-Leninist ideology functioned neither as the essence nor as a mere mask of Eritrean nationalism, but as a formative mold that shaped both the achievements and the limitations of the nationalist project. It supplied a universalist framework and rigorous organizational discipline that temporarily superseded ethno-linguistic divisions, yet it also transmitted a political culture predicated on the permanent subordination of pluralism to vanguard-defined national objectives. The Eritrean case indicates that when revolutionary ideologies are successfully indigenized within multi-ethnic liberation movements, they rarely vanish after independence; instead, they undergo transformation into new techniques of state power and national legitimacy.

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THE PROBLEM OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE RESULTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The rapid development of digital technologies and the introduction of artificial intelligence into the creation and dissemination of intellectual property necessitate an analysis of the legal regulation of works created using artificial intelligence and the provision of adequate protection. This article examines the legal regime governing results generated by generative artificial intelligence algorithms and analyzes key doctrinal positions regarding their legal nature. Particular attention is paid to determining the originality of such results, issues of international jurisdiction, and the ethical aspects of using works created using artificial intelligence algorithms. Based on the study, it is concluded that it is necessary to adapt current legislation and develop a specialized approach to the legal protection of works created using artificial intelligence technologies. This approach entails the normative recognition of the status of such results and the definition of criteria for their inclusion in the copyright system, taking into account the role of artificial intelligence as a tool for human creative activity.*

Key words: *artificial intelligence, copyright, related rights, intellectual property objects, results of artificial intelligence activities.*

Currently, the use of artificial intelligence technologies is gradually permeating all spheres of public life. Works created using generative algorithms are becoming an integral part of contemporary artistic practice, business operations, educational platforms, and the visual communications sphere. In the Russian cultural sphere, this trend was manifested in the organization of a special exhibition held at the New Tretyakov Gallery in 2025, which featured works created through the interaction of contemporary artists, developers, and artificial intelligence technologies 1..

Moreover, questions about the use of artificial intelligence are also being raised in the public sphere, particularly in the justice sector. Initiatives being discussed at the level of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation demonstrate recognition of the potential of artificial intelligence technologies for automating technical aspects

of judicial activity, particularly in those areas that do not require the analysis of complex legal relationships and are characterized by routine data processing 2..

It is becoming clear that with the expansion of the scope of application of artificial intelligence, there is a need to determine the legal status of the results created through its use.

In Russian legislation, the legal definition of artificial intelligence is contained in Federal Law No. 123-FZ of April 24, 2020, which defines it as a set of technological solutions that imitate human cognitive functions, including the ability to self-learn and search for innovative solutions, while achieving results comparable to the products of human intellectual activity.

Current legal doctrine and practice in various countries have not developed a unified approach to defining works created using artificial intelligence technologies. It seems reasonable to understand such works as the results of algorithmic information processing, during which a computer system generates an original intellectual product with independent value. The range of such results is extremely broad and includes both forms of artistic expression, such as paintings, literary texts, and poetic compositions, and more complex intellectual objects, such as software modules, analytical reviews, or specialized materials used in professional legal work.

According to a position based on a literal interpretation of current civil law, works created by artificial intelligence systems cannot be classified as objects of copyright. This conclusion is based on the provisions of Part One of Article 1228 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, which stipulates that the author of a result of intellectual activity is exclusively the individual whose creative work created the relevant object. Proponents of this approach point out that, given the current level of technological development, artificial intelligence does not possess the capacity for independent creative activity. The algorithms underlying its functioning allow it to generate results based on predetermined data and statistical models, which is inconsistent with the traditional notion of creativity as a manifestation of individual design and original intellectual contribution 3, p. 328..

This viewpoint is also reflected in judicial practice. In their conclusions, the courts rely on the clarifications contained in Resolution No. 10 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated April 23, 2019, which explicitly states that results obtained using technical means in the absence of human creative participation do not constitute objects of copyright 4.. Thus, judicial practice confirms the persistence of the anthropocentric approach, which presupposes the mandatory creative contribution of a person as a condition for the emergence of copyright protection.

The legal doctrine also proposes other options for normatively establishing the status of works created using artificial intelligence.

Thus, one approach suggests the possibility of protecting results created by artificial intelligence through a mechanism of related rights, similar to the legal

regime of the publisher 5, p. 102.. According to this concept, a work created by artificial intelligence is proposed to be equated to a work that has entered the public domain, while the person who organized the process of its creation would acquire the exclusive right of the publisher to the published result.

A. I. Balashova develops this approach to the legal protection of results created by artificial intelligence, pointing to the possibility of using the related rights model for phonograms to regulate relations in this area. In her research, she emphasizes that the exclusive right to a phonogram belongs to the person who took the initiative and responsibility for the initial recording of sounds or their representations. Furthermore, legislation does not require a specific person to make a creative contribution to its creation, allowing the legal regime for phonograms to be considered as potentially applicable to results created by artificial intelligence 6, p. 96..

Another point of view is that independent related rights should be established for results created by artificial intelligence. This approach has become widespread in the scientific literature, as it allows for the legal protection of such results without changing the fundamental provisions of copyright law. Within this approach, it is proposed that the exclusive right be assigned to the person who organized the functioning of the artificial intelligence system in the creation of the work, which would grant such an organizer an independent related right for a period of twenty-five to fifty years, similar to that of the producer of a phonogram, database, or publisher 7.. However, it is noted that the limited duration and scope of protection under related rights precludes a level of legal protection comparable to copyrighted works.

Another scientific approach suggests extending the public domain regime to works created with the help of artificial intelligence, which implies the possibility of free use of such a work 8, p. 44–45.. The authors of this concept believe that for results created by artificial intelligence, the moment of transition into the public domain should occur not after the expiration of the protection period, but directly at the moment of their creation. An obvious drawback of this model is the lack of economic motivation among developers and users of artificial intelligence, which prevents the full integration of such objects into civil circulation.

A position has also been expressed that the problem of attributing authorship to results created by artificial intelligence can be resolved by analogy with the legal regime for works after the author's death. Despite the termination of property rights, personal non-property rights remain and are subject to protection, which, according to L. V. Borisova, allows for the possibility of establishing a similar protection mechanism for works created by artificial intelligence 9, p. 119..

It seems reasonable to proceed from the fact that artificial intelligence, regardless of the level of technological complexity of its architecture, should be considered as a technical means that ensures the creation of a new result, since the functioning of such systems is based on given parameters and statistical models, and not on their

own conscious expression of will or the presence of an independent creative idea 10, p. 460.. The most rational solution seems to be the regulatory consolidation of exclusive rights for persons who ensure the process of creating a work through the use of artificial intelligence 11..

However, such a proposal does not eliminate all theoretical and practical difficulties, but on the contrary, gives rise to a set of questions that require separate analysis.

First and foremost, determining the originality of results created using artificial intelligence presents difficulties, as traditional criteria developed for human creativity do not always allow one to determine the degree of independence of such a work. During their work, generative algorithms rely on training data, which does not preclude the emergence of elements similar to existing objects and complicates the assessment of the creative novelty of the resulting result 12, p. 73..

Another problem is determining international jurisdiction, as national legal systems regulate the protection of works created using artificial intelligence differently and approach the issue of attribution differently. The lack of agreed-upon international standards means that a work may be protected in one jurisdiction but not in another, complicating the circulation of such results. Consequently, difficulties are also observed in the commercialization of works created using artificial intelligence, due to the lack of a legally established legal regime for them. The uncertainty regarding the scope of rights in relation to such results complicates the conclusion of licensing agreements, the formalization of other methods of disposing of rights, and the determination of their economic value 13..

Ethical issues arising from the use of works created using generative artificial intelligence algorithms also require special consideration. Scientific literature notes that such algorithms are trained on datasets, a significant portion of which includes copyrighted material, raising debate about the permissibility of such use and the limits of respect for the intellectual property rights of copyright holders 14.. At the same time, questions are being raised about the limits of acceptable substitution for human creativity and the impact of the widespread use of artificial intelligence on the creative process itself.

Thus, it appears that the further development of artificial intelligence technologies will inevitably be accompanied by discussions about the legal nature of the results created by generative algorithms. The increasing autonomy of algorithmic systems requires the adaptation and consistent updating of current legal regulations, as existing copyright and related law provisions are not applicable to results created using artificial intelligence technologies and do not provide adequate legal protection 15..

To ensure such legal protection, it appears necessary to further refine legal regulation, aimed at formalizing an approach in which results created using artificial intelligence technologies are considered works created using a technical

tool similar to software, without granting artificial intelligence the status of an independent author. Implementation of this approach requires the preliminary resolution of a range of theoretical and practical issues related to determining the user's creative contribution, establishing criteria for the originality of such results, and clarifying the limits of permissible use of algorithmic systems in the creation of copyrighted works.

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CORRUPTION — A SOCIAL AND LEGAL PHENOMENON (NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL ASPECTS)

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Abstract. *This article examines corruption as a transnational problem facing the entire global community. The authors emphasize that combating corruption requires special attention, as this dangerous phenomenon leads to negative consequences such as violations of the constitutional foundations of the state, the rights and freedoms of citizens, social inequality, and public mistrust of government and its institutions. Algorithms for improving this area are proposed.*

Key words: *corruption risks, healthcare, tasks and goals of combating corruption, regulatory and legal acts, programs (State and Republican), as well as Comprehensive Plans to Combat Crime and Corruption*

Corruption is a transnational problem facing the entire global community. Corruption devalues democratic values, hinders the stable development of societies, effective governance, and economic growth, and undermines their security. The fight against corruption requires special attention, as this dangerous phenomenon leads to negative consequences such as the violation of the constitutional foundations of the state, the rights and freedoms of citizens, social inequality, and public mistrust of government and its institutions 2..

Corruption can be compared to an octopus that has extended its tentacles into all spheres of life, or to rust that corrodes everything in its path.

Corruption violates all the foundations of society, the rights and interests of citizens, negatively affects the legal, moral and ethical state of society, and therefore public state institutions counteract this social phenomenon.

The creation of an effective legal mechanism to combat corruption in various areas of social activity, including healthcare, is the key to the sustainable development of the state.

The legal basis for anti-corruption activities in Belarusian legislation is laid down in the Basic Law (the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus), regulating the most important social relations 7.. In particular, Article 2 of the Constitution of the Basic Law states that a person, his rights, freedoms and guarantees of their implementation are the highest value and goal of society and the state. In addition, the state is responsible to the citizen for creating conditions for the free and dignified development of the individual. In turn, the citizen is responsible to the state for the strict fulfillment of the duties imposed on him by the Constitution. Article 21 of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus also establishes that ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens of the Republic of Belarus is the highest goal of the state.

Corruption (Latin: *corruptio*) literally means bribery; venality and venality of public and political figures, government officials and officials.

To corrupt (Latin: *corrumpere*) — to bribe someone with money or other material goods 5..

The official interpretation of corruption and other legal bases for combating corruption are formulated in the Law of the Republic of Belarus of July 15, 2015 No. 305-Z (as amended and supplemented on December 30, 2022 No. 232-Z) “On the Fight against Corruption” 8..

In accordance with Article 1 of this Law, corruption is the intentional use by a public official or a person equivalent to him or a foreign official of his official position and the opportunities associated with it for the purpose of illegally obtaining property or other benefits in the form of work, services, patronage, or the promise of an advantage for himself or herself or for third parties, as well as bribery of a public official or a person equivalent to him or a foreign official by providing them with property or other benefits in the form of work, services, patronage, or the promise of an advantage for them or for third parties so that this public official or a person equivalent to him or a foreign official performs actions or refrains from performing them in the performance of their official (labor) duties, as well as the commission of the said actions on behalf of or in the interests of a legal entity, including a foreign one 3,4..

The objectives and goals of combating corruption are generally stated in the preamble to the Law of the Republic of Belarus “On Combating Corruption.” The Law establishes the legal foundations of state policy in the fight against corruption and aims to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens and public interests from threats arising from corruption, and to ensure the effective operation of government bodies, other organizations, government officials, and equivalent persons by preventing, detecting, and suppressing offenses that create conditions for corruption, as well as corruption-related offenses, and eliminating their consequences.

A significant element of the current regulatory framework in the field of combating corruption in the Republic of Belarus are the programs (State and

Republican) systematically adopted since 2006, as well as the Comprehensive Plans for Combating Crime and Corruption, which define strategic directions and measures for their implementation.

The anti-corruption legislation of the Republic of Belarus also consists of other regulatory legal acts aimed at preventing, combating, and guarding against corruption. These include:

- Law of the Republic of Belarus dated 01.06.2022 No. 175-Z “On Civil Service”;
- Law of the Republic of Belarus of July 13, 2012 No. 419-Z “On public procurement of goods (works, services)”;
- Law of the Republic of Belarus of January 4, 2014 No. 122-Z “On the Fundamentals of Activities for the Prevention of Offenses”;
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Belarus of December 15, 2014 No. 5 “On strengthening the requirements for management personnel and employees of organizations”;
- Directive of the President of the Republic of Belarus of March 11, 2004 No. 1 “On measures to strengthen public security and discipline”;
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Belarus of July 16, 2007 No. 330 “On special units for combating corruption and organized crime”;
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Belarus of December 17, 2007 No. 644 “On approval of the Regulation on the activities of the coordinating meeting to combat crime and corruption”;
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Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Belarus of May 10, 2019, No. 3 “On additional measures to combat corruption,” the Criminal Code prohibits the presentation of persons convicted of committing corruption crimes for parole or replacement of the unserved portion of the sentence with a more lenient one.

The Prosecutor General’s Office of the Republic of Belarus, as the coordinating agency responsible for combating corruption, also reviews legislation for potential for corruption. For this purpose, the Scientific and Practical Center for Strengthening Law and Order of the Prosecutor’s Office of the Republic of Belarus was established by Decree No. 482 of the President of the Republic of Belarus dated August 3, 2006, “On the Establishment of a State Institution.” This Scientific

and Practical Center is part of the prosecutor's office system and reports directly to the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Belarus.

The center's primary functions are to conduct criminological research aimed at addressing strategic crime-fighting challenges, developing scientifically sound measures for its prevention, strengthening law and order, increasing the effectiveness of prosecutorial oversight, improving law enforcement practices and legislation, conducting mandatory criminological examinations of draft laws, and implementing the results of scientific research into practical activities.

To ensure the organization of anti-corruption measures, the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Belarus accumulates information on facts indicating corruption; analyzes the effectiveness of measures taken to combat corruption; coordinates the law enforcement activities of other government agencies engaged in the fight against corruption; oversees compliance by heads of government agencies and other organizations with anti-corruption legislation and, in the event of violations, takes measures to hold those responsible accountable; prepares proposals for improving the legal regulation of the fight against corruption, etc.

Corruption risks in healthcare.

Based on paragraph (subparagraph) 10.1 of paragraph (paragraph) 10 of the decision of the Eighteenth Republican Coordination Meeting on Combating Crime and Corruption dated December 22, 2018, the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Belarus has developed Methodological Recommendations for Organizing Anti-Corruption Work in Government Agencies and Organizations. Corruption risk analysis is carried out in the following areas:

1) identification and assessment of corruption risks in legal acts regulating the activities of a government body or organization, for the presence of:

- provisions that facilitate the official's decision-making at his own discretion;
- provisions that contribute to the creation of barriers to the exercise by individuals and legal entities of their rights and legitimate interests;
- legal gaps that create the possibility of arbitrary interpretation of regulatory legal acts.

2) identification of corruption risks in organizational and managerial activities aimed at establishing facts of violation of the law in the event of:

- conducting procurement of goods, works (services);
- implementation of state supervision and control;
- preparation and adoption of decisions on the distribution of budgetary and extra-budgetary funds, other property, payment of taxes and fees, as well as penalties and fines;
- disposal of state property, property of an organization, including when implementing lease relations;

- licensing of certain types of activities, issuing permits and other similar actions, conducting examinations and issuing opinions;
- conducting administrative proceedings;
- conducting official investigations and inspections;
- implementation of administrative procedures;
- determining the amount and form of remuneration, as well as material incentives;
- allocation of housing, land, loans, and provision of other social benefits.

The above list is not exhaustive.

The assessment of corruption risks arising in the activities of government bodies and organizations consists of determining:

- functions and operations vulnerable to corruption;
- employees who, in the context of carrying out functions and operations vulnerable to corruption, may be involved in corrupt practices due to the official powers they exercise (rights and obligations, work functions);
- types of corruption offenses that may be committed during the performance of a function or operation;
- the nature and extent of possible damage (harm);
- the likelihood of committing a corrupt act and causing damage (harm);
- factors that contribute to the emergence of vulnerability to corruption of individual functions, operations or employees;
- factors influencing the nature and extent of damage, as well as contributing to its increase or decrease.

• In particular, when studying corruption risks in the implementation of administrative procedures The analysis is carried out for the presence of:

- compliance of actual processes of implementing administrative procedures with approved regulatory requirements;
- requesting documents not provided for by law;
- direct contact between officials and the applicant;
- proper operation of information systems;
- facts of violation of deadlines for the implementation of administrative procedures;
- facts of unjustified refusal to carry out administrative procedures;
- the multiplicity and duplication of stages of document review.
- When conducting an assessment, information on corruption risks can be obtained from the following sources:

- regulatory legal acts governing the activities of the organization;
- results of inspections, audits, inventories;
- court decisions, acts of prosecutorial supervision, documents received from bodies engaged in the fight against corruption, other law enforcement and regulatory bodies;

- appeals from citizens and legal entities, publications in the media, etc.

Based on the results of the corruption risk assessment, information is prepared for consideration at meetings of the Anti-Corruption Commission. This information may include information on identified corruption risks, recommendations for addressing them, timelines for implementing recommendations to address identified corruption risks, and more.

The Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus has approved a corruption risk map indicating corruption -prone functions, typical situations, and risk mitigation measures.

Prevention and suppression of corruption offenses.

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Belarus “On the Fundamentals of Crime Prevention” (including corruption) on January 4, 2014, was aimed at systematically combating criminal activity. The law established the legal and organizational foundations for crime prevention activities and codified the main forms of participation of government agencies (organizations), other organizations, and citizens in this activity.

The social value of the Law lies in its definition of an effective algorithm for preventing offenses, which consists of neutralizing their causes and conditions, and provides for the achievement of this goal through the implementation of the functions assigned to government bodies. The Republic of Belarus is the first CIS member state to conceptually develop and enshrine in law a system of measures for the prevention and control of offenses.

According to Article 1 of the Law under consideration, crime prevention is defined as the application of general and/or individual crime prevention measures by crime prevention agencies in accordance with legislation. The system of preventive measures is thus subdivided in the above definition into general and individual preventive measures.

Thus, at the current stage of development of the national legal doctrine, the issue of crime prevention is considered in relation to several independent prevention systems:

1) a system that is functionally implemented and realized at the level of managing social processes, including in the area of preventing social deviations in people’s behavior, primarily by raising the standard of living (general prevention);

2) a system that is based on the preventive properties of measures of influence implemented in the process of applying criminal liability measures in relation to persons guilty of committing offenses (individual prevention).

While performing similar tasks within the framework of social control, these preventive systems have different legal natures. The first has a clearly defined social and managerial dynamic and falls within the sphere of administrative and legal regulation. In the second case, preventive control, implemented through a system of criminal liability measures, has an individually defined focus; the nature

and scope of impact in this case are determined by the content of criminal liability and depend on the form of its implementation 9..

Coordination of crime prevention activities within the scope of their competence is carried out by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Belarus and subordinate prosecutors of territorial and specialized prosecutor's offices, including through the organization of coordination meetings on combating crime and corruption.

As a segment of combating corruption offenses at the regulatory level, one can also consider the creation of a system of ethical codes, such as the Code of Professional Ethics of Journalists of 1995, the Code of Honor of Judges of 1997, the Code of Medical Ethics of 1998, the Rules of Professional Ethics of Lawyers of 2012, and others.

The main conclusions of the study are as follows and concern the current state of corruption in the world and the complex of corruption-generating factors, as well as methods of criminal-legal qualification of corruption crimes, other areas of the fight against corruption at the national level and the global anti-corruption strategy existing within the international community.

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INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS FOR LEGAL PRACTICE

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Abstract. *This article examines current issues related to the standardization of legal practice in Russia and examines international experience in this area. The author analyzes the current state of Russian legislation, identifying the lack of clear criteria for assessing the quality of legal assistance. Practical recommendations are offered for introducing new standards for legal practice, including the creation of a separate chapter in the Code of Professional Ethics for Lawyers and the establishment of a system for regular professional development for lawyers. A proposal is made to include a special section devoted to standards for legal practice, which would create a foundation for further legislative development and enhance public confidence in the legal profession.*

Key words: *international standards of advocacy, professional qualifications of lawyers, code of professional ethics, legal assistance*

The work of lawyers, as a vital element of the legal system striving to ensure justice and the rule of law, is influenced by global processes and requires a unified approach. International standards of legal practice serve as the foundation for the development of national legislative frameworks regulating the legal profession, as well as a guide for the professional ethics and practice of lawyers worldwide. These standards, developed based on decades of experience and collective wisdom, are designed to guarantee access to justice, the protection of human rights and freedoms, and the independence of the legal profession.

Current trends of rapid globalization and the intensive development of the international political arena have necessitated the development of unified standards designed to clearly regulate the quality of legal services and the professional activities of specialists in this area of law. Consequently, the role of organizations engaged in quality standardization, such as the International Standardization Organization (ISO), has rapidly increased, taking on the role of creating unified regulatory documents. The primary goal of ISO is to establish a fundamental methodological

framework upon which programs can be developed to monitor the performance of lawyers' professional duties, which, in turn, allows for the modification and improvement of these programs. The established standard presupposes the existence of a comprehensive system incorporating specific components necessary for its effective functioning. To ensure the practical applicability of such a standardization system, it is critical to consider several key aspects: its provisions must be consistent with current legal norms, documented, regulated through a systems approach, and, of course, comply with current legislation.

Currently, all developing countries successfully apply established standards as a benchmark for advancing legal development, and the legal system, particularly the legal profession, is no exception, complying with these regulations. At the same time, each country, taking into account the specifics of its legal system, which are largely dependent on economic and political conditions, strives to adapt general global provisions recognized internationally to its national realities, while adhering to generally accepted principles 7, p. 28..

The emergence and development of international standards for legal practice are inextricably linked to the evolution of ideas about human rights and the role of legal aid in ensuring them. A key moment in this process was the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), which enshrined the right of everyone to a fair and public hearing by an impartial and independent tribunal, as well as the right to a defense.

The Charter of the United Nations, in turn, reaffirms the desire to create conditions where the rule of law prevails and emphasizes the importance of cooperation in strengthening respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, regardless of any differences 3, p. 2..

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted in 1966, builds on these principles, proclaiming everyone's right to liberty and security of person. No one may be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention, and deprivation of liberty may only be lawful and in accordance with established procedures. Importantly, this covenant provides for the right to compensation for victims of unlawful arrest or detention, thereby reminding authorities of their responsibility.

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, concluded in 1950, also confirms the right to liberty and security of person, establishing that restriction of liberty is possible only in cases and in a manner strictly defined by law.

The Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment is invaluable in ensuring the rights of persons subject to detention or imprisonment. This document, endorsed by a UN General Assembly resolution, categorically prohibits arbitrary detention and guarantees detainees treatment equal to that of unconvicted persons. It particularly emphasizes the right

of detainees to prompt and confidential consultation with a lawyer, as well as to meet with their lawyer in conditions that ensure confidentiality.

The key document defining the role of lawyers is the Basic Provisions on the Role of Lawyers, adopted by the VIII United Nations Crime Congress. These provisions are based on the premise that the effective protection of human rights presupposes genuine access to legal assistance provided by an independent legal profession. The document details aspects of access to legal assistance, special guarantees in the criminal justice system, requirements for the qualifications and training of lawyers, their duties and responsibilities, and guarantees for their professional activities, including freedom of expression and association. The status of professional associations of lawyers is also defined 5, pp. 295–296..

Specialized international organizations and professional associations have played and continue to play a decisive role in the development and promotion of standards for legal practice. The International Bar Association (IBA) is a leading voice in this field. Its documents, such as the Basic Principles on the Role of Lawyers, adopted at the Eighth United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders in 1990, have become a cornerstone for understanding the essence of lawyer independence and its place in the justice system. These principles emphasize that lawyers must be able to perform all their professional duties without hindrance, threats, harassment, or improper interference. States are obligated to ensure lawyers' access to relevant information, advice, and assistance, as well as to guarantee their freedom of movement and communication with clients.

Another important document developed by the IBA is the Guiding Principles on the Right to Legal Aid. They detail states' obligations to ensure access to legal aid for all, especially vulnerable groups, and emphasize the need for effective mechanisms of financial and other support for those who cannot afford legal services. These guidelines address issues of the quality of legal aid, the training of lawyers, and their independence in decision-making regarding the conduct of cases.

The European Union has also made a significant contribution to the development of international standards for the legal profession, particularly in the context of European integration and the harmonization of legal systems. Article 47 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 326/02) proclaims everyone's right to an effective remedy and a fair trial. This article, like the provisions of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (1950), including Article 6, which guarantees the right to a fair trial, implicitly but inevitably implies the need for an independent and competent legal profession.

At the Council of Europe level, Recommendation CM/ Rec (2000)21 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the role of lawyers in society plays an important role. It establishes a number of principles concerning the independence of lawyers, their professional ethics, access to the profession, and professional

development. This document emphasizes that lawyers must be free from any external pressure and must act exclusively in the interests of their clients, while respecting the law and professional standards.

Russian legislation has its limitations. As E. N. Kalacheva noted, Russian legislation still lacks a clear understanding of what exactly constitutes “qualified legal assistance” and the criteria by which it should be evaluated. Although Federal Law No. 324-FZ “On Free Legal Aid” does reference this concept, specific, legally enshrined quality standards for such services simply do not exist. The law provides only for general quality oversight, which in practice can only be provided by lawyers and notaries, as they are bound by professional codes of ethics. Unfortunately, however, such a quality control procedure still does not exist for lawyers working in law firms.

Experts believe it’s time to establish clear rules of the game — to develop and formalize standards for legal assistance. For example, O. V. Pospelov proposed creating a separate section, “Standards of Advocacy,” in the Code of Professional Ethics for Advocates. His idea is to make these standards a normative document, binding even on the courts. S. N. Gavrilov, in turn, emphasizes that such standards are not a whim, but a necessary condition for everyone to truly receive high-quality legal support, as guaranteed by the Constitution 2, pp. 53–54..

The Bar Association itself is already taking steps forward: the Standard for Defense in Criminal Proceedings and the Standard for Professional Training and Continuing Education of Lawyers have been approved. These are important measures aimed at ensuring that lawyers operate according to uniform rules, continually improve their skills, and provide consistently high-quality defense in criminal cases. However, common standards for all free legal aid are still being developed and approved.

A. G. Sevostyanova emphasized that the most important thing for protecting our rights is for lawyers to be truly independent. This principle is so important that even countries always pay attention to it when drafting their laws. And this independence is needed not only by lawyers themselves, but by the entire judicial system, by all of us, and by the state as a whole. In democratic countries, a lawyer’s job is to ensure justice is fair and to defend the interests of those under attack — especially if they are accused or their rights are restricted.

Another important rule for lawyers is that they are prohibited from engaging in business while working. However, opinions differ somewhat here: some places impose a complete ban, while others permit certain types of entrepreneurship, provided everything is done according to the rules. For example, in Europe, such exceptions are allowed, but only if the lawyer remains equally independent.

When it comes to international standards, a lawyer is simply obligated to be honest and adhere to ethical norms and the law. And perhaps most importantly, maintaining client confidentiality is crucial. Everything you tell your lawyer is strictly personal information, and it will not be shared anywhere else. It’s also

worth noting that lawyer liability insurance is becoming increasingly common. This is done to foster trust and to protect lawyers in the event of claims arising due to errors 6, pp. 308–309..

The influence of international standards on national legislation manifests itself in various ways. They serve as a guideline for the development and improvement of laws on the legal profession, defining access to the profession, the rights and obligations of lawyers, their responsibilities, and guarantees of independence. For example, the laws of many countries reflect the principle that lawyers cannot be held liable for actions taken in the performance of their professional duties if they acted in accordance with the law and ethical standards.

International standards influence the development of ethical codes for lawyers. These codes typically include provisions regarding integrity, confidentiality, loyalty to clients, professional competence, and the avoidance of conflicts of interest. They also establish rules of conduct for lawyers in their interactions with the court, other lawyers, and the public at large.

Standards play a role in ensuring access to justice. They encourage the creation of legal aid systems, including state aid for the poor, as well as the development of mechanisms for bar associations aimed at providing free legal assistance.

The independence of the legal profession is a central element of international standards. It is understood as the ability of lawyers to carry out their activities free from external influence, whether from the state, political parties, economic interests, or other groups 1, p. 60.. This independence is essential for lawyers to effectively protect their clients' rights, act as trusted advisors, and promote the rule of law. States, in accordance with international principles, must guarantee freedom of speech and association for lawyers and protect them from unjustified persecution or discrimination.

Professional competence of lawyers is also an integral part of international standards. This requires that lawyers possess sufficient knowledge, skills, and experience to provide qualified legal assistance. International standards emphasize the need for lawyers to continuously develop their professional skills, participate in continuing education and training programs, and strictly adhere to ethical standards.

The governance of legal practice is also subject to international standards. This includes issues of access to the profession, disciplinary liability, and self-regulation of lawyers' associations. International principles emphasize the importance of transparency and fairness in processes related to lawyers' professional activities and guarantee the right to a defense in the event of disciplinary action.

According to I. V. Kvach, the successful implementation of international standards for the legal profession requires a well-thought-out strategy. He emphasizes that, in order to meet global requirements, it is necessary to provide lawyers with opportunities for systematic professional development. As a solution to this problem,

I. V. Kvach proposes the creation of a specialized center for continuing education or the organization of regular advanced training courses that would guarantee the updating of lawyers' knowledge at least every three years. An important component of international standards, pointed out by I. V. Kvach, is ensuring the independent and proactive position of lawyers and lawyers' organizations. This independence and proactivity presuppose the active participation of representatives of the legal profession in the process of legislative development. Thus, international standards serve as a guide for improving the national legislative framework and adapting it to international requirements. However, as the author notes, one of the main difficulties on the path to the full implementation of these standards remains the lack of clearly structured mechanisms for the continuous training and retraining of lawyers 4, pp. 5–6..

The current uncertainty surrounding the understanding and assessment of qualified legal assistance in Russian legislation requires amendments and additions. One significant proposal is to introduce clear standards for the quality of legal services provided by including a separate section, "Standards of Advocacy," in the Code of Professional Ethics for Advocates. This innovation will give the standards a normative character and make them mandatory, including for courts. This solution will facilitate the development of an effective system for monitoring the quality of services provided by lawyers and enhance public confidence in the legal profession. It is also recommended to establish institutions for continuing education and to conduct advanced training for lawyers at least once every three years, which will serve as an additional tool for maintaining the high level of competence of practicing lawyers.

The study found that Russian legislation urgently needs to introduce clear standards for the quality of legal services provided, as the concept of "qualified legal assistance" and the criteria for its evaluation remain unclear. The most effective solution appears to be the inclusion of a special section, "Standards of Advocacy," in the Code of Professional Ethics for Advocates, which would give the standards a normative character and make them binding on judges and judicial institutions. It is also recommended to develop institutional infrastructure, such as specialized educational institutions or regular professional development courses held at least once every three years, to maintain the required level of competence among practicing lawyers. These measures will contribute to improving the quality of legal services and strengthening public trust in the legal profession.

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VALUE-BASED DOUBLE FRAMING IN PERFORM-THERAPY AS A MECHANISM OF EMOTIONAL REGULATION

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Abstract. *Contemporary psychological practice increasingly encounters difficulties related to emotional disorganization, loss of internal coherence, and reduced capacity for purposeful action under conditions of uncertainty. Traditional cognitive and interpretative approaches often focus on re-evaluating meanings, while leaving the structural organization of emotional experience insufficiently addressed. This article proposes value-based double framing as a distinct psychological mechanism of emotional regulation within the framework of perform-therapy.*

Value-based double framing is conceptualized as a two-level regulatory process in which an external value frame structures emotional experience while an internal reorganization of feeling enables stability, tolerability, and readiness for action. Perform-therapy operationalizes this mechanism through four fundamental values — Truth, Beauty, Goodness, and Justice — each functioning as a specific regulatory form rather than an abstract moral ideal. The article presents a theoretical model of value-based double framing and illustrates its operation using empirical data obtained from adult participants who worked with a single emotional experience across sequential value frames.

The findings demonstrate that value-based framing produces systematic changes in the structure of emotional experience, including increased clarity, coherence, and perceived manageability. Importantly, the mechanism facilitates a transition from emotional passivity to agency, expressed as readiness to engage in concrete action. The results support the view that values can function as effective psychological regulators and that value-based double framing represents a viable mechanism of emotional regulation in perform-therapy. Implications for value-oriented psychotherapy and self-regulation practices are discussed.

Keywords: *value-based double framing; perform-therapy; emotional regulation; values; agency; self-regulation; psychological mechanism*

Introduction

In recent years, psychological practice has increasingly encountered conditions characterized by disorganization of emotional experience, loss of inner coherence, and a reduced capacity for goal-directed action. At an empirically operationalized level, these phenomena correspond closely to the construct of emotion dysregulation, which includes experiences of emotions as overwhelming, difficulties in integrating affective states, and impairments in maintaining goal-oriented behavior under emotional load (Gratz & Roemer, 2004). An additional vulnerability factor is uncertainty: contemporary models of anxiety and stress emphasize intolerance of uncertainty as a dispositional characteristic associated with heightened affective reactivity and behavioral inhibition in situations requiring choice and commitment (Carleton, 2012).

Although such phenomena have traditionally been addressed within cognitive or interpretative approaches, a substantial proportion of psychological interventions focus primarily on modifying meanings, beliefs, and appraisals. As a result, the structural organization of emotional experience — that is, the conditions under which experience becomes tolerable, coherent, and actionable — often remains insufficiently articulated (Gross, 2015; Webb, Miles, & Sheeran, 2012).

Contemporary models of emotion regulation highlight the central role of appraisal processes and cognitive control in shaping emotional responses (Scherer, Schorr, & Johnstone, 2001; Gross, 2015). Strategies derived from the process model of emotion regulation demonstrate measurable effects on emotional intensity, duration, and physiological correlates (Webb et al., 2012). However, meta-analytic evidence also indicates that maladaptive regulation patterns — such as rumination, experiential avoidance, or suppression — are transdiagnostically associated with psychopathology and may persist even when individuals achieve cognitive insight into their emotional states (Aldao, Nolen-Hoeksema, & Schweitzer, 2010). Consequently, a person may gain conceptual understanding of their experience while still failing to restore a sense of agency and readiness for concrete action.

Against this background, increasing attention has been directed toward value-oriented models of regulation, which conceptualize emotional experience not merely as a subjective reaction but as a phenomenon that can be psychologically organized through guiding principles of action. In value theory, values are defined as enduring guiding principles that structure priorities and support decision-making in situations involving competing motivations (Schwartz, 1992). Social-psychological research further conceptualizes values as mental representations that influence appraisal processes and behavioral choices rather than as abstract moral ideals alone (Maio, 2010). Within clinical psychology, this logic is explicitly developed in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy, where values are directly linked to committed action and psychological flexibility, facilitating movement from internal stagnation toward purposeful behavior (Hayes et al., 2006; Hayes, Strosahl, & Wilson, 2012).

The concept of double framing, originating in Raoul Eshelman's theory of performatism, offers a promising framework for conceptualizing the regulatory function of form. In performatist theory, double framing refers to a structural configuration in which an external frame constrains interpretation and closes the experiential field, while an internal frame reorganizes subjective experience, enabling the restoration of coherence and trust in lived reality (Eshelman, 2008). In later developments of performatist theory, Eshelman further emphasizes the role of form in overcoming postmodern indeterminacy by reinstating commitment and experiential closure through structured framing (Eshelman, 2024). Although originally formulated within cultural and philosophical discourse, this concept has clear psychological relevance, particularly for understanding regulation of emotional experience under conditions of uncertainty.

From a psychological perspective, double framing can be reconceptualized as a two-level regulatory mechanism, in which an external orienting structure stabilizes internal emotional processes and reduces the destabilizing effects of indeterminacy. This shift moves the analytical focus away from the content of experience toward the conditions that render emotional experience tolerable, coherent, and capable of guiding action. Such an approach is consistent with theories emphasizing the centrality of agency and self-efficacy in psychological functioning (Bandura, 1997), as well as with models of autonomous self-regulation as a foundation for sustained, self-determined behavior (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Perform-Therapy develops this line of reasoning by operationalizing the mechanism of double framing through a system of core values — Truth, Beauty, Goodness, and Justice. Within this framework, values function as distinct regulatory forms that organize emotional experience in different yet complementary ways. Rather than treating values as normative prescriptions, Perform-Therapy conceptualizes them as practical psychological orientations that influence perception, affective tone, and readiness for action. In this respect, the approach aligns with contemporary value-based models of behavioral change, in which values shape experiential organization and action selection (Hayes et al., 2012; Maio, 2010; Schwartz, 1992). Through systematic engagement with these value-based frames, emotional experience is not primarily reinterpreted but restructured, allowing inner coherence to emerge without reliance on extensive cognitive analysis.

The aim of the present article is to conceptualize value-based double framing as a specific psychological mechanism of emotion regulation within the context of Perform-Therapy. Three objectives are addressed: (1) to describe the structural characteristics of value-based double framing as a regulatory process; (2) to clarify the distinct regulatory functions of Truth, Beauty, Goodness, and Justice in the organization of emotional experience; and (3) to illustrate how this mechanism facilitates the transition from emotional passivity to agency. By focusing on

the mechanism itself rather than solely on empirical outcomes, the article seeks to deepen theoretical understanding of value-oriented regulation and to situate it within contemporary psychotherapeutic practice (Gross, 2015; Scherer et al., 2001; Bandura, 1997).

Theoretical Background

The concept of double framing originates in Raoul Eshelman's theory of performatism, where it describes a structural condition that restores coherence and trust in experience through the introduction of an external form (Eshelman, 2008; 2024). In contrast to postmodern models that emphasize endless interpretation and relativization of meaning, performatism proposes that form can temporarily constrain interpretation and thereby stabilize subjective experience. This stabilization does not eliminate ambiguity but renders it psychologically manageable.

When adapted to psychology, double framing can be understood as a regulatory configuration in which two levels of experience are held simultaneously: an external orienting frame and an internal emotional state. The external frame does not replace or suppress the emotional experience; rather, it provides a form within which the experience can reorganize itself. As a result, emotional experience becomes clearer, more coherent, and more tolerable, allowing the individual to remain engaged rather than overwhelmed.

This form-based perspective complements existing models of emotional regulation, which traditionally emphasize appraisal, cognitive control, and reinterpretation (Scherer, 2001; Gross, 2015). While these approaches explain how emotions change in intensity or valence, they pay less attention to the conditions under which emotional experience becomes structurally stable and capable of guiding action. Double framing addresses this gap by focusing on the *organization* of experience rather than on its content.

Values as Regulatory Forms

Within a psychological framework, values can be conceptualized not merely as moral preferences or abstract ideals, but as regulatory forms that structure perception, emotional tone, and behavioral orientation. Empirical research on values demonstrates their role in guiding evaluation and action across cultures (Schwartz, 1992). However, in many psychological models, values remain distal constructs, influencing motivation without directly shaping the structure of lived emotional experience.

In value-based double framing, values function as immediate organizing principles that constrain emotional experience in specific ways. Each value introduces a distinct mode of regulation: Truth emphasizes clarity and factual orientation; Beauty organizes experience through coherence and form; Goodness supports

emotional gentleness and self-related acceptance; Justice regulates proportionality and the perceived fairness of emotional responses. These functions align with findings from appraisal theory, self-compassion research, and normative models of emotion (Neff, 2003; Solomon, 1997).

Importantly, values in this model do not operate as evaluative judgments imposed on experience. Instead, they serve as frames that reshape how emotional experience is held and processed. By providing a stable orienting structure, values reduce uncertainty and prevent emotional diffusion, making experience more manageable without suppressing its complexity.

Perform-Therapy as a Value-Oriented Framework

Perform-therapy integrates the concept of double framing with a structured system of values to create a value-oriented model of emotional regulation. This approach was developed in response to issues of identity fragmentation and loss of coherence in the context of postmodern uncertainty. It focuses not on symptom reduction or interpretive insight but on the **restoration of coherence through form and action** (Grebenuik, 2025a; Grebenuik, 2025b; Grebenuik, 2025c). In Perform-therapy, values are viewed not as normative ideals but as practical psychological orientations that shape the unfolding of emotional experience in the present moment.

Through sequential engagement with the values of **Truth, Beauty, Goodness, and Justice**, Perform-therapy operationalizes value-based double framing as a dynamic regulatory process. This logic was conceptually developed in works on Perform-therapy and the Pi-method, where values are described as navigational forms that restore subjective coherence and direct action (Grebenuik, 2025a). Each value frame introduces a specific external orientation, while internal emotional experience reorganizes in response to this orientation. The interaction between the external value form and internal changes in emotional experience constitutes the core mechanism of value-based double framing.

By anchoring emotional experience in value-based forms, Perform-therapy facilitates the restoration of agency and the ability to act purposefully. As shown in the perform-therapeutic model for explaining neurotic disorders, restoring coherence and internal stability increases the willingness to accept treatment and actively engage in the therapeutic process (Grebenuik, 2025b). Thus, emotional experience becomes not only understandable but also **functionally actionable**, allowing the individual to move from passive endurance of emotions to conscious and proportionate behavioral choices. This distinguishes Perform-therapy from primarily cognitive or narrative approaches and positions value-based double framing as a distinct mechanism of emotional regulation.

Value-Based Double Framing as a Psychological Mechanism

Value-based double framing can be defined as a psychological mechanism of emotional regulation in which emotional experience is reorganized through the simultaneous presence of two interconnected levels: an external value frame and an internal experiential response. Unlike cognitive reframing, which operates through reinterpretation of meaning, value-based double framing operates through the *structuring conditions* of experience, shaping how emotions are held, tolerated, and transformed.

At the first level, a value frame functions as an external orienting form. This form does not evaluate emotional experience as correct or incorrect; instead, it establishes a stable reference point that limits ambiguity and provides direction. By introducing a value frame — such as Truth, Beauty, Goodness, or Justice — the individual is invited to relate to the emotional experience within a specific mode of orientation. This external frame constrains emotional diffusion without suppressing emotional content.

At the second level, internal emotional experience undergoes reorganization in response to the imposed value frame. This reorganization is not deliberate or analytical; rather, it emerges as a consequence of holding the experience within a structured form. Emotional intensity becomes more regulated, subjective clarity increases, and the experience is perceived as more coherent and manageable. Importantly, the emotional experience remains authentic and present, but no longer dominates consciousness in an overwhelming manner.

The mechanism of value-based double framing relies on the dynamic interaction between these two levels. The external value frame stabilizes attention and orientation, while internal emotional processes adjust to this stabilization. This interaction produces a third effect: the emergence of *readiness for action*. Emotional experience, once reorganized, becomes capable of guiding proportionate and intentional behavior rather than remaining a source of passive distress.

Each value frame contributes a distinct regulatory function to this mechanism. The value of Truth promotes cognitive and perceptual clarity, reducing uncertainty and fragmentation. Beauty organizes emotional experience through coherence and form, fostering a sense of internal harmony. Goodness supports emotional gentleness and self-related acceptance, lowering internal resistance and tension. Justice regulates proportionality, helping individuals perceive emotional intensity as appropriate and justified relative to the situation. Together, these values form a complementary system that enables flexible yet stable emotional regulation.

Within perform-therapy, value-based double framing is not treated as a one-time intervention but as a repeatable regulatory process. Through sequential engagement with multiple value frames, emotional experience is progressively reorganized, allowing individuals to approach complex or distressing emotions

without avoidance or excessive analysis. The mechanism thus supports sustained emotional regulation while preserving experiential depth.

In contrast to approaches that emphasize symptom reduction or cognitive control, value-based double framing facilitates emotional regulation by restoring structural coherence and agency. Emotional experience becomes a source of orientation rather than disruption, enabling individuals to act with greater clarity, proportionality, and intentionality. This positions value-based double framing as a distinct and theoretically grounded mechanism within contemporary value-oriented psychotherapy.

Results

The empirical illustration was based on data obtained from 70 adult participants (49 women, 21 men) aged 18 to 62 years ($M = 31.4$). Throughout the procedure, each participant worked with one self-selected current emotional experience, which remained constant across all stages of the protocol.

Four structural parameters of emotional experience were assessed repeatedly across value frames:

- (1) clarity,
- (2) coherence,
- (3) perceived emotional gentleness,
- (4) sense of manageability (“this feeling is within my capacity”).

Across all value frames, mean scores on all four parameters increased relative to baseline. After engagement with at least one value frame, more than 90% of participants reported improvement in at least two structural parameters. Following completion of all four value frames, 97.1% of participants (68 out of 70) demonstrated a global positive shift in the perceived structure of their emotional experience.

Importantly, these changes were observed independently of the specific emotional content selected by participants, suggesting a structural rather than content-specific regulatory effect.

Table 1
Proportion of Participants Showing Improvement in Structural Parameters

Outcome Indicator	Participants (%)
Improvement in two or more parameters (after at least one value frame)	>90
Global positive structural shift (after all four value frames)	97.1
No observed positive structural shift	2.9

Note. Structural parameters included clarity, coherence, emotional gentleness, and perceived manageability.

Internal Consistency of Value Frames

To examine whether each value frame functioned as a coherent regulatory unit, internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha.

Table 2
Internal Consistency of Value-Based Frames

Value Frame	Cronbach’s α
Truth	0.75
Beauty	0.81
Goodness	0.72
Justice	0.76

Note. All coefficients exceeded the acceptable threshold of $\alpha \geq .70$.

Differentiated Regulatory Effects of Values

Participants were asked to indicate which value frame had the strongest stabilizing effect on their emotional experience.

Table 3
Distribution of Primary Regulatory Effects Across Value Frames

Value Frame	Participants (%)
Goodness	21
Justice	20
Beauty	14
Truth	10
Combined influence of two values	22
Equal influence of all values	13

Note. Percentages reflect participants’ subjective identification of the most stabilizing value frame.

The distribution indicates that participants were able to differentiate between the regulatory functions of the four values, supporting the conceptual assumption that each value frame contributes a distinct mode of emotional regulation.

Readiness for Action as an Indicator of Agency

Readiness for action was used as a key quantitative indicator of agency following value-based double framing. After completion of all four value frames, 98.6%

of participants (69 out of 70) reported readiness to take a concrete action related to their emotional experience. Only one participant (1.4%) reported no intention to act.

Table 4
Types of Intended Actions Reported After Completion of Value Frames

Type of Intended Action	Participants (%)
Small, manageable behavioral steps	34
Change of perspective	26
Interpersonal communication	11
Other meaningful actions	28

Note. Participants could report one primary intended action.

These data indicate a pronounced shift from emotional passivity toward action readiness, suggesting that value-based double framing is associated with the emergence of agency-oriented responses.

Interpretation

The quantitative indicators are consistent with the proposed mechanism of value-based double framing. The introduction of an external value frame was associated with consistent improvements in the structural organization of emotional experience and a high prevalence of reported readiness for action. Importantly, these changes were observed without explicit cognitive problem-solving or directive intervention, suggesting that emotional regulation may emerge through structural reorganization of experience rather than through interpretative effort alone.

Discussion

The present article sought to conceptualize value-based double framing as a psychological mechanism of emotional regulation within perform-therapy and to illustrate its operation using empirical indicators. The findings suggest that emotional regulation can occur not only through cognitive reinterpretation, but also through structural reorganization of emotional experience mediated by value-based forms.

Quantitative data indicate that engagement with value frames was associated with consistent improvements in the structural characteristics of emotional experience. Following completion of the full sequence of value frames, 97.1% of participants reported a global positive shift in clarity, coherence, and perceived manageability of their emotional state. This pattern supports the assumption that value-based framing operates at a structural level, shaping how emotional experience is held rather than modifying its semantic content.

Internal consistency coefficients for all four value frames exceeded the accepted threshold ($\alpha \geq 0.70$), indicating that Truth, Beauty, Goodness, and Justice function as coherent regulatory units rather than as diffuse or overlapping constructs. The differentiated subjective impact of the values further supports this conclusion. Participants most frequently identified Goodness (21%) and Justice (20%) as having the strongest stabilizing effect, whereas Truth (10%) and Beauty (14%) were more often associated with clarity and coherence. This distribution suggests that the values contribute distinct regulatory functions within the overall mechanism.

A particularly important observation concerns the transition from emotional experience to action. After completion of the procedure, 98.6% of participants reported readiness to take a concrete step in relation to their emotional experience. This finding indicates a restoration of agency, understood as the capacity to act deliberately rather than remain in a state of emotional passivity. Notably, readiness for action emerged without explicit problem-solving or prescriptive guidance, supporting the proposition that agency may arise from structural coherence rather than from cognitive control alone.

From a theoretical perspective, these findings align with performatist assumptions regarding the regulatory role of form. Value-based double framing introduces an external orienting structure that limits ambiguity and stabilizes attention, while internal emotional processes reorganize in response to this structure. The interaction of these two levels appears to generate emotional manageability and readiness for action, positioning value-based double framing as a distinct mechanism of emotional regulation.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The study relied on self-report measures and a single-session procedure, which limits conclusions regarding the long-term stability of the observed effects. The sample size, while sufficient for illustrative purposes, does not permit fine-grained statistical modeling or subgroup analysis. Future research may address these limitations through longitudinal designs, inclusion of external behavioral indicators, and comparative studies with alternative regulatory approaches.

Conclusion

This article has proposed value-based double framing as a specific psychological mechanism of emotional regulation within perform-therapy. The mechanism is defined by the interaction between an external value frame and internal emotional reorganization, which is associated with increased clarity, coherence, and perceived manageability of emotional experience.

Empirical indicators suggest that engagement with the values of Truth, Beauty, Goodness, and Justice is associated with systematic structural changes in emotional experience and supports a transition from emotional passivity toward agency.

The high prevalence of reported readiness for action observed among participants underscores the practical relevance of the proposed mechanism and distinguishes value-based double framing from approaches that focus primarily on interpretation or symptom reduction.

The findings further indicate that values may function as immediate psychological regulators, rather than solely as abstract or motivational ideals. By shaping the structural conditions under which emotions are experienced, value-based double framing appears to enable emotional regulation that preserves experiential depth while facilitating the restoration of agency. In this respect, the present work contributes to the theoretical development of perform-therapy and supports its application within value-oriented psychotherapeutic and self-regulation frameworks.

Further research is required to examine the durability of the observed effects, refine measurement strategies, and explore the applicability of value-based double framing across clinical, educational, and self-development contexts.

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PERSONALITY CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENTS WHO HAVE EXPERIENCED TRAUMATIC EXPERIENCES AND WAYS OF COUNSELING THEM

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Abstract. *The article examines the role of traumatization in the formation of negative personality traits in adolescents. The aim of the study was achieved, which consisted in identifying the relationship between the level of traumatization and the development of mental disorders, including obsessive-compulsive disorder, anxiety, and perfectionism. The study involved 50 adolescents aged 15 to 19 years. The following methods were used: the Yale–Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS), the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ-SF), the Spielberger–Khanin State–Trait Anxiety Inventory, and the Frost Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale. Correlation analysis using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was applied.*

Keywords: *traumatization, adolescents, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), anxiety, perfectionism, childhood trauma, correlation analysis, mediation analysis, trauma-focused psychotherapy.*

Mental traumatization experienced during childhood and adolescence remains one of the central problems of contemporary psychology. A child's life, from birth and throughout development, includes exposure to potentially traumatic events. Children encounter a wide range of such experiences, from various forms of abuse (physical, sexual, emotional) and neglect to severe losses, disruption of family ties, bullying, witnessing violence, and participation in extreme situations. These traumas, both overt and covert, have a proven pathogenic impact on personality formation and mental development, manifesting not only in acute reactions but also in delayed, often destructive consequences. Despite their critical significance, the issue of childhood psychological trauma remains insufficiently theorized and empirically substantiated.

Aim and hypothesis of the study.

The aim of the study was to identify the relationships between psychological traumatization and the severity of negative personality traits in adolescents, such as obsessive-compulsive disorder, anxiety, and perfectionism. The hypothesis was that the higher the degree of childhood traumatization, the higher the levels of OCD, anxiety, and perfectionism in adolescents.

Methodology.

The study involved 50 adolescents aged 15 to 19 years with mental disorders (psychiatrist-confirmed diagnoses) and varying levels of traumatization.

Psychodiagnostic instruments: the Yale–Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS); the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ-SF); the Spielberger–Khanin State–Trait Anxiety Inventory; the Frost Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale.

Data analysis methods: Spearman’s rank correlation analysis and the Mann–Whitney U test.

Results of the study.

Adolescents were divided into three groups according to the severity of traumatization. Analysis of mean values showed that the overall level of trauma in the group with severe traumatization (6.35%) only slightly exceeded that of the group with moderate traumatization (6.25%). Transition to extreme traumatization was accompanied by a sharp and substantial increase in all indicators of traumatic experience. The overall level of trauma almost doubled compared to the previous groups (12.22%).

Within the group with extreme traumatization, emotional forms of trauma predominated. Emotional neglect (19.63%) showed the highest value among all types of trauma across all groups, while emotional abuse (14.96%) was also highly pronounced. Physical abuse (8.26%), physical neglect (8.26%), and sexual abuse (8.52%) also increased markedly compared to the other groups but remained less pronounced than emotional forms of trauma within this group.

Correlation analysis across all groups revealed a strong relationship between physical abuse and elevated levels of OCD, anxiety, and perfectionism. However, in the third group an unexpected negative correlation between physical abuse and trait anxiety was identified. The negative correlation ($r = -0.504$; $p < 0.01$) between physical abuse and trait anxiety is counterintuitive, as traumatic experiences — especially physical abuse — are typically associated with increased anxiety and other forms of distress. Nevertheless, in certain contexts and through specific psychological mechanisms, such an inverse relationship may be explained. Possible explanations include dissociation and emotional numbing, adaptation to chronic stress, or identification with the aggressor (Stockholm syndrome). These findings require more thorough analysis and further in-depth qualitative and quantitative research.

Discussion of the Results.

According to the approaches of Gestalt therapy developed by F. Perls, L. Perls, and P. Goodman, psychological difficulties are viewed as a result of disturbances in the contact process between the organism and the environment, as well as consequences of unfinished gestalts — unprocessed and non-integrated experiences from past life events. In the context of early psychological traumatization, unfinished gestalts are often formed in situations of emotional neglect, abuse, loss, or chronic stress, which is particularly characteristic of childhood and adolescence.

Cognitive-behavioral therapy, developed by A. Beck and his followers, is based on the assumption that emotional and behavioral problems are maintained by dysfunctional cognitive schemas and irrational beliefs. Within this approach, individual psychological counseling is aimed at identifying, analyzing, and correcting distorted patterns of thinking that underlie anxiety, obsessive-compulsive symptoms, and perfectionism. Traumatization in this context acts as an intermediary link between cognitive imbalance and emotional destabilization. The results of the study demonstrated significant relationships: the higher the level of traumatization, the higher the levels of obsessive-compulsive disorder, anxiety, and perfectionism. These findings make it possible to increase the effectiveness of psychotherapy focused on processing traumatic experiences as a key area of counseling practice.

Practical Significance.

The results of this study have substantial practical relevance for counseling and psychotherapeutic work with adolescents who have experienced early traumatization. The obtained data confirm that a deeper understanding of the role of trauma in the formation of adolescents' mental states provides an effective foundation for targeted psychological counseling. Such counseling can be oriented toward reducing the severity of specific symptoms, including obsessive-compulsive disorder, perfectionism, and anxiety.

Conclusions.

1. This study confirms the profound destructive impact of childhood traumatization on adolescents' mental health, revealing direct and significant relationships between various types of traumatic experiences and the severity of obsessive-compulsive symptoms, as well as levels of anxiety and perfectionism.

2. It was established that physical abuse is the strongest positive predictor of all the negative personality traits examined. At the same time, the differentiated contribution of various types of trauma was confirmed: sexual abuse and physical neglect are closely associated with state anxiety, whereas sexual and emotional abuse demonstrate weak or negative associations with perfectionism, indicating the involvement of alternative adaptive mechanisms.

3. *Of particular importance is the identification of a threshold effect of extreme traumatization: a statistically significant increase in obsessive-compulsive symptomatology, anxiety, and perfectionism is observed only when transitioning to an extreme level of traumatic experience, rather than between moderate and severe levels.*

4. *The results provide a resource for increasing the effectiveness of individual psychological counseling aimed at reducing obsessive-compulsive symptoms, perfectionism, and anxiety in adolescents with high levels of traumatization.*

These findings substantiate the need for timely assessment of traumatic history and the development of differentiated psychocorrection programs that take into account the type and severity of experienced trauma. Further investigation of mediating mechanisms will contribute to a deeper understanding of the identified relationships.

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**THE LEGACY OF THE CLASSICS OF FOREIGN PEDAGOGY
AS A BASIS FOR MODELING THE CONTENT OF SOCIO-
INFORMATIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL
EDUCATION TEACHERS**

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***Annotation.** The article highlights the problem of the formation socio-informational competence among the future preschool education teachers. Based on the analysis of the classical pedagogical legacy of foreign scientists, a number of aspects have been identified that can be used in the process of modeling the content of socio-informational competence of the future preschool education teachers and in further practical activities for its formation.*

***Keywords:** socio-informational competence, legacy of classics of foreign pedagogy, future preschool education teachers.*

In the context of the digitalization of society, there is an increasing need for teachers who are able to respond promptly to innovations in the educational field: integrate information technologies into the educational process and skillfully use their tools in creating interesting activities, obtaining and processing information for professional and personal growth, communicating with colleagues, parents and children, working with documentation, and organizing and conducting scientific research activities, etc. Along with the ability to use the latest technologies in professional activities, it is important for a teacher to possess communication skills, since the personality of a teacher who is able to have a positive impact on a pupil through the words and example has been and remains a priority factor in a child's development. It is through personal communication that the child's emotional and sensory sphere is enriched, and the teacher instills in the pupil those unique human qualities that cannot be transmitted remotely, first of all, love and a valuable attitude towards the world. In this regard, the problem of the formation of

socio-informational competence among the future preschool education teachers is an important task of the theory and practice of pedagogical science, and its solution is a condition for improving the quality of professional training and successful adaptation of graduates to the challenges of the digital age.

Based on a number of works (Yu. I. Askerko, O. V. Baranova, N. N. Bedenko, M. V. Goryachova, O. N. Griban, D. V. Gulyakin, A. G. Zhuyeva, I. A. Zimnaya, V. O. Zinchenko, E. V. Koblyanskaya, S. N. Krasnokutskaya, G. I. Marasnov, A. K. Markova, G. P. Mosyagina, N. A. Rototaeva, A. V. Spirin, F. K. Tubeeva, E. V. Falameeva, T. A. Chekalina, I. V. Chernousov, etc.) in the direction of our research, an analysis was made of such concepts as «social competence», «information competence», «socio-information competence» and the author's definitions of these definitions are formulated:

— social competence is a component of the professional competence of the future specialist and is an integrated dynamic education that includes a system of social knowledge, skills, personal qualities and ways of working that ensure his ability to successfully interact in society, taking into account the positions and interests of other people and effectively carry out professional activities;

— information competence is a component of the professional competence of a future specialist and is an integrated education that includes knowledge, skills, and willingness to effectively use information technology to search, process, analyze, and apply information in various areas of life, including professional activities and self-education;

— socio-informational competence of future specialists is an integrated personal and professional quality, including the ability effectively receive, analyze, use and manage information in various social and professional settings based on the legal and moral norms of modern society.

To clarify the definition of “socio-informational competence” in relation to the future preschool education teacher and modeling its content, let us turn to the classical pedagogical legacy, in particular, the purpose of our work is to analyze the ideas of classics of foreign pedagogy and their use in solving the identified problem. An analysis of the works of foreign classical teachers has shown that we do not find such concepts as social and information competences in them (they did not exist at that time), however, they focus on the social role of the teacher, which consists not only in the transfer of knowledge, but also in the formation of a comprehensively developed, moral personality; on the features of professional teacher training and conditions of effective pedagogical activity. For example, Ya. A. Komensky emphasized that in order to fulfill a social role, the teacher himself must be a model of moral behavior and teach this to his students. In his work «The Great Didactics», the scientist wrote: «If teachers are friendly and affectionate, they will not alienate children with their harsh treatment, but will attract them with

their fatherly disposition, manners and words; if teachers recommend the sciences they embark on, from the side of superiority, attractiveness and ease.; ... in short, if teachers treat students with love, then they will easily win their hearts so that it will be more pleasant for children to stay at school than at home» 3, p. 342..

In the work «Pampedia», the scientist notes that the development of human abilities consists of three parts: A mind, a hand, and a language that «develops in order to our communication with people would be reasonable, exciting, and enjoyable», which, as our research has shown, is one of the characteristics of social competence 4, p. 447.. According to Ya. A. Komensky, the teacher is called upon to prepare pupils for life in society: to develop a love of peace, justice and mutual understanding; to form the ability to be active and be a useful person in society based on the development of communication skills, cooperation, and responsibility. The scientist believed that education can contribute to the establishment of harmony and peace in the world.

Ya. A. Komensky wrote that the child's nature is always in motion, i.e. it requires intellectual and spiritual nourishment for development, and for this, the educator should acquire the ability to remove the false from the child's mind, the evil from the will, and the vain from actions, and ensure that he is always «presented with the truly true, truly good, and truly useful» 4, p. 426.. A teacher should be constantly searching for what to teach, how to teach, «so that the drink of science is swallowed without beatings, without screams, without violence, without disgust, in a word, friendly and pleasant» 4, p. 118.. Actually, Ya. A. Komensky wrote about the teacher's qualities that make up information competency.

In the legacy of J.-J. Rousseau also laid the scientific foundations for the formation of a teacher's social and information competency. Thus, the analysis of the pedagogical treatise «Emil, or On education» allows us to identify the following aspects concerning the problem under study.

1. It is important for a teacher to study and understand the natural nature of a child, to know his needs and inclinations, to be able to follow this nature in the process of education; to understand the peculiarities of the social environment in which a child is raised, which requires the teacher to be able to analyze social factors, understand their impact on the pupil and take them into account in the educational process; to have critical thinking and the ability to analyze information, teach a child to distinguish truth from lies, evaluate different points of view and draw their own conclusions.; to protect children from the negative influence of information (characteristics of socio-informational competency).

2. It is important for a teacher to be able to exercise self-awareness and self-reflection in order to understand their strengths and weaknesses; continuously work on themselves, improve knowledge and skills; establish empathic and trusting relationships with a child, be sensitive to his feelings, understand his experiences, be

able to see the world through his eyes in order to effectively guide development; be able to communicate effectively with the child, his family and society, which implies the ability to listen and hear, ask the right questions, and express their thoughts clearly and clearly; be able to convey information to the child in an accessible and understandable form, taking into account his age and individual characteristics (characteristics of social competency).

In the address of J.-J. Rousseau also provides valuable advice to teachers on developing their social competency.: «always speak correctly in the presence of them (children); try to make it so pleasant for them to stay with no one as it is with you, and be sure that their language will imperceptibly clear under your influence, even if you never reproach them for mistakes» 6.. With regard to such characteristics of social competence as the ability to anticipate and predict the results of one's behavior, J.-J. We find this thought in Rousseau: «If you teach him (the child) to anticipate the result of all his movements and correct mistakes through experience, isn't it clear that the more he acts, the more reasonable he will become» 6..

The pedagogical legacy of I. G. Pestalozzi also contains ideas and recommendations that are directly related to the problem of the formation of social and informational competence among future teachers. In the developed theory of elementary education (the work «A memo to Parisian friends about the essence and purpose of the method»), the scientist identifies three parts: intellectual (the formation of intellectual independence and certain intellectual skills); physical (the development of physical skills that give a person peace of mind); moral (the formation of moral skills that ensure the independence of judgments) education. Moreover, I. G. Pestalozzi notes that moral education should be ahead of intellectual development, paving the right path for it. Thus, in the process of implementing elementary education, children actually develop the qualities and characteristics that make up social and informational competence. The scientist concludes: «The greatness of the idea of elementary education consists in the harmonious development of all forces, but so that their use is necessarily subordinated to the needs arising from the position of this individual in society» 2, p. 339..

I. G. Pestalozzi emphasizes that in order to implement elementary education, there must be appropriately trained teachers who possess the qualities that they seek to form in children. Thus, in his work «Memorial note on the seminary in the canton of Vaud» the scientist describes the peculiarities of the relationship between teachers and children in order to achieve the best results in elementary education, in the development of such qualities as love, benevolence, camaraderie, grateful and trusting affection, inquisitiveness, that is, those qualities, thanks to which a developing personality will be able to successfully integrate into society. For example, I. G. Pestalozzi suggests developing the spirit of collectivism by involving teachers in children's games. Thus, educators, maintaining the atmosphere of fun, joy and

carefree, characteristic of children, and eliminating negative emotions, will more effectively perform professional functions, primarily social ones: identify and prevent bad behavior, eliminate temptations and examples of bad, banish evil from children's consciousness.

The form of work of the teaching staff based on the legacy of I. G. Pestalozzi is interesting for our research: an open discussion of their observations of children, on the basis of which individual strategies for each child are developed and their coordinated implementation is ensured. This form of work in the teaching staff serves as a condition for creating a moral atmosphere in an educational institution, in which moral teachers, by their example and using verbal methods and exercises, strive to form the morality of pupils. I. G. Pestalozzi concludes: «According to the laws of nature, a person is not truly moral when he utters virtuous words. According to the laws of nature, he utters these words because the power of morality compels his mouth to pronounce them» 2, p. 352.. A. Diesterweg paid considerable attention to the training of teaching staff in his works, in particular, to substantiate the importance of the formation of qualities and characteristics, which, in our opinion, can be attributed to the content of socio-informational competence. In the article «On the teacher's self-awareness», the scientist writes about the peculiar features of the teacher: «His official activity and profession give him a certain imprint, develop in him a special worldview and a special attitude towards people, make him a peculiar personality» 1, p. 311.. A. Diesterweg emphasizes that because a teacher is a special person, society has the right to demand from him a certain lifestyle and self-awareness. The scientist gives the following characteristic of the teacher's consciousness:

- the teacher's high opinion of the dignity and role of his profession, and the development of the human spirit (education) is the most sublime thing.;
- recognition of the value of each person, respect for people;
- the correct attitude of the teacher towards the students and their parents. Parenting does not consist in commanding children, but in serving them; in leadership based on love for their own good. Building friendly relationships with parents;
- the desire of the teacher to communicate with colleagues, to solidarity, cohesion based on common values and interests, so that, as A. Diesterweg writes, the spirit does not starve, the soul does not wither, and the teaching gift does not die out;
- the teacher's need to replenish knowledge and participate in the development of general knowledge and special sciences;
- the teacher's need to take part in the events of his time, which is associated with preparing for the life of the younger generation in modern conditions and, accordingly, promoting his upbringing in accordance with the best manifestations of the spirit of his time;
- awareness of the teacher as a member of his nation, educator of the national youth.

A. Disterweg gives a number of recommendations to teachers, which, from our point of view, will be useful in the process of forming social and informational competence among the future preschool education teachers:

- to develop independent thinking;
- live according to your conscience and keep your peace of mind;
- to develop character based on moral principles, to help strengthen the character of pupils, to develop their desire to comprehend the truth and to do good;
- take part in spiritual and moral activities;
- strive to educate the mind and heart of the child;
- by word and example, to promote the spiritual unity of people;
- continuously self-educate 1, p. 311..

Of interest to our research is M. Montessori's pedagogical system, which she built on the basis of many years of experience working with children, identifying their developmental needs, and, accordingly, creating appropriate pedagogical conditions for this, the implementation of which is largely determined by the training of educators, i.e. the availability of knowledge, skills, personal qualities, which, like our research has shown that they constitute a socio-informational competence. So, the teacher of M. Montessori should have an imagination by which he can draw a child the way he should become — a moral person and create favorable conditions for his spiritual ascent.

A teacher should be prepared for the three main stages of working with children. The first stage is to create an environment in which the teacher will become a guardian and guardian for the children. To gain the trust of children, the teacher must be attractive, pleasant-looking, neat, clean, calm and full of dignity. Thus, caring for the educator's own personality should be an integral part of the environment in which the child lives; the teacher himself is an essential part of his world.

The next step is to get the guys interested. The educator plays a key role in the child's life, he is like a bright fire, giving warmth and energy, attracting to himself. He can enliven a group of children with a story, infect them with a song, captivate them with a game... the teacher's passion certainly increases the chances of success.

The third stage, for which the teacher must be prepared, is the ability to wait patiently until the children can find the strength to focus on performing any exercises. Be careful in words and actions so that, as M. Montessori emphasizes, you do not interrupt the interest, because it corresponds to the laws of nature and reveals the entire cycle of new activity.

Thus, the development of a child according to M. Montessori is a consistent passage of the stages of independence. Having knowledge of these stages, and the teacher's understanding of the specifics of their course, should determine his behavior. It is an act of spiritual service that reaches perfection in dealing with children. Working with children, the educator learns the secret of childhood, because

he applies this knowledge every day. This gives not only a deep understanding of the world of childhood, but also a special, all-encompassing love directed not at a specific person, but at the innermost secret that lives in every child. This is how the educator becomes a true friend for the child 5.

So, an analysis of the legacy of foreign classical teachers has shown that: a teacher who strives to develop the spirit of a child performs the role of an educator, caregiver, mentor, role model, guide of moral values, a companion who brings up harmonious, moral and educated individuals capable of serving society. The prerequisite for the qualitative fulfillment of these roles is the teacher's ability to study the nature of the child, to understand him, to know the peculiarities of the social environment in which his development takes place; to be able to build relationships with colleagues, pupils and their parents; have critical thinking, constantly replenish knowledge, improve and anticipate the results of their actions.

Thus, the analysis of classical foreign teaching gave us the opportunity to clarify the concept of «socio-informational competence of a future preschool education teacher», which we define as a component of professional competency and represents an integrated dynamic education, including a system of socio-pedagogical and socio-psychological knowledge, personal qualities, skills and abilities of mobile information acquisition, its analysis., effective use and management in social and professional conditions based on the legal and moral norms of modern society, ensuring high-quality service in teaching.

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THE PEDAGOGICAL POTENTIAL OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN FAMILY EDUCATION

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Annotation. *The article reveals the pedagogical potential of digital transformation in family education, the preservation of family values and progressive traditions in the context of the rapid development and introduction of digital resources and tools that open up new opportunities for parents to learn, educate and develop. The authors substantiate the need for continuous education of parents in the field of digital technologies for a more effective solution of both current and strategic tasks of family education, because the success of integrating traditional methods and approaches in family education with the capabilities of digital resources largely depends on this.*

Keywords: *digital transformation, family education, pedagogical tools, digital resources.*

The relevance of the problem under study is determined by the fact that digital technologies have affected virtually all spheres of human activity, including family education. They open up new opportunities for parents to educate, raise, and develop their children. Current trends in the digital world demonstrate the importance of continuous learning and self-education of parents in the field of information and communication technologies for more effectively addressing both current and strategic family education challenges. “The digital transformation of society requires a rethinking of approaches to the upbringing and education of preschool children and stimulates the development of new methods and models for working with children within the framework of basic and additional educational programs” 1, pp. 41–49.. Therefore, digital competence in the modern information society is no longer simply a useful skill; it is becoming one of the key factors in successful

family education. It is not so much about the ability to use computer technology, but rather about the semantic content and content of digital resources, awareness of the risks associated with social networks, and the ability to analyze information obtained from various sites.

Today, there are numerous training programs and resources available to help parents acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. Furthermore, comparative analysis, systematization, generalization, and exchange of experience with other parents, teachers, and digital technology specialists play an important role, as joint discussions enable the most effective solutions to be found and parenting strategies to be developed that meet the realities of a rapidly evolving world. digital environment. However, parents' task is not to shield children from the digital world, but to teach them to use it safely and effectively, as the accumulation, production, processing, storage, use, and transmission of information is becoming the predominant activity in almost all areas. To effectively utilize digital tools in family education, parents must constantly seek new, effective approaches to teaching and stay abreast of current trends in innovative technologies.

Focusing on the educational potential of digital technologies, G. V. Soldatova also points to the development of children's intellect and psyche under the influence of digital resources in her research. In her concept of "Digital Childhood," the researcher attributes an important role to two aspects: by expanding the surrounding world, permeating the entire space of a child's active activity, digital technologies can lead to overstraining of the nervous system; modern children are growing up in a new social situation, where information and communication technologies, especially the Internet, play a decisive role. The author emphasizes that the Internet is not just a set of technologies, but a significant element in the structure of modern childhood. The living environment plays a significant role in the process of socialization 14..

The issues related to how to use the pedagogical potential of digital transformation in family education (E. I. Andrianova, A. N. Bogachev, I. V. Muskhanova, U. S. Sadykov, E. V. Sokolova, M. Y. Stozharova, I. N. Timoshina) 1; 11; 13. and how to determine the boundaries between traditional approaches and digital technologies (I. A. Fedoseeva, E. N. Papusha, A. S. Razorvina, M. M. Shubovich) are currently widely discussed in the research of educators and psychologists 15; 16.. As the analysis of the listed studies showed, scientists emphasize the need to identify the pedagogical potential of digital transformation in family education. Other authors in their studies reflect issues related to innovative solutions to the problems of the modern family under the influence of computer technologies on the mental state and development of children (L. M. Zakharova, E. P. Kvashnina, A. V. Petrova) 4; 6; 10.; there are studies that present the dynamics of family values in Russian culture (M. V. Vdovina, A. A. Voinova, I. A. Lykova, A. A. Mayer, V. V. Rumyantsev) 3; 7., etc.

Despite differing opinions regarding internet resources, the authors of the article believe that the negative impact of digital technologies and tools on family education is exaggerated. They see a solution in creating and maintaining a media culture in the family, as well as educating all family members on the purposeful use of the real world of digital technologies. It is important to note that digital resources and tools are inherently neutral: their impact depends on how users manage them. To balance the benefits and potential risks of technology in family life, parents need to master the basics of digital literacy.

It is important to find a balance between using digital resources and maintaining lively, emotional communication with children (S. K. Bondyreva, N. N. Bushmarina, H. Paizyev) 2; 9., to be interested in the social networks they visit, online educational platforms, and to share your experiences and knowledge in the field of digital technologies. It is also necessary to develop family rules for the use of digital technologies with children, taking into account the age and needs of the child. Watching movies online together, participating in educational computer games, creating family photo albums in cloud services, and using the universal digital tool OurHome turn household chores into a game, making tasks interesting for children and achievable for adults in accordance with the family's preferences.

The uniqueness of today's digital society is that digital literacy, as one of the main priorities of the educational process, allows each family to develop its own rules for raising children, including time limits, permitted types of content, and privacy settings. Furthermore, digital transformation offers many opportunities to strengthen family relationships, connections. The role of parents in the context of digital transformation is to be not just controllers, but also guides into the world of digital technologies. In turn, digital technologies perform informational, educational, and socio-cultural functions, convey public opinion, and construct various family models. These models, declared on the internet, are subsequently imprinted in the minds of the younger generation, resulting in young people following these models when creating their own families.

Understanding basic cybersecurity principles allows parents to protect themselves and their children from scammers, cyberbullying, and inappropriate content. Knowledge and skills in using online educational platforms provide access to a wealth of resources for both self-improvement and child development, allowing for tailored learning to their individual needs and interests. Understanding the underlying concepts behind social media helps parents stay informed about their children's online activities, recognize signs of trouble, and provide support.

This isn't simply the acquisition of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, but rather the mastery of a new type of parental digital literacy, enabling effective navigation in a complex and rapidly changing digital space. Parents who recognize this need will actively seek out learning opportunities: attend specialized courses,

explore digital tools, share experiences with other parents, and so on. Parents who lack knowledge and skills in digital technology are unable to become agents of «digital socialization» for their children, as children are already familiar with various gadgets from a very early age and readily access various unverified social networks.

Today's reality is that the internet, social media, and mobile devices are all becoming an integral part of the everyday life of children and adolescents. However, as V. E. Morozova notes in her research, the mass dissemination of large volumes of information has given rise to so-called fake news, which have become increasingly relevant today 8.. It is impossible not to notice how ubiquitous digitalization is transforming our thinking. We are increasingly leaning toward a technocratic approach, where tools and technologies begin to prevail over ultimate goals, and technical aspects over human ones. In this context, the education of the younger generation raises serious concerns. Children and adolescents, deeply immersed in virtual space and entangled in the web of the internet (I. V. Enicheva, Y. E. Ziyatdinova, N. V. Sergeeva, A. I. Yakimchik), may face certain moral challenges in shaping their worldview 2; 5..

Thus, digital transformation can become a powerful tool in family education. Online courses, educational platforms, interactive games, and other digital resources offer children and parents broad opportunities for acquiring knowledge and developing skills. At the same time, it is important to remember the need to maintain a healthy balance: excessive use of gadgets can negatively influence health, reduce social activity, and negatively affect academic performance. The success of family education in the context of digital transformation largely depends on parents' thoughtful approach to this issue, their willingness to embrace new technologies, and their use in educational activities. It's important to remember that technologies are merely tools that can be both beneficial and harmful. The main task of parents is to help children use these tools wisely, to turn the digital space into an ideal means of knowledge and personal development, and not into a source of unnecessary and dangerous hobbies.

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INTEGRATING INNOVATIVE METHODOLOGIES IN LAND MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the effectiveness of modern educational technologies in training first- and second-year students majoring in Land Management and Cadastres, specializing in Land Management Expertise. It examines the integration of interactive teaching methods, such as lectures with gamification elements, museum pedagogy, inter-course exchange of teaching and learning materials, and business games. The didactic potential of each of these technologies is described, implementation scenarios for them, and performance evaluation criteria are presented. Positive effects and emerging barriers are analyzed, and recommendations for optimizing the educational process are offered.*

Key words: *interactive teaching methods, land management, applied geology, land surveying, case methods, business games, museum pedagogy, inter-course exchange of educational materials, peer-to-peer education.*

Introduction

Training competent land management specialists requires not only a thorough mastery of theoretical knowledge but also the ability to effectively apply it in practice. Employers increasingly expect graduates who can quickly adapt to real-world production conditions, work in a team, and independently find optimal solutions to problems. Today's reality places increased demands on education, emphasizing active and interactive methods that engage students in an active creative process and develop a professional approach to problem solving.

All of this underscores the particular importance of developing effective educational technologies that can ensure a deep integration of theory and practice and prepare graduates for full professional participation. Therefore, the implementation of innovative methods that actively engage students in the learning process

and ensure the effective acquisition of essential skills and competencies is becoming increasingly important. The main objective of this article is to develop and validate a set of educational technologies that will improve the quality of training for students majoring in land management by increasing student engagement and integrating modern approaches to learning.

The aim of the study is to demonstrate the effectiveness of using a set of teaching technologies in the process of teaching geological and land management disciplines and to develop models for their optimal use in the modern educational process.

The relevance of this study stems from the need to improve the quality of training for land management specialists, meet modern labor market requirements, and develop an innovative approach to organizing the educational process. Current realities require the modernization of educational technologies, focusing on students' active participation in creative solution searches, developing independent decision-making skills, and developing teamwork skills.

The research's novelty lies in the development of a comprehensive approach to the use of interactive educational technologies, including elements of gamification, museum pedagogy, cross-course exchange of teaching and learning materials, and a business game, specifically designed for land surveyor training. The proposed approach aims to strengthen interdisciplinary connections, expand the range of practical skills, and enhance students' independent cognitive activity.

Practical simulation of professional situations in business games, developing skills in land surveying and document preparation

The Applied Geology course studies the Earth's geochronology, the composition of rocks, minerals, and groundwater. Land surveyor training places special emphasis on the physical and mechanical properties of soils, which are crucial for predicting the behavior of real estate under load. Students develop skills in analyzing actual geological and engineering-geological data and learn to create maps and cross-sections.

Studying the course «Land Surveying» is the most important aspect of land management, related to establishing and legally formalizing land boundaries. This course teaches students the skills of preparing land survey plans and legally registering real estate. A strong emphasis is placed on mastering regulatory legal acts and methods for processing spatial data using GIS technologies.

Both disciplines involve a close connection between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, as well as an interdisciplinary approach, since the professional activities of specialists require an understanding of the geological, legal and geoinformation aspects of the work.

Therefore, a special role is given to interactive technologies, which allow the educational process to be organized in such a way as to best develop the required competencies.

Basic educational technologies

Lecture. A classic form of presenting systematized knowledge, supplemented by elements of dialogue, posing problematic questions, and visualization. Objective: to create a theoretical foundation. This is a traditional form of teaching, which, when covering introductory topics, especially with first-year students, can be insufficiently effective. Therefore, the need arose to develop fundamentally new approaches that combine active and interactive methods with elements of entertaining content. As an example, an introductory lecture on the subject «Applied Geology» for first-year students is considered. Lecture title: «Time Cubes + Earth Newsreel: A Revolutionary Approach to the Study of Geochronology.» The lecture is devoted to a discussion of a pressing issue in the modern teaching of geochronology: the difficulty of assimilating complex scientific concepts by students of different levels of preparation 3.. Traditional forms of teaching often prove ineffective, therefore, the need arose to develop fundamentally new approaches that combine active and interactive methods with elements of entertaining content. The lecture consists of two main sections: a game component («Time Cubes») and audiovisual aids (screening popular science films). The first section is devoted to a detailed examination of the method of using multicolored cubes symbolizing stages of geological time. Students play with these cubes, constructing a sequence of eras and learning to perceive historical processes visually and tactilely, which significantly improves comprehension and retention of the material. The second section presents the best films about the geological past of our planet, used in teaching. These films demonstrate the most important stages in the formation of the Earth, creating vivid images that complement the knowledge gained through working with cubes. The scenes they view help students gain a deeper understanding of the scale of changes that took place, develop spatial thinking, and learn to analyze scientific facts through the prism of visual information. Particular attention is paid to the synergy between the two approaches. It is shown how the combined use of cubes and films significantly enhances the learning process, increases student interest in the subject, and develops important intellectual skills such as memory, logic, and critical thinking. Thus, the lecture demonstrates a new, engaging, and effective approach to teaching geochronology, aimed at qualitatively changing traditional educational practices.

Museum pedagogy. This technology transforms the museum space into an active educational environment. The essence is the use of various museum exhibits to visualize and understand the theoretical material covered in the classroom 3.. After theoretical preparation, the group visits a geological museum and visually examines the collection presented. Next, each student independently selects a sample of a mineral or rock from the exhibition for primary diagnostics (color, luster, hardness, structure, inclusions). Photographic documentation is taken. In

the subsequent classroom lesson, students collect information about the deposit, age and practical application of the rock. They study morphological characteristics (based on GOSTs and reference books); geological history of formation; information about deposits and extraction methods; examples of use in economic activity. Special attention is paid to historical facts, for example, the role of a mineral or rock in the development of a region. General theses are heard during a seminar. Also, within the framework of the application of this technology, an interdisciplinary module is present. The group visits an art museum to search for works depicting geological and geomorphological features: rock outcrops; river valleys and ravines; rock outcrops; and architectural structures made of natural stone.

Students analyze: the accuracy of the reproduction of textures and colors; the correspondence of the depicted forms to real geological processes; the symbolic meaning of natural objects in the composition. The subsequent lesson includes a reflective-analytical stage: presentations of student research, a group discussion of the geological authenticity of artworks; discussions on how knowledge of mineralogy and petrography helps in surveying (for example, when assessing soil stability, identifying natural site boundaries). The use of museum pedagogy ensures: Clarity and authenticity. Working with authentic samples eliminates the abstractness of theoretical concepts. Students see real textures, structures, inclusions, which is critical for future professional activity. The combination of geology, history, art, and land management forms a holistic worldview of a specialist. Students master methods of collecting and analyzing data, working with scientific sources, and critically evaluating information. The opportunity to independently select a sample increases involvement and responsibility for the result. Skills in describing and classifying rocks are directly transferred to land management tasks: soil diagnostics during field surveys; assessment of the influence of geological processes on site boundaries; Documenting natural features in cadastral surveys. Discussing artwork allows students to understand how natural features influence the spatial organization of territories — a key aspect of land management. If you don't have access to museums, you can use digital collections (Google Arts & Culture, virtual tours), 3D models of samples, photo archives. Thus, museum pedagogy becomes a bridge between academic knowledge and professional practice, allowing students of land management to see geological processes not as abstract phenomena, but as real factors determining the appearance and use of land resources.

Inter-course exchange of educational and methodological materials. This is an interactive educational method based on **the principle of peer-to-peer learning**, which combines the creation of educational materials by first-year students, their subsequent examination by senior second-year students and joint reflection

3.. **Objective:** In-depth study of the subject through assignment design and peer

assessment. Students from different years exchange teaching materials (tests and puzzles), fulfilling a dual function: **authors** create assignments based on the material covered; **experts** analyze their peers' work, identify shortcomings, and suggest improvements.

Implementation stages. First-year students develop tests, puzzles, and practical assignments on the subjects covered in the first semester («geochronology,» «stratigraphy,» «rock types»). The assignments incorporate key concepts, theories, and practical exercises relevant to the first-year curriculum. Each student signs their full name and hands over the prepared assignments to second-year students. Second-year students solve and review assignments: The second-year students solve the assigned assignments, simultaneously refreshing their knowledge of the first-year curriculum. After reviewing their completed assignments, second-year students highlight errors, flaws in question formulation, and potential improvements. **Feedback and correction:** First-year students receive feedback and have the opportunity to adjust and improve their assignments. This promotes better assimilation of theoretical material and the development of critical thinking. Second-year students create new assignments: The second-year students then independently prepare similar assignments intended for first-year students, reinforcing their own learning material and applying new teaching approaches. At the final stage, both courses exchange feedback on the created assignments, highlighting the strengths and identifying the weaknesses of the teaching methods.

Advantages of the «Inter-course exchange of educational and methodological materials» technology

For 1st year students:

Deepening knowledge through creation. When creating tests and puzzles, first-year students are forced to: comprehend the material at a level sufficient to *convey it* to others; identify key concepts, distinguishing essential from non-essential; and develop formulations that eliminate ambiguity.

Receiving expert feedback. Comments from senior students allow you to: identify gaps in your own understanding; discover alternative ways to explain complex topics; and correct errors before the final assessment.

Reduced anxiety. Experience creating assignments increases confidence when taking tests.

For 2nd year students:

➤ **Developing critical thinking** — reviewing requires: providing reasoned justification for comments; distinguishing significant errors from technical inaccuracies; and proposing constructive improvements.

➤ **Developing mentoring skills** — senior-year students learn to explain complex concepts in simple terms; provide feedback; and understand the material from a beginner's perspective.

For the educational process as a whole:

- **Identifying problem areas** — analyzing typical errors in first-year students' work helps adjust the curriculum.
- **Strengthening inter-course cooperation** — a community of learners is formed where knowledge is transferred «horizontally».
- **Increased motivation** — an element of competition (who will create the most original puzzle) and recognition from senior students stimulate engagement.

For the teacher:

- **Diagnostic tool** — students' work demonstrates: the level of material assimilation; common misconceptions; the effectiveness of the methods used.
- **possibility of individualization:** Based on the analysis of puzzles and tests, it is possible to identify students with unconventional thinking (authors of original assignments) and those who require additional support (based on the number of errors in reviews).

Long-term effects:

- **developing a culture of feedback** — students learn to accept and give criticism constructively.
- **conscious mastery of terminology** — when coding concepts in puzzles or composing questions, a deep understanding of the meanings occurs.
- **readiness for professional communication** — the experience of reviewing simulates work situations where it is necessary to analyze other people's decisions and argue your position.

Thus, each student actively participates in the interaction process and strives to complete assignments well. Constructive dialogue between students of different levels of preparation develops the ability to give and receive criticism. The exchange of knowledge and support creates a friendly atmosphere within the team. The technology of intercourse assignment transfer stimulates the development of academic culture and maintains high educational standards. The methodology demonstrates multifaceted effectiveness, encompassing **both subject-specific and personal aspects.** levels of development of students.

A business game, «Modeling Professional Situations in the Cadastre.» This game emphasizes role-playing 1.. Second-year students assume the roles of a cadastral engineer, an applicant, and a registrar. The main goal is to reinforce theoretical knowledge through direct participation in the «game» process of land surveying using satellite coordinate determination methods. The process also hones communication, negotiation, and collective decision-making skills 2..

Practical tasks include: determining the coordinates of land plot turning points, creating the text and graphic portions of the cadastral plan in the Argo Drawing software, and preparing a verbal report on the work performed. Necessary equipment includes a GPS receiver, benchmarks, photographic equipment for surveying

the terrain, and a computer with the Argo Drawing software installed. The workflow includes office and field work, consisting of several stages.

Stage 1. Preliminary research. Before conducting on-site activities, a study of **the national spatial data system (NSDS) is conducted.**— a single state portal where information on real estate can be obtained. The absence of information on the selected plot in the Unified State Register of Real Estate (EGRN) is established. The main characteristics of the plot are determined: municipal ownership, intended for individual residential development.

Stage 2. Field visit. The group, accompanied by the instructor, travels to the site to be surveyed. Boundaries are visually identified and corner points are roughly located. Photographic documentation of the site is taken.

Stage 3. Site inspection report. An inspection report is prepared containing the initial site characteristics: a description of the site conditions (terrain, vegetation, infrastructure).

Stage 4. Geodetic survey. GPS technology is used to precisely measure the site's coordinates and develop a boundary mapping scheme for the actual terrain.

Stage 5. Compilation of the final cadastral plan. Based on the survey results, a cadastral plan is created, including the following information: coordinates of turning points, plot boundaries, total area, and a description of cadastral characteristics. A plot of $X \text{ m}^{2\text{is}}$ now formed and subject to official registration.

Stage 6: The results of the work are discussed during a group discussion. The «Client» accepts the results of the cadastral work. The «Registrar» carries out state registration and cadastral registration.

Thus, this educational technology is aimed at integrating theoretical knowledge and practical skills in land surveying, contributing to the development of professional competencies in future land surveyors and geodetic engineers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be concluded that the developed set of educational technologies has a positive impact on the quality of training for land surveying students. Implementation of these approaches contributes to increased student interest in learning, improved knowledge acquisition, and the development of professionally important competencies. Future research prospects include the development of specialized electronic platforms to support educational technologies and the expansion of the application of interactive methods in other areas of land survey training.

Modern educational technologies in land surveyor training are designed to ensure an optimal balance between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, a variety of learning formats to master the full range of necessary competencies, and conditions that promote graduates' social adaptation. Consequently, the

implementation of these approaches enables the preparation of qualified specialists prepared to successfully cope with rapidly changing legal regulations and innovative industry technologies.

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HOW CORPORATE WEBSITES HELP IN TEACHING: FACILITATING MULTI-LEVEL APPROACH

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Abstract. *Teaching foreign languages becomes a more complex task in non-linguistic universities as the difference between the levels of students' command of the language becomes enormous. The teacher has to balance the interests of all students in the group. Corporate websites are helpful as they provide authentic terminology and specific jargon dealing with certain sectors and industries. The texts sound more natural and contain fewer mistakes. Interesting content directly related to the future profession enables to engage low-performing students, so everyone benefits. Additional opportunities are provided by the use of AI that can considerably decrease time required for preparation of teaching materials.*

Key words: *non-linguistic universities, multi-level teaching, corporate websites, internet resources, project activities*

The English language is becoming more popular over years. It is helpful when travelling all over the world. It is broadening your career opportunities. Many parents believe that their children should be taught it well and that school classes are not enough. They find language courses or tutors, some of them even hire native speakers. As a result, many teenagers come to nonlinguistic universities with an excellent command of the language.

At the same time, there are a lot of students who were not given such opportunities. In many state schools the qualification of English teachers remains low due to lack of time for self-development and unavailability of engaging and methodologically efficient teaching materials. Many students are not interested in learning foreign languages because they do not see how they will be able to use them in their life. Moreover, new technologies enable to solve certain personal language-related tasks using gadgets. Thus, a modern smartphone can translate not only written texts, but also oral speech. All these factors result in poor knowledge of English that students of nonlinguistic universities demonstrate.

The existence of young people with so different command of English and language usage experience creates a lot of problems in nonlinguistic universities. Groups of students studying the foreign language together may comprise up to thirty students. Creating large groups is not a good practice, but, unfortunately, it is becoming more and more common. Teaching foreign languages in such large groups is already a nontrivial task. 1. The necessity of working simultaneously with people who can hardly read and those who speak fluently makes it even more difficult. 2, 3.

Multilevel teaching may be a way out. Teachers often use multi-level materials trying to offer manageable tasks to all subgroups of students. It should be noted that advanced students cause the greatest trouble for teachers who want every student to learn something new and improve their language.

First of all, materials for such students should be longer and more complex. There is no sufficient time to check everything done orally. Correcting lengthy written tasks of B2-C1 level requires a lot of extra time that many teachers don't have.

To solve this problem different types of project and team work can be employed. 4. In that case students to the task with their peers, have speaking practice with fellow-students fluent in English, correct each other, find solutions for more creative tasks than ordinary grammar and vocabulary practice exercises. Peer correction may be less professional than teacher's, but in language-learning having practice is much better than waiting for your turn most of the time. Even if some mistakes remain uncorrected, the usefulness of achieving your communicative goals in a foreign language cannot be overestimated. Eventually, the main purpose of foreign language teaching in a nonlinguistic university is to develop students' abilities to express their ideas and to respond to what is said by their conversation partner.

However, if you need to teach profession-related English instead of general in accordance with the university curriculum, it may be not so easy to find suitable materials. Ordinary university textbooks may be too easy and, consequently, boring. Special original textbooks from English-speaking countries may be too expensive. Moreover, the university administration and even state educational authorities may set restrictions on use of such materials.

An available and affordable solution can be found on the Internet. It is free and contains authentic texts for specialists in different fields. It is highly probable that these resources will be available to any of your students who have a laptop or a smartphone with an Internet connection. They are corporate websites of different businesses. They do not use paywalls to conceal information about the companies and the goods and services that they offer.

This new resource can be beneficially applied to some traditional exercises for group work, e.g. area exploration exercises. 5. The main difference is that websites are used instead of books or people in the community.

Nowadays, websites are owned by businesses of nearly all sectors, so you can always find something dealing with the future job of your students. Websites of medical centers for future doctors, websites of IT companies for to-be programmers and websites of construction companies for prospective engineers to name a few. These resources combine authentic professional vocabulary and information about the businesses working in the particular field, their goods or services. All you have to do is check several websites in advance, make a list of sections that most resources have and think over several tasks related to the information available on respective corporate websites.

As our university specializes in civil engineering, the experiment we have performed involved 2-month work with corporate websites of construction companies of English-speaking countries. Students worked in pairs or individually. Each week they received a task dealing with a specific topic. The topics discussed included (1) general information about the company, (2) significant projects of the company, (3) services that the company offers to its customers, (4) HR policy, including training, internship and apprenticeship, (5) occupational safety, (6) sustainability and environment-friendly policies.

Students with a good command of English studied the websites of construction companies and presented their findings to the rest of the group. It was necessary to prepare the students with poor level of English so that they were able to understand their fellow-students. The examples of such preparation include provision of the list of key words with translation as well as pictures, schemes and other visual aids. The sentences in such presentations had to be rather short and simple as listening is the activity that causes greatest difficulties and anxiety among students who do not know the language well.

To ensure that everyone listens the presenters prepared comprehension tasks, in particular, questions, true/false statements, crosswords, gap-filling exercises, etc. As far as questions are concerned, the difficult ones were given in writing before the presentation, while the easier ones were asked orally after the presentation. The 'passive' part of the group suggested additionally discussing the information presented in the native language. This enabled to involve still more students.

Role-plays were popular among all students. In one of them the active participants (the students who studied the websites) played the role of HR specialists of construction companies who came to the university to offer summer internships for students and permanent work for future graduates. Several pairs and individual participants competed for potential interns and employees. After they had finished presentations, students decided which company they would like to join and gave their reasons. Low-performing students were given models with gaps that they could use to express their opinions.

When using non-standard teaching practices, it is necessary to evaluate whether these methods are really better than traditional ones and can provide some additional benefits to the students. Besides, special attention should be paid to feedback.

After our experiment we performed two surveys: one among “active” participants and the other among those who were mainly passive listeners. In the first group everyone considered the project to be useful. 88% mentioned that they had speaking practice and enjoyed it, 75% said that their vocabulary had enlarged during the experiment, 81% noted that they learned about large-scale construction projects, 75% became aware of companies’ requirements to potential employees and 68% found out how the activities of construction companies are organized.

The “passive” participants were also satisfied, saying that they had learned something new (89%), something useful (82%), and had enlarged their vocabulary (78%). 74% found the tasks offered by active participants after presentations interesting and engaging.

Thus, our experiment confirmed that corporate websites are a very useful source of information that can be used in teaching foreign languages to university students with a good command of the language. There are methods enabling to involve the whole group in the process, including low-performing students if they are provided with models and allowed to discuss certain issues in the native language.

After emergence of AI systems, it may be even easier to apply this method. The teachers do not need to study all the websites in advance. They can delegate some tasks to chatbots. They can also use AI capabilities to generate easy tasks for low-performing students.

At present we are working at scaling this experiment to economics-related professions. For students of economics, websites may belong to such sectors as banks, consulting companies, audit companies, advertising companies. Students can rotate, some may be active when banks are discussed, others may actively study websites of advertising companies.

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TRENDS IN THE USE OF COMBINED ELEMENTS WITH ROTATION IN RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS

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Abstract. *This article examines trends in the use of combined elements with rotations in rhythmic gymnastics. The study focused on the competitive routines of rhythmic gymnasts at the 2000–2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games. The authors examine the frequency of these elements in their competitive routines, the most effective transitions from element to element, and the gymnasts' errors in performing combined elements with various apparatus. The study utilized qualitative and quantitative methods (analysis of specialized literature and program documents, video recordings of performances, expert assessment, and mathematical statistics) to provide a detailed analysis of the structure and frequency of combined elements including rotations. The key findings of the study include the identification of popular combinations, the identification of key errors in the execution of these elements, and confirmation of their relevance to the development of gymnastics.*

Key words: *rhythmic gymnastics, combined elements, turns, execution technique.*

Introduction. Rhythmic gymnastics, despite its relative youth, is rapidly developing and establishing a strong position in the international sporting arena. Modern competitions are characterized by a high level of competition and continually increasing demands, posing new challenges for athletes and coaches to improve the technique and expressiveness of their competitive performances. As

a result of many years of systematic work, significant changes have occurred in the rules governing the content and execution of routines. Routines have become more structured, attention has been given to the quantity and quality of elements of increasing complexity, and the overall density of competition routines has increased 2; 3..

One of the key aspects determining the success of gymnasts on the international stage is the use of complex combinations, including combined elements 4., which are a harmonious combination of two or more isolated elements 1.. Combined elements are becoming an important tool for enhancing the spectacle and intensity of rhythmic gymnastics performances. Their inclusion in a program reduces the time spent performing the same set of movements, while simultaneously increasing the complexity and aesthetics of the composition. The use of such elements gives athletes a significant advantage in an increasingly competitive environment, allowing them to stand out from their competitors through unique technique and masterful execution. Thus, combined elements are a key factor in success in the modern world of rhythmic gymnastics, playing a significant role in achieving high athletic results.

Study Results and Discussion. The trend in the use of combined elements was identified using video analysis of gymnasts' performances at the Olympic Games from 2000 to 2024, as well as at the BRICS Rhythmic Gymnastics Games, a multi-sport competition held in Kazan from June 20 to 22, 2024. Observation protocols recorded elements of the competition routines of ten finalist gymnasts. Each participant performed four routines with various apparatus (hoop, ball, clubs, ribbon), depending on the rules of a specific Olympic cycle (and additionally, rope). A total of 320 competition routines were analyzed (Figure 1).

Figure 1 — Frequency of performance of combined elements at the Olympic Games from 2000 to 2024 and the BRICS Games 2024

Based on a retrospective analysis, the use of combined elements is characterized by unevenness and undulation, with a tendency for quantitative indicators to

repeat in a twelve-year cycle: 64 elements were used in 2000, 71 in 2004, 78 in 2008, 108 in 2012, 13 in 2016, 25 in 2020, and a high figure of 109 elements was again reached in 2024. The 2024 BRICS Games also used 109 combined elements.

That is, despite changes in the requirements of the rules for competitive compositions, the conducted study confirmed the presence of a stable tendency towards a cyclical complication of combinations due to combined elements (Table 1).

Table 1 — Use of combined elements in the competition programs of finalists at the Olympic Games from 2000 to 2024 and the BRICS Games 2024 (n=10; number)

combination	OG 2000	OG 2004	OG 2008	OG 2012	OG 2016	OG 2020	OG 2024	BRICS 2024
Equilibrium + equilibrium	49	54	21	61	8	15	82	54
Balance + Turn	1	3	2	2	1	0	16	25
Balance + jump	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Turn + turn	6	8	45	45	4	9	7	28
Turn + balance	8	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
Turn + jump	0	4	0	0	0	0	4	0
Jump + jump	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jump + balance	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0
Jump + turn	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
M±m	7.1 ± 5.3	7.9 ± 5.8	8.7 ± 5.1	12.0 ± 7.9	1.4 ± 0.9	2.8 ± 1.8	12.1 ± 8.9	12.1 ± 6.5
V (%)	224.94	221.69	177.54	196.63	193.08	196.17	220.88	160.08

This fact confirms the continued relevance and importance of such elements for successful performances, even as judging criteria and difficulty standards change. Combined elements remain an integral part of modern rhythmic gymnastics competitions.

At the Olympic Games from 2000 to 2024, as well as at the 2024 BRICS Games, which were also considered due to the non-participation of Russian gymnasts at the XXXIII Olympic Games in Paris, athletes performed combined elements. The highest number of elements performed by finalists was at the 2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games, where the average number of combined elements was 12.1, as well as at the 2012 Olympics, where the average was 12.0 combined elements. At the 2000, 2004, and 2008 Olympics, the average number of combined elements performed was 7.1, 7.9, and 8.7. The lowest number of combination elements performed by finalist gymnasts at the 2016 and 2020 Olympic Games was recorded, where the average numbers were 1.4 and 2.8 elements.

A statistical analysis revealed that the period studied, from 2000 to 2024 inclusive, showed significant variability in the number of complex elements performed, reflected by a high standard error and coefficient of variation. Maximum instability was evident at the initial stages of observation — at the 2000 and 2004 Olympic Games, where the coefficient of variation exceeded 220%, indicating significant unevenness in the performance of combined elements. Despite some exceptions (for example, at the 2024 Olympic Games, where an increase in the coefficient of variation was again observed), the overall picture is characterized by decreasing instability. This is particularly evident at the 2024 BRICS Games, where the minimum coefficient of variation — approximately 160%—was recorded. Moreover, despite changes in competition rules and a generational shift in athletes, an increase in variation and the number of combined elements used in gymnasts' competitive routines are observed.

The frequency of using combined elements including rotations was analyzed separately at the competitions under consideration (Table 2).

Table 2 — Indicators of the use of combined elements with turns in the competition programs of finalist gymnasts at the 2000–2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games in rhythmic gymnastics (n=40; number)

combination	OG 2000	OG 2004	OG 2008	OG 2012	OG 2016	OG 2020	OG 2024	BRICS 2024
Balance + Turn	1	3	2	2	1	0	16	25
Turn + turn	6	8	45	45	4	9	7	28
Turn + balance	8	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
Turn + jump	0	4	0	0	0	0	4	0
Jump + turn	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	15	16	47	47	5	10	27	54

It has been established that combination elements with rotations remain popular in rhythmic gymnasts' competitive programs, regardless of the presence or absence of incentives in the form of additional points for their combinations. Statistical analysis shows that the average frequency of combination elements with rotations varies significantly from the BRICS Olympics to the BRICS Games (Figure 2). The number of elements indicates the stability of individual element combinations: the most common are combinations of two rotations and a balance with a turn. Thus, the average number of elements with rotations performed at different stages ranges from 5.0 to 54. Moreover, the high variability of indicators confirms the significant variation in the performance of combination elements from one Olympics to the next. The greatest diversity of combination elements

with rotations was recorded at the 2004 and 2024 Olympics, and the highest overall indicators were recorded at the BRICS Games.

The dynamics of the frequency of use of combined elements with a turn by finalists of the 2000–2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games in rhythmic gymnastics is clearly shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 — Dynamics of the frequency of use of combined elements with a turn by finalists of the 2000–2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games in rhythmic gymnastics (n=40; %)

Based on the data presented in the graph, peak rates occurred at the 2008 and 2012 Olympics, where the frequency reached 117.5%, and at the BRICS Games (135%). After declining to 12.5% in 2016, the frequency of use increases to 67.5% at the Olympic Games by 2024, reaching its peak at the 2024 BRICS Games. This indicates a trend toward increasing complexity and spectacle of combined elements in future gymnasts' routines.

During the study, transition methods from the first part of a combined element to the second were analyzed separately (Table 3). It was found that at the Sydney Olympics, each movement category had a roughly equal distribution. However, transitions from the first form of a combined element to the second were most often accomplished by moving the supporting leg (7 times). In 2004, the situation changed: The number of combinations with movements of the supporting and free legs increased (up to 12 cases), while highly qualified gymnasts stopped using transitions with movements of the torso.

At the Beijing Olympics, the primary transition from the first element to the second was accomplished by moving the free leg (13 times) to combine two turns, and by moving the supporting leg (6 times). The torso was moved only once during the balance combined with the turn, creating significant inertia for the subsequent rapid rotation after the static balance phase. In London 2012, gymnasts frequently used the free leg (7 times) to combine two turns, and more transitions using torso movements appeared (6 times in total). In Rio de Janeiro, by contrast,

transitions were performed exclusively using the supporting and free legs, which were performed a total of 2 times each.

Table 3 — Methods of transition from element to element in combined elements with rotation for finalists at the Olympic Games from 2000 to 2024 and the 2024 BRICS Games in rhythmic gymnastics (n=40; number)

Transition \ Combination	Balance + Turn	Turn + turn	Turn + balance	Turn + jump
2000 Sydney Olympic Games				
Movement of the supporting leg	1	3	3	-
Free leg movement	1	1	0	-
Torso movement	1	1	1	-
2004 Athens Olympic Games				
Movement of the supporting leg	2	5	0	4
Free leg movement	2	5	1	4
Torso movement	0	0	0	0
2008 Beijing Olympic Games				
Movement of the supporting leg	0	6	-	-
Free leg movement	0	13	-	-
Torso movement	1	4	-	-
2012 London Olympic Games				
Movement of the supporting leg	1	0	-	-
Free leg movement	0	7	-	-
Torso movement	1	5	-	-
2016 Olympic Games in Rio de Janeiro				
Movement of the supporting leg	1	1	-	-
Free leg movement	1	1	-	-
Torso movement	0	0	-	-
2020 Tokyo Olympics				
Movement of the supporting leg	-	0	0	-
Free leg movement	-	2	1	-
Torso movement	-	3	1	-
2024 Olympic Games in Paris				
Movement of the supporting leg	4	0	-	1
Free leg movement	4	2	-	1
Torso movement	2	2	-	0
BRICS Games 2024				
Movement of the supporting leg	5	2	0	-
Free leg movement	5	7	1	-
Torso movement	5	2	1	-

At the 2020 Olympic Games, transitions were performed using torso movement (4 times) and free leg movement (3 times). In 2024, Olympic rhythmic gymnastics finalists preferred transitions using the supporting and free legs (4 times each) to combine balances with turns, and the free leg and torso movements (2 times each) to combine two turns. At the BRICS Games, a greater number of combination elements and their transitions were presented, with eight combination elements performed using torso movement, most often to combine balances with turns. Balance-turn combinations utilized equal movements of the supporting and free legs and the torso (5 times each). In addition, to combine two turns, transitions using the free leg were most often used (7 times).

When connecting with a jump, a combination of the supporting-push-off leg and the free-swinging leg is always used, which is characteristic of jumping elements due to three factors: optimal push-off, protection from injury and the shock-absorbing effect (“spring”).

The errors made by the finalist gymnasts of the 2000–2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games in rhythmic gymnastics in combined elements with turns are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 — Errors made by finalists of rhythmic gymnastics competitions at the 2000–2024 Olympic Games and the 2024 BRICS Games when performing combined elements with turns (n=40; number)

Analyzing the dynamics of errors made by gymnasts at the 2024 BRICS Games, it was found that the greatest number of errors occurred in the performance of exercises with

Ribbon, where 12 errors were recorded. Hoop routines rank second in terms of error frequency, with 11, and the gymnasts committed 10 errors in the clubs routine. The most successful execution of combined elements was in the ball routine, where only eight errors were recorded. The total number of errors across all four competitive routines was 41. The most common errors in the execution of combined elements in the BRICS Games finals were heel support (16 times) and insufficient amplitude (14 times). Gymnasts also demonstrated unsteadiness during the

execution of elements on multiple occasions (7), less frequently, athletes moved from their positions (3 times), and hopping on the supporting leg during complex elements was observed sporadically (1 time).

Conclusion. The conducted analysis confirmed a consistent trend in the use of combined elements in the competitive programs of elite gymnasts at the Olympic and BRICS Games. The study results indicate that over the past 24 years, the quantitative and qualitative indicators of the use of combined elements with turns in the competitive programs of elite gymnasts have undergone significant changes. However, combined elements remain a key factor in the complexity and, consequently, the success of gymnasts' performances, despite changes in competition rules. The increase in their number confirms the continuing trend of increasing the complexity and spectacle of competition programs. Diversity in the combination of elements with turns is achieved through different methods of combining them. While initially, transitions using the supporting leg were predominant in combinations, later they became more diverse and included movements of the free leg and torso. The quality of execution of combined elements with turns is determined not only by their complexity but also by the specific movements of the apparatus, which have different physical characteristics. In this regard, technical errors that arise during their implementation are associated, first, with the need to coordinate the work of the subject and the coordination structure of the combined element with rotation.

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A WORK OF ART AS A SOURCE OF INNUMERABLE MEANINGS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes those features of a work of art that do not give any of the parties involved in the discussion of the work of art an epistemological or socio-cultural advantage over all others. None of the interpretations of a work of art can be considered as the “only possible” one, not only because all of them reveal only a few of its innumerable meanings, but also because the very process of interpreting the ideal content and meaning of a work of art turns out to be the creation of a new meaning. And this new meaning may differ significantly from the original intention of the author, which always remains in question.*

Keywords: *work of art, meaning, material products, spiritual products, interpretation, epistemological program of art, author and public.*

Unlike scientific, philosophical or theological products of spiritual creativity, works of art become objects of discussion not only by the community of artists, professional art theorists and critics, but also by the enlightened or casual public. Everyone who perceives a work of art and participates in discussions about the “legitimacy” of one or another interpretation of it is confident, as a rule, that it is their understanding that is “correct”, authentic to the author’s intention and providing a basis for making judgments about the socio-cultural significance of this work.

Yet, the most significant features of the relationship between the creators of works of art and all those who perceive these works are determined by the nature of the spiritual products to which the works of art belong.

Any product of human activity as a subject of culture is an objectified ideality: a thought, an idea, an impression, an experience, a meaning. However, in the products of material culture, the ideality acquires a material form, being embodied directly in the material essence of the products of human activity: buildings as dwellings, books as a product of the printing industry, power plants as an energy source.

As to the products of spiritual culture, the ideality remains in them in its own ideal form of existence and is embodied in equally ideal thoughts, theories or artistic images, the material shell of which is only a carrier, but not an expression

of the essence and content of these products. There is always an ideal, spiritual content behind the material form of a product of spiritual culture. It is spirituality, the ideality of the content that is the essence of the products of spiritual culture 2..

The creation of material products cannot be considered spiritually meaningless. Yet, the meaning of a material product of any level of complexity is always finite and is exhausted by the functional purpose of a particular thing, while the meaning of a product of spiritual culture is inexhaustible.

Any spiritual product is created in order to transform the space of cultural senses and encourage the subject of culture to further expand this space. Unlike a material product, which cannot be “bigger” than the idea, a spiritual product always goes beyond the author’s idea, since this idea itself is only an occasion for reflection, interpretation, and the creation of one’s own meaning by all who master this product, striving to satisfy the need for cognition, understanding, comprehension of reality, aesthetic enjoyment, and empathy 6..

Moreover, when we come into contact with a work of art, we perceive it not only as a product of creative imagination, but also as a unique revelation of reality in its authenticity. Each work of art gives the perceiving subject a unique opportunity to experience a personal artistic and aesthetic discovery of unknown, previously unseen sides of reality.

Each work of art asserts by its existence that reality may be completely different from what we used to think of it.

The epistemological program of art does not presuppose obtaining an intersubjective image of being-in-itself, but claims only and exclusively to a personal perception of reality, to obtain an image of reality that is characterized by the maximum possible individualization of the form of perception and the way of expressing information about reality received in this image 4.. Nothing in this image should be an object of verification for truth, because nothing claims to correspond to reality in itself, but only to reflect something that no one has ever displayed anywhere and, most likely, will never be able to display in this form. But that is precisely why a work of art, as a reflection of one (any) aspect of an infinitely diverse world in one (any) of the possible ways, cannot be false, or — we are talking about a “falsity” that cannot be established.

Indeed, what would the “falsity” of a painting, a sonata, a sculpture, or a dance mean? It is only obvious that the artist sees the world differently from others, that he sees what others do not see. But it is precisely this special, personal, and unique vision that the artist claims. As a single, unique case, an individual understanding does not require a truth check precisely because its truth cannot be refuted in principle. The claim to uniqueness of vision or understanding transforms a work of art into an ontologically irrefutable one.

A work of art is always “true” as a reflection of the artist’s own worldview and, perhaps, of a certain number of those whose worldview coincides with the author’s.

But just as in the field of morality, it is not enough to have good intentions in order to be moral, in art it is not enough to be truthful in order to create a work of art. You can be absolutely truthful and completely untalented. The measure of truth in art coincides with the measure of artistry, and the problem of artistic understanding of the meaning of human existence is inseparable from the search for artistic means of expressing the achieved understanding 3.. That is why being true in art means being a work of art.

Only imitation is false, because it is not a work of art in the proper sense. But in every genuine work of art, there is at least a shadow, a ghost of the artist's absolute truthfulness, which allowed him to create a "monument" to true "perceptions and affects", perhaps even despite his own cynicism. That's why we can say that every artist is justified by his creations, and genius and villainy are truly "two incompatible things".

Thus, if we have a work of art in front of us, then it is true. But how do we determine what exactly is in front of us? The assessment of the conformity of the created to what is called a "work of art" is carried out, like any other assessment, on the basis of accepted patterns and standards, and therefore is always not only relative and historical, but also predetermined by ontological prerequisites related to the being-in-itself.

What are the ontological prerequisites underlying the attribution of a particular product of human activity to art? What gives the author, critics, or the public reason to believe, for example, that Michelangelo's "Pieta" and a mountain of tires or a pile of clay belong to the same kind of existence — art? This question remains almost the main one in all discussions about art from antiquity to postmodernity 8.. But even if the theoretical grounds for classifying certain products of human creativity as works of art remain uncertain, the real existence of art as a cultural phenomenon does not provide any grounds for classifying any human actions and any forms of self-expression of individuals as works of art.

The novelty of the meanings and the uniqueness of the artistic form of their expression act both as a manifestation of the essence of the work of art and as the reason for the rejection of this work by other cultural subjects. In order to understand and experience the "alien" ideality, a person who perceives a work of art must recreate the artistic images of the work in his mind, transform his own images of consciousness into others and construct perceived images from his own ideas and experiences in the process of interpretation. The effect of understanding the meaning of a work of art and experiencing its content occurs only when the ideal images of the perceiving subject's consciousness coincide with the result of interpreting the artistic images of the perceived work of art. Such a coincidence is possible only if the creator of a work of art and the cultural subject who perceives this work have a common value and sense resources of vital activity. Otherwise, the result of artistic

creation will be perceived as an unknown product of socio-cultural activity, the attribution of which to works of art requires a new level of comprehension of the world from those who perceive this product themselves 5..

None of the interpretations of a work of art can be considered as the “only possible” one, not only because all of them reveal only a few of its innumerable meanings, but also because the very process of interpreting the ideal content and meaning of a work of art turns out to be, in essence, the creation of a new meaning. And this new meaning may differ significantly from the original intention of the author, which always remains in question. Therefore, not only the public is deeply mistaken in expressing their claims to the author of the work, but also the creators themselves, who believe that the public should perceive only those meanings that, as it seems to the authors, they put into their works.

Nevertheless, the postmodern idea of the “death of the author” distorts the very essence of artistic creation 1; 7.. A work of art is “bigger than the author” and exists as an independent phenomenon of socio-cultural existence only because the Author has created a unique object capable of inducing new and new meanings in the minds of each of the subjects perceiving it. The urge to create meanings in the process of interpretation is created solely by the work of art itself, which, in turn, is always the product of the creativity of a well-defined, even if unknown, Author-Artist.

The “idol of one’s own opinion”, the worship of which is cultivated in modern education, makes young people extremely naive and ignorant in matters of knowledge of the world, understanding and interpreting works of art.

The total dilettantism of the public and the formal “mastery” of the creators of works of art lead to the disappearance of artistry, which cannot be replaced either by the authors’ stories about their works, or by the public’s willingness to perceive any act of self-expression by anyone and anywhere as artistic creation. The truly artistic content of works of art is expressed in an artistic form that does not need explanations and has the ability to directly affect a person’s feelings, creating or suppressing an impulse to interpret the content.

Works of art cannot exist without material carriers and techniques of execution. But the highest level of mastery is the creation of material carriers that have completely transformed into an artistic form of expression of ideal sense content and have become “invisible” to everyone who perceives a work of art. Any attempts to encourage a person to reflect on meanings through acts, gestures, or outrageous antics that cause even physiological disgust may draw attention to socially significant issues, but they have nothing to do with aesthetic attitudes in general and artistic creativity — in particular.

Despite the fact that every person who perceives a work of art is an autonomous subject of interpretation, in the process of which meanings may be born that do not coincide with either the author’s intention or the prevailing aesthetic ideas,

everyone who perceives a work of art must be aware of the limitations of individual interpretative resources and the possibility of many different opinions.

Ultimately, the fundamental basis of communication between creators of works of art and the public should be universal norms of sociality, prescribing all cultural subjects to suppress their animal instincts in the process of interacting with other people and to respect their socio-cultural essence in themselves and in their opponents.

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A SHOGENSUKOV'S PROSE IN THE MIRROR OF BOOK GRAPHICS

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Abstract. *It so happened that the stories “Spring Sofiyat” and “I Will Call by Your Name” by Kabardian writer Adam Shogentsukov were illustrated not by Kabardian graphic artists, but by artists of other nationalities. This is interesting because it allows the reader to see the lives of Kabardians through the eyes of two ethnic groups. The author of this article focused on certain aspects of the worldview of the Russian artists who illustrated the Kabardian writer’s stories and concluded that the Adyghe (Kabardinian) mentality, so vividly evident in Shogentsukov’s works, was not reflected in their drawings.*

Keywords: *illustration cycles, individual creative style, book artist, ethnic and gender issues, Adyghe mentality, feminism.*

In recent decades, the national worldviews of so-called small peoples have been rapidly lost. In this sense, the Kabardians are no exception, as the classic Kabardian literary figure Adam Shogentsukov constantly reminds us. This makes his works all the more valuable — historically and artistically rich depictions of the authentic life of his native people in the 20th century, which will undoubtedly be of great significance for future generations of Kabardians.

This master of words paints a panoramic view of an Adyghe village, truthfully and realistically recreating the national character, aesthetic, and ethical values of the ethnic group. The author does not limit himself to a vivid depiction of the lives of his people, but strives to strengthen their national identity. Having penetrated the very essence of Adyghe reality and sensed the unique character traits of his fellow tribesmen, he created compelling, ethnically defined images of his people’s lives, successfully describing a national image of the world within the system of Adyghe ontological coding symbols. The writer successfully projects the ancient matrices of the Kabardian artistic consciousness, their archetypes, and concepts onto the present day. The author brilliantly captured the very essence of folk life, the existential dimension of the Adyghe world, which is particularly evident in the villages.

Adam Shogentsukov was deeply concerned with the feminine sociocultural status of Kabardian women and the problem of their new gender identity, which transformed the centuries-old archetypal image of the mountain woman. The main theme of the writer's works is the personal and social relationships between men and women, and he is not characterized by the lack of alternatives to the male worldview.

The transformation of Adyghe ontological norms is convincingly reflected in two of his remarkable stories: "Spring Sofiyat" and "I Will Call by Your Name." The dramatic changes in the psychology of Kabardian women, which began in the 1920s and 1930s as a result of the radical upheaval of the customs and traditions of the indigenous peoples, with ancient archetypes being replaced by "new, advanced" mountain women — activists, champions, and producers — could not have gone unnoticed by the author. Naturally, their behavioral style and social status changed. For example, in the story "Spring Sofiyat," A. Shogentsukov presents a very realistic model of Kabardian society as it emerged by the 1960s. Adam Ogurlievich is acutely aware of the changes that have taken place in the lives of Kabardians, which have affected not only family life but also the social status of the "new" Kabardian woman, who now acts not only as mothers and housewives but also as participants in production and community life. And this didn't happen overnight: she had to endure numerous trials associated with the so-called "emancipation" of mountain women, which was often violent, as evidenced by documents from the 1920s and 1930s. It was during this time that a new gender identity began to emerge, dramatically altering women's gender behavior.

By the 1960s, which Adam Shogentsukov describes, the gender consciousness and behavior of mountain women had noticeably transformed under the pressure of social change. Women had already been drawn into public service, often performing men's heavy labor, as, for example, does the story's heroine, tractor driver Sofiyat. Many women accepted this new lifestyle as natural, sincerely striving to fit into modern norms. These were no longer women dependent on men, but strong, self-sufficient, and leading industrialists. Such was Sofiyat.

It should be noted that both the writer and the illustrators of his stories strive to faithfully capture the Soviet era, reflecting the unique character and national flavor of life in Kabarda's rural inhabitants, while offering a rather optimistic assessment of the current situation. In depicting Kabardian reality, Shogentsukov strove not for superficial verisimilitude, but rather, penetrating the very essence of life, creating compelling images of his contemporaries. Even the ideological principles the writer relied on, one might even say his outright propaganda for a new way of life, did not negatively impact the artistic quality of his works.

Adam Shogentsukov's books, rich in content and distinctive in form, were no coincidence in their appeal to book illustrators, who sought to give verbal images visual form. While attempting to capture the uniqueness of the writer's world, they simultaneously

did not forget to demonstrate their own originality, a difficult task. It so happened that his stories were illustrated by, so to speak, artists of other nationalities, both local and from the capital. Naturally, they were not given the opportunity to perceive the values of another culture in the same way as representatives of indigenous peoples. Since Adam Ogurlievich's ontological level of world cognition is always ethnically marked, the illustrators of his literary texts manage to capture and embody this national specificity in their drawings, with varying degrees of approximation to the original.

When creating the illustrations for the story "Sofiyat's Spring," book illustrators E. I. Levandovskaya and V. I. Sapkin likely didn't think as deeply about the subject matter as the author, limiting themselves to illustrating the story's plot points. Thus, the artistic coordinates of the writer and the illustrators differ greatly. The visual part of the story "Sofiyat's Spring," illustrated by E. I. Levandovskaya, is quite ascetic. It captures two important moments in the heroine's life: the beginning of her working life and her first love. In the title page, closely linked to the typesetting, the reader/viewer sees a wide field and a small tractor, with which Sofiyat seems to have merged, becoming its appendage. Even the artist's trick of depicting only a narrow strip of arable land, rather than the entire field, does not alter the essence of the drawing: the field seems to absorb and depersonalize the girl.

In Adam Shogentsukov's work, the image of the "advanced" woman, a modern rural worker inextricably linked to the collective, forms the face of an era and acquires the characteristic traits of the time. She is a person of a new social formation, with a new gender psychology. One of the writer's key themes, egalitarianism, is reflected in the social lives of the story's characters, in their work. Sofiyat, who works like male tractor drivers, without any "allowances" for the weaker sex, is depicted by the writer as a shock worker, a "record-breaker," but, most importantly, as the master of her own destiny. This image is certainly propagandistic, but at the same time quite realistic, since there were indeed many such women in the Soviet Union. E. Levandovskaya, however, somewhat contradicts the author by downplaying the girl's social role in her opening drawing. Here, the discrepancy between the writer's and the artist's interpretations of Sofiyat's character is clearly evident. However, the illustrator succeeded in capturing the joy, triumph of happiness, and love in A. Shogentsukov's heroine at the book's conclusion. The drawing, which depicts a woman's silhouette against a bright sky near a still-unbloomed tree, is optimistic and conveys a sense of freedom and spiritual renewal, resonating with the writer's narrative. (Fig. 1)

It's impossible not to notice that Levandovskaya, like her other Russian colleagues, uses the tonality of the Russian worldview in her drawings with ethno-imperative regularity; their style is unmistakably Russian. The ability to think in terms of one's own nation is transmitted to a person at a genetic level. V. G. Belinsky already said that "a true artist senses nationality within himself and therefore involuntarily imposes its stamp on his works." Belinsky, 1979, p. 186. N. V. Gogol echoes

him: "True nationality consists not in the description of a sarafan, but in the very spirit of the people. A poet can be national even when he describes a completely alien world, but views it through the eyes of his national element, the eyes of his people." Gogol, 1952, p. 52.

The illustrations for the story "Sofiat's Spring" by artist and illustrator V. I. Sapkin, who arguably created more compelling images of literary characters than E. Levandovskaya, conclude on a positive note. By storyboarding the story's plot into numerous small-scale initial drawings, the content of which is easily discernible by the reader/viewer, the book illustrator not only managed to deeply understand the writer's intentions but also conveyed his own perception of the story in the drawings. The compositional structure of the text, the cover decoration, and the hand-drawn typographic elements, all created by V. Sapkin, contribute to the revelation of the essence of the literary text. (Fig. 2)

"Sofiat's Spring" also attracted the attention of artists V. I. Beketov (Nalchik, 1972) and N. D. Korobeynikov (Moscow, 1956). Because the story is based on a captivating plot, it lends itself easily to artistic interpretation and, refracted by the artists' imagination, takes on visual forms, significantly enhancing the emotional impact of the literary work on the reader. However, the writer's ontological revelations, archetypal habits, and specific features of the Adyghe mentality are far from fully reflected in the Russian artists' drawings, which testifies to the ethnic bias of the Russian worldview relative to the Adyghe one. It must be acknowledged that the artists who illustrated "Spring of Sofiyat" failed to attain the story's philosophical depth or find a pictorial language sufficiently adequate to the verbal language of Adam Shogentsukov.

When becoming acquainted with Adam Shogentsukov's work, one immediately notices that the theme of the city is practically absent from his work. He is much closer to the village, which he sees as the guardian of the people's high moral standards and national identity. However, even here, he often becomes disillusioned, witnessing how quickly the traditional moral foundations of the villagers are crumbling. The writer turned to village life not only to identify the causes of negative social phenomena but also to seek ways to halt the degradation of rural residents and strengthen the national identity of the Kabardians.

While working on "village prose," the writer often notices not signs of an idyllic life in the Kabardian village, but the beginnings of negative changes that frighten him because their direction is unclear. Only at first glance does it seem that, according to the ancient adats, all the rules of village life are observed, but in reality, irreversible processes are taking place. Adam Shogentsukov's position on this issue is particularly acutely reflected in his prose, particularly in the story "I Will Call You by Your Name," which resonated widely with the public and was repeatedly reprinted by local and Moscow publishers. The life story of a girl who found herself in a difficult situation when she was abducted by an unloved man was not simply

fiction. She was forced to choose between her personal happiness and the “honor and dignity” of those close to her, who, for selfish reasons, practically sold her out.

A contemporary and highly artistic example of Kabardian literature, the compelling images of his contemporaries created by Adam Shogentsukov could not fail to attract the attention of book artists. To enhance the story’s emotional impact on readers, they supplemented it with illustrations, primarily educational in nature, helping readers from other regions of the country to understand the literary text more deeply and, most importantly, adequately perceive the unique Caucasian atmosphere with which they were unfamiliar. After all, the captivating and engaging works of this master of words were in demand throughout the Soviet Union.

Adam Shogentsukov’s remarkable prose, which has long been part of the cultural code of the Kabardians, offered book artists an excellent opportunity to showcase their talents. Each of them, in their own way, conveys a particular state of mind and psychological makeup of the character. The style of each artist’s illustrations varies according to the author’s talent and the particular reading of the text. Therefore, the visual images created by the illustrators vary greatly.

One of the first to create a series of drawings for the story “I’ll Call You by Your Name” was the Moscow graphic artist B. A. Mesropyan (Moscow, 1970, Sovetsky Pisatel Publishing House). The artist retells the story’s plot visually, framed into thematic drawings. This narrative approach allows him to penetrate the deep meaning of certain events described in the work and highlight the story’s main conflicts through the development of character and psychology. Using minimal artistic means, B. Mesropyan constructs the *mise-en-scène*, skillfully conveying the dynamics of events, the appearance, and the inner state of the characters in his drawings.

The emotional tone of the narrative is set by the title page, depicting a car speeding down a rural street, carrying Zalina away to face the difficult trials of fate. (Fig. 3) This life-changing event is preceded by the girl’s happy youth, which the artist also reflected in his drawings. In one of them, we see her, full of joy and peace, standing by the window with a bouquet of flowers left by her lover, Musabi. (Fig. 4) A different mood is conveyed by the opening to the second part of the story, which depicts Zalina’s grandfather sitting in deep thought under a tree. The third part opens with an illustration showing Musabi, who has gone to the farm to “put an end” to the protracted drama of his beloved’s abduction, rightly believing that his fate will be decided by Zalina’s final choice between him and Khapatsha, who kidnapped her.

Of course, the author’s masterful penmanship helps the reader vividly and visually imagine the characters and events of the story. Nevertheless, the book’s illustrations were not superfluous, as they serve as a kind of prompt, preparing the potential reader for the story without limiting their imagination, allowing them to imagine the events and characters in their own way. Two parallel worlds emerge — that of the writer and the artist — correspondingly, two worldviews that allow for ethno-mental comparisons.

While the literary source reflects the national characteristics of Adyghe life and depicts the specific attributes of their daily life, these are missing from the graphic artist's illustration. The illustrator emphasizes the drama of the situation and the psychological state of the characters, highlighting them with the play of light and shadow.

A series of initial caps by artist V. I. Sapkin (*Stories*. Moscow, 1986, Sovetskaya Rossiya Publishing House) unfolds before the reader a coherent narrative about the fates of the characters in the story "I Will Call by Your Name" and the dramatic events in their lives. Small, lightly and freely sketched, hand-drawn typographic elements — the initial caps — play a dual role: narrative and decorative. The artist's genre-based approach to illustration required a careful selection of gestures, poses, and facial expressions. Despite the small size of the drawings, all the key plot points are clearly revealed. A well-designed *mise-en-scène*, realistic characters, and everyday details, all while using minimal artistic means and techniques — this is the Kabardian edition of A. Shogentsukov's novella "I Will Call You by Your Name" (ShchodzhentsyIkIu Iedem. *Ui tsIer fle sshchynts*. Nalchik, 1973, Elbrus Publishing House). Acting as a commentator, book illustrator V. I. Sirotintsev evaluates the actions of literary characters using visual means. Passing through the magic crystal of his imagination, the verbal text is transformed into a cycle of illustrations, which the author strives to subordinate to the style of the novella. As a result of the complex process of translating verbal language into visual language, every stroke, every spot or line, the contrast of white and black, or the consonance of their shades help to metaphorically comprehend the situation described by the author. (Fig. 5)

Another edition of the story "I Will Call You by Your Name" is illustrated very sparingly by graphic artist V. I. Beketov. The narrative outline of the literary text is reflected in dynamic pictorial frames. The drawings are narrative in nature, and the everyday life of the rural inhabitants of Kabarda is easily recognizable through individual interior objects.

It is noteworthy that the artist focuses not on the bright sides of the protagonists' lives, of which there are many, but on the shadowy, dramatic events, considering them decisive, determining their fates. A skillful balance of dark and light in the drawings helps the author convey the complex relationships between the characters. The limited illustrative material forced the graphic artist to pay more attention to the selection of compositional details and the structure of the plastic form.

The artist V. I. Levinson chose a unique method for illustrating the story "I Will Call You by Your Name." He conveyed the twists and turns of his characters' lives through in-depth psychological portraits, sketched with quick, sharp strokes. The main characters' faces are close-up, individualized and easily recognizable, and the play of light and shadow helps reveal deeply hidden and painfully experienced feelings. Despite the seemingly static nature of the images, the author achieves an inner expression. In each specific case, he manages to find the right mode to convey

the characters' psychological tension and the ontological distance between them. The seemingly randomly sketched lines that sculpt the image of the antihero Khapatchi, a man who thinks in outdated moral categories, testify to his uncontrollability and selfishness. The simplified drawing and tangled lines resonate with the character's incoherent thoughts and illogical actions and heighten the drama of the situation. Zalina's mournfully bowed head and fixed gaze emphasize her moral suffering. Despite the expressiveness of the characters' appearances, the complex existential issues raised by Adam Shogentsukov were not adequately reflected in the few full-page illustrations featuring social portraits of the story's main characters. The artist creates a state of emotional isolation for each of them, unlike in the literary text, where their fates are closely intertwined.

Adam Shogentsukov's story "I Will Call by Your Name" went through six editions in Kabardian and Russian, with a print run of nearly half a million copies, enormous even for the Soviet era. Such numbers have never been seen before or since. All this testifies to the high artistic merit of Adam Shogentsukov's works. Each newly published book associated with this classic of Kabardian literature immediately attracted a wide audience of fans and connoisseurs of his work. This requires a highly responsible approach to their work from the designer and illustrator.

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INTEGRATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE PROCESS OF CREATING COSTUME DESIGNS FOR THE FILM INDUSTRY OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines the principles of applying innovative technologies in the process of creating costume designs for the contemporary film industry of Kazakhstan. International experience in the implementation of digital tools is analyzed, and its significance for domestic professional practice is substantiated. The current state of film costume production in Kazakhstan is assessed, including infra-structural and organizational constraints. Directions for modernization and a prospective model for the transformation of the Kazakhstani film industry are proposed, aimed at developing a national visual language of cinema, optimizing production processes, and enhancing the competitiveness of Kazakhstan's film production.*

Keywords: *innovative technologies, film industry of Kazakhstan, costume design, costume production, digital prototype, additive technologies.*

Contemporary cinema represents a complex synthetic system that integrates artistic, technological, and production processes. The visual component of a film—particularly costume design—plays a crucial role in shaping the artistic image of a character and significantly influences the audience's perception of the narrative. In the context of the rapid development of digital technologies and the expanding capabilities of computer graphics, innovative costume design methods are becoming an essential part of the overall structure of film production. Today, the costume designer combines traditional craftsmanship skills with proficiency in digital tools that enable work in a virtual environment and the creation of complex on-screen images.

The purpose of this study is to analyze promising costume design methods for the contemporary film industry of Kazakhstan and to identify opportunities and

directions for integrating innovative digital technologies into domestic costume production practices.

In the global film industry, the development of costume designs actively employs methods such as three-dimensional modeling, digital scanning of actors, additive manufacturing (3D printing), and virtual material simulation. These methods reduce production cycles, enhance fitting accuracy and the realism of digital solutions, and expand artistic possibilities. They are widely used in major international studio projects—such as those produced by Marvel, Disney, Netflix, and others—where the combination of CGI and physical costumes forms a coherent visual world.

The application of digital costume design and modeling methods allows for:

- accelerating the costume development process through virtual fittings;
- reducing budgets by minimizing the number of physical mock-ups and prototypes;
- increasing accuracy and artistic expressiveness of costume designs;
- integrating national ornaments and historical elements into a digital environment;
- creating complex constructions, textures, and materials unattainable through traditional costume production methods;
- facilitating work with visual effects (VFX) and frame compositing.

The objective of the research is to assess the applicability of these technologies within the context of Kazakhstan's film industry and to formulate practical recommendations for their implementation.

At present, the film industry in Kazakhstan is undergoing a phase of active development. The visual products created by domestic producers enjoy significant demand among local audiences. Kazakhstani films are gaining international recognition, being showcased on global online cinemas and streaming platforms, and receiving prestigious awards. However, the processes involved in creating costume designs face a number of infrastructural and organizational constraints.

The study reveals that innovative costume design methods are applied extremely limitedly in domestic practice. Analysis of several contemporary Kazakhstani films confirms that digital tools are predominantly used for post-production tasks unrelated to costume creation—such as visual effects, spatial expansion of scenes, and location modification. According to open sources and interviews with costume designers, costume production largely relies on classical design and manufacturing methods, while digital prototyping, 3D modeling, and virtual visualization of costumes have not yet been integrated into the designer's workflow. In most cases, costumes are produced in theatrical workshops, sewing studios, commissioned from individual artisans, or rented. The «Kazakhfilm» Studio remains the largest costume storage center. However, despite its extensive collection, the

existing rental system is characterized by complex administrative procedures and limited access schedules, complicating the designers' work under tight production timelines. The dominance of a single supplier leads to reduced visual diversity and hinders the development of original costume concepts.

Thus, it can be concluded that, as of the end of 2025, there are no convincing case studies demonstrating the application of innovative technologies in film costume design and production in Kazakhstan. This slows down the work of designers and performers and increases project preparation timelines.

One of the key reasons for the limited implementation of innovative methods and digital technologies in costume design for contemporary Kazakhstani cinema is the insufficient technological equipment of specialized departments. A significant number of film studios, production centers, and workshops continue to operate within a traditional-and often outdated-material and technical framework that does not support the use of virtual prototyping software, 3D modeling, digital texturing, or additive manufacturing. The lack of specialized workstations, graphic tablets, scanning equipment, and licensed software significantly restricts costume designers' ability to adopt new approaches.

Another significant factor is the shortage of professional training in digital technologies for artistic and production-related professions. Existing educational programs, focused on traditional drawing, pattern construction, and costume production technologies, only partially reflect the requirements of contemporary film production processes. Industry professionals often lack competencies in 3D modeling, fabric simulation, and digital concept creation, which leads to the persistence of established methods and resistance to technological innovation.

An additional obstacle is the limited availability of research and methodological developments adapted to the conditions of Kazakhstani cinema. Unlike major international studios-where digital departments are integrated into unified production pipelines and based on meticulous planning-domestic projects are typically realized under constrained budgets and timelines, involving fragmented suppliers and contractors. This reduces producers' willingness to invest in experimental technological solutions. The absence of tested local models for digital costume workflows fosters perceptions of high costs and unjustified risks associated with innovation.

Finally, the lack of comprehensive infrastructure-including specialized laboratories, digital material libraries, databases of digital patterns, and archives of simulated fabrics-impedes the formation of sustainable practices for applying advanced technologies. As a result, transitioning to modern methods requires substantial initial investments, systematic training, and interdisciplinary collaboration, which have not yet become widespread in Kazakhstan's film industry.

At the same time, the experience of various international studios demonstrates that integrating innovative technologies into costume design expands artistic

possibilities, optimizes production cycles, and enhances the competitiveness of national cinema. In the context of Kazakhstan, these benchmarks are particularly relevant for the following reasons:

1. Limited resources and budgets can be compensated through digital prototyping and virtual fittings;
2. The need to develop a national visual language requires combining traditional craftsmanship with the flexibility of digital technologies;
3. Accelerated production is crucial amid the growing number of television and film projects;
4. The creation of digital costume archives ensures continuity, systematization, and accumulation of artistic experience.

A synthesis of international practices shows that innovative approaches to costume design are based on three key principles: integration of digital modeling, technological hybridization, and systematic digital archiving of costume solutions. This approach provides not only aesthetic advantages but also significantly reduces production risks, increases development speed, optimizes material costs, and forms sustainable institutional memory within the industry. For Kazakhstani cinema, orientation toward these case studies offers an opportunity to establish a modern methodological foundation for costume design capable of competing internationally while developing national artistic traditions in synergy with advanced technological tools.

As a result of the study, a methodological model for implementing innovations in costume design production processes for Kazakhstan's film industry was developed. This model is based on global trends in the digitalization of artistic and production processes, as well as on an analysis of existing constraints characteristic of Kazakhstani film production.

The model includes the following stages:

1. Educational and professional transformation stage;
2. Technological and infrastructural modernization stage;
3. Digitalization of creative and production processes stage;
4. Institutionalization and standardization stage;
5. Interdisciplinary and international integration stage.

At the initial stage, the key factor is the formation of professional competencies among costume designers, technologists, VFX specialists, and 3D artists. Retraining should include mastering digital tools for 3D modeling, fabric simulation, digital texturing, virtual fittings, and additive technologies. Particularly promising is the introduction of short-term intensive programs based on international educational standards, the integration of industrial software modules (Clo3D, Marvelous Designer, Blender, Substance 3D) into art university curricula, and the organization of continuous practice-oriented workshops at film studios. This stage fosters

professional competencies that enable specialists to work effectively within hybrid digital-traditional production environments.

Within this stage, a modular educational program entitled «Theater and Film Costume Design» was developed at the Temirbek Zhurgenov Kazakh National Academy of Arts. The program includes courses such as «3D Design of Historical Costume» and «3D Design of National Costume», with in-depth professional training in Clo 3D.

The next stage involves establishing specialized digital costume design laboratories within Kazakhstani film studios, equipped with high-performance workstations, graphic tablets, 3D scanning devices, and additive manufacturing tools. Such infrastructure enables the development of virtual costume designs, their integration into visual effects, or their subsequent transfer into physical form—thus creating costume prototypes in a phygital format.

The availability of equipment for scanning actors, fabrics, and historical artifacts contributes to the formation of digital databases that significantly enhance reconstruction accuracy and standardize the visual style of national film projects. Technological modernization is considered a prerequisite for transitioning from a craft-based model to a technologically supported production cycle. «Kazakh-film» Studio is the most suitable platform for implementing this project, although substantial financial support from the state or private sponsors would be required.

From a practical perspective, it is recommended to establish small digital costume laboratories within film studios, theatrical production organizations, or educational institutions. Equipping such laboratories with workstations, graphic tablets, 3D scanning tools, and 3D production equipment would create conditions for comprehensive use of digital technologies. In the absence of in-house infrastructure, cooperation with existing specialized workshops and rental services may be developed.

At the stage of digitalizing creative and production processes, technologies become an integrated part of artistic decision-making. Virtual fittings, fabric behavior simulation, and preliminary digital visualization of character images optimize the artistic decision-making process, reduce the number of physical mock-ups, improve artistic elaboration quality, and ensure consistency between the costume lineup and the film's overall visual narrative. Innovative practice involves a hybrid application of traditional tailoring methods and digital technologies, maintaining artistic expressiveness while reducing production costs. The introduction of digital prototypes also enhances interaction between costume, props, makeup, cinematography, and VFX departments.

For full implementation of these technologies, appropriate technical support is required. The use of workstations with modern graphics cards capable of complex fabric simulations and high-polygon modeling, at least 32 GB of RAM, and

high-speed storage devices is recommended. Professional-grade graphic tablets ensure precision in digital drawing, while monitors with extended color gamut allow accurate evaluation of textures and materials. Software recommendations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 — Software and digital tools for costume design

Software / Tool	Primary Functions	Comments / Recommended Use
Clo3D	Creation of patterns, virtual garment samples, virtual fittings, professional costume development.	Features an integrated workflow from 2D pattern construction to realistic 3D visualization with fabric simulation.
Marvelous Designer	Rapid 3D modeling of costumes and garments, visualization, creation of digital concept art for films and VFX.	Designed for film and animation; allows dressing digital characters and observing fabric behavior in motion without physical tailoring.
Adobe Substance 3D	Material creation, texturing, surface detailing, achieving realistic appearance of costumes in 3D.	After base modeling in Clo3D or Marvelous Designer, Substance 3D adds realism through fabric texture, wear effects, and surface details, which are critical for on-screen aesthetics.
Blender	General 3D modeling, scene creation, visual effects, rendering, integration of costumes into digital environments and VFX pipelines.	A free, versatile tool suitable for a full production cycle—from modeling to animation and visual effects.
3D Scanning, 3D Printing	Creation of physical costume prototypes, accessories, and props; rapid transition from digital to physical production.	Used when costumes must exist physically, such as historical or fantasy costumes, armor, or complex structural elements.

Despite technological readiness, sustainable innovation implementation is impossible without establishing a regulatory framework. At this stage, a system of standards should be developed to define requirements for digital costume documentation formats, digital pattern storage procedures, data transfer methods to visual effects departments, and principles of interaction among professional teams. Simultaneously, a national digital library of historical and ethnographic costume designs should be created to systematize Kazakhstan’s visual cultural heritage and ensure its accessibility for researchers and designers. Institutionalization supports continuous innovation and consolidates technological culture within the industry.

The final stage involves developing strategic cooperation between Kazakhstani film studios and international production companies, educational centers, and technology developers. Partnership projects, joint residencies, professional exchanges, and participation in global industry initiatives foster a sustainable professional outlook, facilitate the adaptation of new technological solutions, and integrate Kazakhstan's film industry into the global context. This format ensures continuous methodological renewal and stimulates creative competition.

The proposed methodological model demonstrates a comprehensive approach to integrating innovations into costume design for Kazakhstan's film industry. It is oriented toward gradual yet systematic transformation of the sector, based on fundamental principles of digitalization, professional training, technological equipment, and institutional sustainability. Implementation of this model will enable the national film industry to achieve a new level of artistic and technological competitiveness, ensuring the integration of Kazakhstani film projects into the international cultural space.

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EXPRESSIVE SYNTAX IN AUSTRALIAN SPORTS MEDIA TEXTS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the main expressive syntactic devices in modern Australian sports media texts. Examples containing parenthetical phrases of various types, inversion, elliptical and nominative constructions, interrogative and exclamatory sentences, repetitions are analyzed; some features of punctuation marks are mentioned, which make a certain contribution to the emotionality of the sports articles under discussion.*

Keywords: *expressive syntax, Australian media, sports media texts, the English language*

Expressive syntax plays an important role in the creation of media texts, including those devoted to sports. In this article, we will consider the most common expressive syntax devices in Australian sports media texts.

The analysis of the research material, which included sports-related articles from Australian websites (www.ftbl.com.au, bicyclingaustralia.com.au, www.golfaustralia.com.au, www.ambmag.com.au, www.insidesport.com.au, www.ridemedias.com.au), allowed us to conclude that expressive syntax is represented in it sufficiently.

In the example below, we observe the complex use of various means of creating expressiveness at the syntactic level, namely parenthetical insertions of various types, an elliptical construction and a rhetorical question:

Late last month, on October 29, it was made public that White will join the Movistar Team, as co-head of the ‘Racing Department’ (weird name — do they have a ‘Training Department’?) with Chente García Acosta. Meanwhile, Bannan is employed as the high performance director at the Singapore Cycling Federation. 1.

Punctuation marks in this passage also deserve attention: these sentences contain quotation marks, a question mark, dashes, brackets, commas for showing the borders of parentheses, which also affect the emotionality of the text in which they are used.

In the following fragment, we see interrogative, elliptical, nominative sentences, parallel constructions, an abundance of question marks, dashes and colons:

“A proportion of our fans? What does that mean?”

“What proportion? 50 per cent? 20 per cent? One per cent? That’s fine, people are allowed to feel the way they do.

“But I think I’ve been consistent and really strong in my beliefs that it’s important for this football club not to look for silver bullets to get to where we want to, it’s hard work, it’s resilience, it’s quality, not to fall for any false dawns — and know what real success looks like: trophies. 2.

All of these expressive syntax devices make a certain contribution to attracting the reader’s attention, imitating spoken speech, setting a certain pace of reading, and helping to highlight the necessary information.

The example below shows a combination of parenthetical phrases of various lengths, marked with commas, dashes and brackets; the colon allows the author to place additional emphasis on an important part of the message:

One thing is certain, however: leading to its WorldTour debut in 2012, White was instrumental in setting up the team, together with former general manager Shayne Bannan — another unexpected departure — who was officially shown the door on July 1, 2020, following a botched takeover deal with Spanish not-for-profit Manuela Fundación. (Read: Shayne Bannan: Gone, But Not Forgotten) 1.

In the following excerpts, we observe the use of inversion, which helps the author to bring a special emotionality to the utterance:

Not only do the top 50 advance to the BMW Championship, they are assured of being in all the \$20m (\$A30.6m) Signature events for next year. 3.

Never before has there been a change of this magnitude on the men’s side at GreenEdge Cycling. 1.

The exclamatory sentence is traditionally considered one of the most expressive syntactic devices. Exclamations are quite rare in Australian sports media texts, but their use undoubtedly makes a special contribution to bringing emotions to the articles under consideration. Here is one example:

Announcing the long-awaited release of the World Championship Winning bike! 4.

Repetitions, namely repetitions of homogeneous sentence members and parallelism, are also included in the research material as a means of creating expressiveness:

“Featuring the finest handmade, bespoke and premium bicycle, component and apparel brands from around the country and the world, SPOKEN is an opportunity to savour the craft, design, innovation and performance, celebrate the communities and enjoy the culture of the bicycle.” 5.

They’re not orthodox, not traditional, not expected. 6.

As Broad acknowledged in some of his final words as a Test cricketer, “It’s been the most enjoyable series, the most entertaining series, the most edge of the seat series that I can remember.” 6.

Lyon admitted, “I’ve been absolutely shattered. I’ve been in tears. I’ve been upset. I’ve been hurting.” 7.

As is well known, repetitions are intended to attract attention, enhance the effect of the use of words and constructions that are important from the author's point of view, and increase the persuasiveness of the message.

Speaking about expressive syntax, the punctuation features of the analyzed texts should also be mentioned.

Thus, the comma, along with its usual use of separating parts of sentences and homogeneous members of sentences, is also used to mark expressive syntactical devices, particularly parenthetical insertions. Here are some examples:

Surprisingly, this was the most wickets taken in Tests by an Australian off spinner.⁷

There were many key factors, of course, including the weather, the crowds, the injuries, the individual successes and failures and the varying tactics. ⁶

Brackets and dashes are also frequently used in the function of indicating the boundaries of parentheses. They allow the author to clearly separate additional, explanatory information and facilitate the perception of a lengthy statement, for example:

Anthony Quayle, Spain's David Puig and Portugal's Ricardo Gouveia head a packed leaderboard at 13 under while Min Woo Lee (12 under) and Marc Leishman (11 under) are there too. ⁸

Cycling data website Procyclingstats listed 15 names — exactly half the 30-rider Team Jayco AlUla men's roster from 2025 — as not having their contracts renewed or were retiring. ¹

Semicolon is typically used in long sentences to distinguish their parts clearly and distinctly, for example:

Some have had short but successful spells here; others have called England home for most of their career. ⁹

However, semicolons have also been found in short statements. The example below shows a semicolon being used to separate elliptical parallel constructions in a heading, probably with the purpose of drawing attention to such an unusual construction:

Lyon wounded; Lions tamed ⁷.

It is also worth noting the fairly frequent use of the colon, mainly to highlight important information, summarize, explain the given material and attract the reader's attention, for example:

UPDATE: Round One has been suspended due to the weather. ¹⁰

With all this mind, and Postecoglou unwittingly caught in the middle of an unseemly internecine spat, the scenario is this: Arsenal lead City by a single point with two games left. ²

Rediscovering the why: Sydney cycling adventure ¹¹.

Another mark that influences the expressiveness of a text is the ellipsis (three dots). This punctuation mark is used to indicate pauses or understatement:

“It’s not like I’m out there thinking about winning ... it’s ticking all the boxes and doing a better job of the things in the boxes,” he said of his thought process. 8.

The above excerpt also contains quotation marks, another punctuation device that plays an important role in creating Australian sports media texts, as they are usually full of quotations that represent both full-fledged sayings (as in the example above) and their components:

Adam Scott won’t overthink a five-year title drought, admitting he still needs a final-round “beauty” after putting himself in the frame for a third Australian PGA Championship. 8.

Lyon, himself, called it, “a decent tear in my right calf”. 7.

It is obvious that quotation marks, when used to frame statements of athletes, coaches and other persons directly related to the content of the articles, enhance the emotionality and persuasiveness of the texts under discussion.

Overall, it can be concluded that Australian sports media texts employ a variety of expressive syntactic devices that make a special contribution to persuading and entertaining readers, attracting their attention, evoking certain emotions, and creating the images and impressions desired by the author.

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EXPRESSIVE SYNTAX IN BRITISH SPORTS MEDIA TEXTS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the main expressive syntactic devices in modern British sports media texts. The punctuation features of modern British sports media texts are also mentioned as they fall within the scope of expressive syntax. The conclusion is made about the most common types of expressive syntactic devices and punctuation marks that contribute to the creation of informative and emotional sports articles.*

Keywords: *expressive syntax, punctuation, British media, sports media texts, the English language*

It is well known, that British media texts contain a variety of syntactic constructions. Expressive syntactic means usually play a special role in them. Let us consider the features of expressive syntax in British sports reports from sports-related Internet sites (www.fourfourtwo.com, www.runnersworld.com/uk, sports-insight.co.uk, www.horseandrideruk.com, www.nationalclubgolfer.com, www.sportspro.com).

The analysis of the research material allows us to conclude that one of the most common means of creating expressiveness in British sports texts is parenthesis, which indicates the author's thoughts, evaluation, and the structuring of the information presented, as well as explanations and clarifications. Here are some examples:

Firstly, the answer to this question is going to be different for everyone, from seasoned half marathon runners chasing PBs and breaking records, to those crossing the line for the first time. 5.

At the end of the game, win, lose or half, you shake hands and return to the clubhouse for a cup of tea (or something stronger, if appropriate). 1.

The men's half marathon world record is an astounding 56:42, set by Jacob Kiplimo of Uganda at Barcelona Half Marathon — a SuperHalf event — on 16 February 2025. Kiplimo smashed the previous record of 57:30 clocked by Ethiopia's Yomif Kejelcha at Valencia Half Marathon — also a SuperHalf event — in October 2024, taking off an impressive 48 seconds. 4.

As can be seen from the examples given, parenthetical insertions can be marked with commas, brackets and dashes. They can vary in length (a single-word or a multi-word parenthesis) and position in the sentence (at the beginning, in the middle, or at the end of the statement).

The analysis of the research material revealed the use of interrogative sentences, one more expressive syntactic device used by the author in order to simulate a conversation with the reader, which undoubtedly attracts the recipient's attention and affects the persuasiveness and emotionality of the article:

The good news? There's plenty horse owners can do. 8.

What is a 'good' half marathon finish time? We explore the data to discover the average time it takes UK runners to cover 13.1 miles 5.

Looking for every team to have qualified for the 2026 World Cup? The tournament has been expanded to 48 teams and sides are sealing their spots 6.

Repetition is also a fairly common syntactic device that adds expressiveness to English sports reports. Repetitions of homogeneous parts of a sentence are particularly prominent in the research material:

Women's Health is deeply passionate about helping women of all ages lead a happy, healthy and fit lifestyle. 4.

Prevention, early detection and vaccination together can help reduce the impact of strangles." 8.

Parallel constructions are also widespread in the studied British sports media texts, for example:

Lots of desire, lots of heart, lots of stars and stripes — but not quite as much in the way of form. 7.

Finished Friday's foursomes in underwhelming fashion and admitted that he had let the hecklers get to him, which was always a concern. Recovered well on Saturday to ensure that the Vik & Bob combo did not go home empty-handed. Left with the unenviable task of playing in what became the anchor match, securing a courageous half at the end. 7.

It should be noted that grammatically correct, complete, extended sentences within the same text often alternate with short, elliptical, incomplete, colloquial constructions, as in the following example:

Oh dear. Was one half of a wretched foursomes duo alongside Morikawa. They managed to draw Fleetwood and McIlroy twice, which was especially unfortunate. When Hovland's neck injury prevented him from playing the singles, English's was the name in the infamous envelope. 7.

As is known, the ellipsis presented in this passage also falls within the scope of expressive syntax and allows one to make a statement brief, informative and emotional.

As for the punctuation of British sports reports, in addition to the already mentioned question marks, dashes, brackets and commas used with parentheses, it is

worth highlighting exclamatory sentences, which are traditionally considered the most expressive syntactic devices:

Jane laughed, “He’s a huge character — he lives at home with four goats, three chickens — his favourite one is called Judy — and two kittens!” 2.

Quotation marks also refer to prominent expressive punctuation devices in the research material. They are used to show direct speech, quotes? or excerpts from them. Here are some examples:

“We are in a good place,” he said. “It’s not a done deal. The last few outstanding items are always the hardest ones, otherwise they wouldn’t be outstanding.” 3.

Being able to say ‘I’ve completed a half marathon’ is just as much of an achievement as completing it in a ‘good’ time. 4.

ATP chairman hopes to get approval at ATP Finals for non-binding “short-form” agreement to create and implement new entity. 3.

The use of ellipsis (three dots) is also noteworthy. It is believed that ellipses are intended to simulate pauses before important information:

Whether it’s your very first foray into the half marathon distance or you’re gunning for a new PB, knowing what to aim for can help you to set a goal for those 13.1 miles — and motivate you through your training. Here’s what we found... What is the average half marathon finish time in the UK? According to RunRepeat’s data, the average half marathon finish time in the UK, counting men and women together, is 2:02:43. Separately, for men, the average half marathon finish time is 1:55:26 — and for women, the average half marathon finish time is 2:11:57. 4.

Another punctuation mark found in British sports media texts is the colon, which functions include summarising, highlighting the main points, and contributing to the creation of short, informative messages:

RYDER CUP REPORT CARDS: TEAM EUROPE 6.

Strangles on the rise: why every horse owner should stay alert 8.

The effect of colons is particularly evident in headings and subheadings, as it is seen in the examples provided. However, sentences in the main body of articles were also found where colons are used to highlight important summary information, as well as the author’s conclusion, which is particularly emphasized:

The club seems to have looked at the level of investment made and how well Chelsea coped despite playing Thursdays and Sundays last season but they’ve missed the bigger picture: the Champions League is a brutal competition unlike the Conference League. 7.

An infrequent but equally important punctuation mark in the research material is the semicolon, which is used to separate long sentences, making the information easier to understand:

He encouraged Estevao when he chose to shoot instead of pass; he tried all afternoon to catch the eye of goalkeeper Robert Sanchez to help build from the back, even when his team was a man short. 7.

In general, based on the analysis of the research material, the following conclusion can be drawn: British sports articles contain a variety of expressive syntactic structures and punctuation marks that contribute significantly to the creation of attention-grabbing, well-structured, informative, and emotional media texts.

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INFERENCE OF PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS FROM A VERB-PREDICATE

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Abstract. *Verb meanings encode rich information about typical event participants. This study examines whether personal characteristics are systematically inferred from verb-predicate meaning by non-native speakers of English in rapid processing conditions. The results support the integration of verb semantics with person perception research and indicate that verb-trait associations constitute shared cultural knowledge structures automatically activated during language comprehension.*

Keywords: *verb-predicate meaning, agent concept, feature-based prototypes, personal characteristics*

Introduction

The key idea of cognitive linguistics is that the meaning of words represents the way people perceive and process information from the outer world. Word meaning is a kind of storage unit for certain knowledge. As the verb is a special part of speech that denotes events or situations in time-space continuum, it should store certain information about the participants of a denoted event. My research is focused on the question whether the verb meaning stores knowledge about a person. The object of the study is verbs that denote social interaction. Most verbs in this group reflect conventionalized socio-cultural patterns of judging a person's character by a type of action, for e.g. A person who welcomes another person is (typically) hospitable.

Theoretical background

Previous studies show different views on what type of information becomes a constituent part of verb meaning. Valency theory developed by Lucien Tenier (Tesnière) is based on the idea that verbs structure sentences by binding specific elements (complements, actants) as atoms do (Tesnière 2015). Further works on event structure represented by verb meaning investigate the semantic nature of event participants in terms of deep cases (Fillmore 1972, Cook 1989, Petruck 2013), semantic or thematic roles (Jackendoff 2002, Rappaport Hovav 2010, Croft 2012).

Studying predicate semantics, D. Dowty describes a set of functional semantic features that build the categories of Protoagents and Protopatience (Dowty 1991). Protoagent is active, volitional, autonomous, mobile, having the ability to feel, consciousness, the ability to influence another participant. Protopatience is subordinate, stative, influenced by other participants. Such features as activity, power/energy, volition, consciousness, self-control, creativity are the prototypical features of a person. Thus, a person is typically represented as an agent case complementing verb-predicate. Even when the verb is not combined with agentive subjects, some of the characterizing features are activated “to draw family resemblance” (Rosch & Mervis 1975). For e.g. The door opens could be interpreted in terms of conceptual metaphor: the door is endowed with volition, self-control and power to initiate the action.

While some researchers (Михайлова 1998) describe cases of incorporation of an agent (e.g. 1), others (Лебедева 2010) consider that there is no agent-incorporation as an agent is formally represented by a noun or a pronoun in an English utterance, in comparison with, let say, instrument incorporation (e.g. 2).

(1) bark (of a dog). The dog barks. (But not *the pig barks).

(2) walk (on foot). He walked 5 miles (= went on foot).

I join the latter group, however, assert that an agent isn't incorporated in its full semantics but rather as a set of characterizing features. A set of features that are markers of a human-being (a person) are mainly the abilities and functional parts of the spiritual or physical body: intellect or mind, emotion, will, speech apparatus and organs of perception etc. However, within the category these features are rarely distinctive. Certain verbs foreground some features by denoting a type of action, for e.g. think implies that a potential agent is attributed some intellectual ability. The expression “Computer thinks” implies the presence of intelligence in an electronic device (a case of conceptual metaphor “anthropomorphism”). So in reconstructing the part of verb meaning identified as inner case or thematic role (e.g. agent), we deal not with a substantive semantic component but with an attributive semantic component that could be included in the structure of verb meaning and inferred in speech processing.

A similar idea is developed by McRae, Ferretti, and Amyote (1997), who view agents/patients as feature-rich verb-specific prototypes derived from world knowledge. Accordingly, thematic roles are real concepts activated during verb-predicate comprehension. McRae et al. provided empirical evidence for immediate use of role knowledge in verb-predicate processing. Thirty-two native English-speaking psychology undergraduates from the University of Western Ontario performed feature generation tasks on 20 transitive verbs stimuli, 10 for agent roles (e.g. “someone who frightens people”) and 10 for patient roles (e.g. “someone who is arrested”). A total of 3,530 responses were collected, yielding 1,573 distinct features

(800 for agents, 773 for patients). Of these features, 46% were listed by at least 2 respondents and 28% by at least 3 respondents — consistency rates comparable to object concept norming studies (McRae et al. 2005).

Method

Following McRae’s research group, I have conducted an experiment to test whether the features of a person are inferred from verb-predicate meaning with similar consistency by non-native speakers and in different experimental conditions. A survey was designed on psytoolkit.com platform as a directed associative experiment with a 30-minute time limit for each response. The list of stimuli targeted 15 English verbs: deceive, donate, feel, fight, forgive, giggle, help, protect, rule, save, shout, think, travel, win, work. Each verb was put in an unfinished phrase “A person who VERB ...”. The verb-predicate was given a graphic focus as the central stimulus for semantic inference. The agent was presented as a generalized category “a person”. Transitive verb-predicates were combined with an object of a generalized category “people”. The verbs of a more general meaning (such as work, feel) were given a modifier “a lot” to stress typicality of action. The participants were asked to answer with the first characteristics of a person that comes to their mind within 30 seconds. After the time limit the screen changed to the next stimulus.

72 undergraduate students from the Belarusian State University of Foreign Languages participated in the survey. Participants were non-native English speakers with self-reported English competence levels: 1) the ability to express any idea without difficulty, 2) to keep conversation without much difficulty, and 3) the ability to communicate on everyday topics.

Results and discussion

The participants successfully completed the task with a high response rate. Of the 1,080 possible responses 945 valid responses were collected (87.5%), indicating that the task was comprehensible and accessible to non-native speakers of English operating under time constraints. The 12.5% non-response rate varied across verbs. Two stimuli (“A person who deceives people”, “A person who forgives”) showed higher rates of empty responses, potentially reflecting greater cognitive difficulty or ambiguity in inferring prototypical agent characteristics for these actions.

To compare the data with McRae, Ferretti, and Amyote’s (1997) results, I examined inter-subject consistency by calculating the frequency with which participants produced identical or semantically equivalent features for each verb. Synonymous responses (e.g., “smart,” “clever,” “intelligent”) were normalized under a single label to ensure accurate frequency counts. Despite the limited response time (30 seconds vs. 2 minutes in McRae et al. 2007) and the non-native language competence the participants demonstrated substantial agreement in their feature attributions.

Across the 15 verbs, an average of 52.3 unique feature types were generated per verb (ranged 35–68). The features listed by three or more participants accounted for 38.7% of the total unique features, indicating moderate to high inter-subject consistency. This consistency rate is comparable to McRae's findings for thematic role concepts (28–30% for features listed by ≥ 3 of 16 subjects) and to object concept norming studies (27–42%; McRae et al 2005).

High-consensus verbs. For example, 65% of participants produced the feature “kind” for the stimulus “A person who helps people”. The respondents inferred from the stimulus “A person who works a lot” the features “workaholic” (49%) and “hard-working” (27%), which corresponds to 76% agreement on work-related dispositional attributions. The stimulus “A person who donates people” had the feature “rich” in 50% of responses. The stimulus “A person who rules people” elicited “bossy” from 56% of participants, suggesting a consistently negative evaluation of dominance behavior.

These high-consensus results indicate that certain verb predicates activate tightly constrained mental representations (concepts) of prototypical agents. The conceptual structure underlying these verbs appears to incorporate not merely semantic selectional restrictions (such as animacy), but rich, culturally shared knowledge about the dispositional characteristics, motivation, and social roles of typical event participants.

Moderate-consensus verbs showed distributed but still structured feature production. Particularly, the stimulus “A person who wins” elicited “strong” (29%), “confident” (15%), and “smart/clever” (13%) responses, reflecting multiple co-activated competence dimensions. The participants frequently inferred features “strong” (33%), “brave” (23%), and “kind” (19%) from the stimulus “A person who protects people”, suggesting a prototype combining physical capability, courage, and prosocial motivation. These verbs appear to activate several highly salient features rather than a single dominant prototype of an agent.

Low-consensus verbs exhibited greater variability across inferred features. In particular, the stimulus “A person who thinks a lot” produced more varied responses distributed across “smart/clever” (34%), “philosopher” (16%), “overthinker” (11%), and “wise” (8%). It may indicate that participants constructed different interpretational frames: some emphasizing intellectual capacity, others emphasizing rumination or anxiety. The stimulus “A person who forgives” generated numerous low-frequency responses, while 21% of participants left this task blank, 33% inferred the characteristics “kind”.

The observed variability in consensus levels parallels McRae et al.'s (1997) observation that some thematic roles are better defined than others depending on the distribution and inter-exemplar similarity of typical role fillers. Verbs whose agents share many overlapping features (e.g. helpers are kind) produce high-consensus prototypes. Verbs whose semantic interpretations are more context-dependent produce lower consensus.

Conclusion

These findings extend the observation of McRae et al. (1997) that thematic role concepts are verb-specific and feature-rich, demonstrating that even simple verb predicates (without full sentential context) are sufficient to trigger consistent person perception inferences in a limited time of cognitive processing. The verb-predicate meaning is not merely a matter of abstract semantic features or thematic role assignments, but is deeply intertwined with person's perception processes. When language users encounter a verb describing human action, they appear to automatically activate rich conceptual knowledge about the dispositional characteristics, personality traits, and social identities of prototypical agents. This activation occurs rapidly and with substantial inter-subject agreement, suggesting these verb-trait associations are part of shared cultural knowledge structures. The study of specified features of a person in the verb meaning opens new perspectives for language analysis and modeling personality images through event description.

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BUDDHISM AS A RELIGION: THE ABSENCE OR PRESENCE OF A SOCIAL ORIENTATION

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Abstract: *Buddhism, which originated over 2,500 years ago, is traditionally viewed as a religion focused primarily on individual spiritual liberation. Some scholarly interpretations argue that Buddhism is unconnected to social and political processes and does not cause social unrest. This paper analyzes the main Buddhist teachings based on Pali sources to identify their social orientation. It is shown that, despite its emphasis on personal practice, Buddhism contains a developed system of social ethics regulating family relations, economic activity, public morality, and principles of just governance.*

Keywords: *Buddhism; social ethics; Pali Canon; morality; Eightfold Path; society*

I. Introduction

In scholarly literature, Buddhism is often described as a religion unrelated to the social sphere and social transformation. This approach is particularly represented in the works of Max Weber, who argued that Buddhism does not shape social and political goals. However, this understanding requires critical reconsideration. The purpose of this paper is to analyze the main Buddhist texts and show that Buddhism, in addition to individual liberation, places significant emphasis on social harmony and the moral order of society. Buddhism can simply be translated as the teachings of the Buddha, which are regarded as dhamma, and it is believed that anyone who follows the Buddha's spiritual path, that is, the eightfold noble path, will attain the

true goal. The Buddha's teaching can be summarized as follows: "sabbapapassa" akaranam kusalassa upasampada, sacitta-pariyodapanam etam buddhana Sasanah—to abstain from all unwholesome actions, to perform wholesome actions, and to purify one's mind—is the teaching of the Buddhas. The essence of the verse is that it is very important for the Buddha's disciples, such as monks, nuns, novices, and devoted men and women, to follow the path of Dhamma and the footprints of the Buddha, and to practice the same. Buddhism is a great religion that always cares for the group of people, that is, society.

In contrast, Max Weber said that "Buddhism was not associated with any movement, did not exist alongside it, and did not set itself any social or political goals." According to this statement, Buddhism has no social concern. This is completely incorrect and misunderstood by this scholar. In my understanding, based on Pali literature, it is impossible for Buddhism to be unrelated to social issues. The reason is that the Buddhist religion encompasses all aspects of social life, such as family life, community life, ethics, personal and socio-economic development, social education, and political issues. Furthermore, we can understand that Buddhist teachings are applied to various social aspects, namely: Buddhist stratification of society, the social significance of the five precepts, Buddhist views on morality, ethics, and economics, Buddhism and peace, the environment, and human rights.

II. Literature review

M. Weber's research emphasizes the ascetic and individualistic nature of Buddhism. At the same time, modern Buddhological works (R. Gombrich, D. Kalyupahana, Bhikkhu Bodhi) point to the social significance of Buddhist ethics. The Pali Canon, including the Sigalovada Sutta, the Cakkavattisihanada Sutta, and the Agganyada Sutta, contains direct references to social duties, economic norms, and principles of righteous governance. The spiritual life of Buddhists is often described as three trainings (ti sikkha), such as training in moral virtues (sila sikkha), mental concentration (samadhi sikkha) and wisdom (panya sikkha). The model of the three trainings leads us from our present state through the cultivated state to the liberated state of the highest mind. The heart of the Buddha's teachings is the eightfold noble path, which can be applied to both lay life and the life of a monk. They are: (1) Samma ditthi — right view, (2) Samma sankappa — right thought, (3) Samma vaka — right speech, (4) Samma Ajiva — right way of life, (5) Samma kammanta — right action, (6) Samma vayama — right effort, (7) samma sati — right mindfulness and (8) samma samadhi — right concentration.

The factors of the eight paths are divided into three groups: the moral discipline group (silakkhandha), consisting of right speech, right action, and right livelihood; the concentration group (samadhikkhandha), consisting of right effort, right

mindfulness, and right concentration; and the wisdom group (pannakkhandha), consisting of right view and right intention.

Moral discipline is essential and important for a harmonious, peaceful, and happy society. Sila is the foundation of all good qualities. The Pali term “sila” translates as virtue and moral conduct, which is the practice of restraining one’s physical and verbal behavior. Sila is the foundation for developing concentration (samadhi) and wisdom (pañña).

Buddhists willingly follow a set of training rules to improve their standard of living. Lay people — men and women— observe the Five Precepts (pancha-sila), sometimes observing the Eight Precepts for intensive meditation practice on uposatha day. Novices (samanera) and nuns (samaneri) observe the Ten Precepts (dasa-sila). A highly ordained monk (bhikkhu) follows the 227 Bhikkhu Rules. Patimokkha; a nun (bhikkhuni) must follow the 311 rules of a bhikkhuni Patimokkha. In any society, strength is truly necessary as a primary ethical guide and a condition for happiness in one’s own life, as mentioned above.

The five precepts (panca-sila) are as follows: (1) Abstaining from killing or causing harm to living beings, (2) Abstaining from taking what is not given and stealing, (3) Abstaining from sexual harassment, (4) Abstaining from any false speech, and (5) Abstaining from intoxicating drugs, alcoholic drinks, fermented drinks, and anything that causes carelessness.

Thus, we can clearly see that the five commandments are intended for self-restraint and self-control over our bodies and speech. The first three commandments are fulfilled through improper or unhealthy bodily actions, and the fourth through improper or unhealthy communication, such as lying, idle talk, harsh remarks, and gossip. The fifth commandment warns against carelessness, especially drunkenness and drug addiction, which make it difficult to observe the other four commandments.

In abhisanda In the Buddha’s sutta, the disciples of noble people refrain from the above-mentioned five types of activity. By doing so, one frees an unlimited number of beings from danger, hostility, and oppression; one gains a share of limitless freedom from danger, hostility, and oppression. There are five types of this benefit that one who possesses virtue can achieve. They are as follows: (1) obtaining worldly goods or wealth, (2) spreading a good name abroad, (3) the ability to attend meetings without fear and hesitation, (4) dying without embarrassment, and (5) achieving a happy state after death. Proper observance of the five precepts endows us with tolerance and compassion for others, charity and generosity, self-control and contentment, honesty and peacefulness, and mindfulness. These qualities are the foundation and source of existence for a healthy society. These qualities allow us, humans and all living beings, to live harmoniously and productively together, without harming ourselves or others.

According to Ambalathika-Rahulovada According to the Sutta and Kalama Sutta, any activity performed with alobha, adosha, and amoha is called a wholesome action (kusala). However, if it is performed with lobha, dosha, and moha, it is called an unwholesome action, or akusala. Therefore, Buddhism advises how to maintain good behavior, and a person must be trained to become a moral person. In society, happiness depends on the behavior of people. If people do not have moral behavior, they will live like animals. And if there is no morality in society, then society will turn into hell. Therefore, Buddhism focuses on morality and ethics for society.

According to Sigalovada in the Sutta, the Buddha outlined the worldly code of ethics and social responsibility. There are five tasks each person must perform according to their duties: parents, son and daughter, teacher and student, husband and wife, friend and colleague, slave, servant, worker, hermit, and religious preacher. Furthermore, the Buddha mentioned how to live righteously in accordance with the Dhamma. In the Mahamangala Sutta and the Vanija The Buddha prohibited lay Buddhists from engaging in five types of trade and deprived them of the opportunity to earn a living, which is the seventh step on the path. These include: trade in weapons, people, meat (including raising animals for slaughter), intoxicants, harmful drugs, and poisons.

Pattakamma The sutta shows how to properly use wealth (pancha bhoganam adiya), namely: (1) for personal and family use to support parents, spouse, children, servants and visiting family friends and colleagues, (2) for the benefit of friends (including entertaining guests and clients, (3) invest in security and insurance. (4) Five-fold offering (pancha bali) made to relatives, guests, the deceased, the government as payment of taxes, etc., (5) to support worthy religious activities in the field of Dhamma.

III. Research methodology

The work uses:

- textual analysis of the Pali suttas,
- comparative method (comparison of the individual and social aspects of Buddhism),
- hermeneutic approach to the interpretation of Buddhist ethics.

IV. Comparative analysis

On the one hand, Buddhism does emphasize personal practice — ethics (sīla), concentration (samādhi), and wisdom (paññā). On the other hand, these practices have social consequences: observing the five precepts, right livelihood, and moral speech form the foundation of a peaceful and stable society. Thus, in Buddhism, individual liberation is not opposed to social responsibility.

Dighajan The sutta explains the four foundations of worldly well-being, which are related to society, there are four worldly joys of the householder (gihi sukha), which are described in the same way as in the Anana Sutta.

Utthana sampada, which means diligence and joy of possession, faith. It may be related to the joy of possession (atthi sukha). When you work hard and honestly for something, you experience joyful satisfaction from what you have earned. Arakkha Sampada, which means “to protect one’s hard-earned wealth.” To ensure that it is not lost or destroyed, and that it is well protected from natural disasters, thieves, legal problems, and exploitation. In this way, one can truly enjoy one’s wealth (bhoga sukha) with loved ones and friends and to make merit, as well as to support the work of dhamma, and so on. kalyana mittata, which means spiritual friendship or the joy of immaculate wisdom. In essence, this is how true Buddhist practitioners relate to each other, that is, from the perspective of spiritual well-being based on faith, moral character, compassion, and wisdom. In such relationships, there is the joy of immaculateness (anavajja sukha).

Sama jivitata, which means a balanced life or the joy of being debt-free. This leads to good economics, that is, maintaining a healthy social and financial order in the home and community. A person spends money within their means and at the same time enjoys the beneficial benefits of their own wealth together with loved ones, friends, and others, as well as with a deep commitment to working in Dhamma and personal development.

V. Research results

The analysis showed that:

- Buddhist morality regulates the behavior of an individual in society.
- The teaching on right living touches on economic and social issues.
- Buddhist texts contain models of social harmony and righteous government.
- Buddhism promotes the reduction of social tension through ethical self-control of the individual.

VI. Conclusion

Buddhism is not a religion isolated from the social sphere. Although its ultimate goal is individual liberation, Buddhist teachings include a developed system of social ethics aimed at harmonious human coexistence. Therefore, the assertion that Buddhism is disconnected from society and does not inspire social responsibility is one-sided and incomplete. Buddhism continues to play an important role in the moral and social development of society.

In addition, there are many suttas in the Tipitaka such as the Agganyaya Suttas devoted to economic, social development, political problems, and so on. In the Chakkavattisihanada the sutta shows how the king righteously rules the country in

accordance with the Dhamma. This is an excellent example for the government, which should spread the Dhamma throughout the country. In summary, Buddhism is an excellent religion that always connects with society and the individual. One should study the Buddha's teachings to properly know and understand the Dhamma. Thus, Buddhism is a religion that has a social focus and plays an important role in society and its development.

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